

> DESIRE6G <

**D5.3: Final report on evaluation
results and proof of concept
demonstrations**

HEU 6G SNS JU Project

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Authors	Asim Zoukarni, Francisco Vogt, Anestis Dalgkitsis, Cyril Hsu, Jose Zerna Torres, Chrysa Papagianni (UVA), Juan José Vegas Olmos, Amelia Pakouline-Navarro (NV), Carlos J. Bernardos, Adam Zahir, Sandra Álvarez, Maria Molina (UC3M), Francesco Paolucci, Michelangelo Guaitolini, Rana Abu Bakar (CNIT), Attila Mihály, Gergely Pongrácz (ERI-HU), Michele Gucciardo (NEC), Anastassios Nanos, Christos Panagiotou, Konstantinos Papazafeiropoulos, Maria Rafaela Gkeka, Anastasia Mallikopoulou, Panagiotis Mavrikos, Maria Goutha, Charalampos Mainas (NUBIS), Chathuranga Weeraddana (UOU), Luis Velasco, Marc Ruiz, Jaume Comellas, Davide Careglio (UPC), Sándor Laki, Gergő Gombos, Károly Kecskeméti, Dávid Kis (ELTE), Andrea Sgambelluri, Faris Alhamed, Emilio Paolini, Massimo Satler, Domenico Uomo (SSSA), Mark Angoustures, Vincent Lefebvre (TSS), Marta Blanco Caamaño, Miguel A. Carnero Fernández (TID), Sultan Ertaş, Zekvan Yilmaz (EBY), Simon Pryor (ACC).
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Abstract

Deliverable D5.3 presents the final evaluation results and comprehensive Proof-of-Concept (PoC) demonstrations within the DESIRE6G project.

This document reports on the finalized testbed deployments, the execution of the integrated demonstrators, and the collection and analysis of the final data sets. It provides a consolidated view of the DESIRE6G architecture as realized with the final release components and applications delivered by WP3 and WP4. In alignment with the official project description in the DoA, D5.3 reports:

1. The final integration and validation of the components and applications that will be demonstrated;
2. The performance results and the analysis of the experiments carried out in the integrated testbeds and in the two final demos, with detailed KPI assessment.

Building upon the initial evaluations presented in Deliverable 5.2, D5.3 highlights the fully integrated PoC solutions across both global and local testbeds. It provides a detailed account of the deployment, execution workflows, and experimental validation of use cases and applications, with a focus on KPIs such as latency, reliability, scalability, and service assurance. The document reports the following main contributions:

- Deployment and integration of DESIRE6G Final Release components across all designated global and local testbeds.
- Results from PoC demonstrations, evaluating the achieved KPIs and providing insights into system performance and reliability.
- Functional validation of integrated components and use cases, demonstrating the readiness of the DESIRE6G platform for advanced operational scenarios.
- Analysis of KPI conformance, informing lessons learned and recommendations for future project phases.

By presenting these results, D5.3 provides the foundation for future advanced demonstrations and sets the stage for project activities in Year 3, ensuring that the DESIRE6G platform achieves its envisioned performance and operational objectives.

Keywords

Use Case Analysis demonstrators, testing and validation, evaluation, integration, tests, PoCs demonstrations

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AAL	Acceleration Abstraction Layer
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
AlaaS	Artificial Intelligence as a Service
AP	Access Point
AR/ VR/ XR	Augmented Reality/ Virtual Reality/ Extended Reality
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
BWE	Bandwidth Enforcer
CFS	Control Flow Shadowing
CID	Connection ID
CODP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CU	Centralized Unit
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
DFP	Data Flow Programming
DLINT	Deterministic Lightweighted In-Band Network Telemetry
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FPS	Frames Per Second
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphic Users Interface
HAP	High-Altitude Platform
HD	High Definition
HH	Heavy hitter

HLIR	High-Level Intermediate Representation
HQoS	Hierarchical Quality of Service
HW	Hardware
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication standardization sector
K8S	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicators
L4S	Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
LEO	LEO
LO-DP	Load Optimizer data plane
MAS	Multi Agent System
MIMO	Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLFO	Machine Learning Function Orchestrator
MR	Mixed Reality
NF	Network Function control plane
NF-DP	Network Function data plane
NFR	Network Function Routing
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
NIC	Network Interface Card
NN	Neural Network
NS	Network Service
OAM	Operations, Administration and Maintenance
O-RAN	Open RAN
OVS	Open vSwitch
P4	Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors
PDP	Programmable Data Plane
PLINT	Probabilistic Lightweighted In-Band Network Telemetry
PM	Performance Monitoring
PoC	Proof of Concept

PPV	Per Packet Value
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	Real Time Intelligent Controller
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROS	Robot Operating System
RoT	Root of Trust
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic positioning
RTT	Round-Trip Time
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDN-CP	Software-Defined Networking Control Plane
SECaaS	Security as a Service
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SMO	Service and Management Orchestrator
SNS IA	Smart Networks and Services Infrastructure Association
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SO	Service Orchestrator
SRv6	Segment Routing IPv6
SW	Software
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
uCID	Micro Connection ID
UE	User Equipment
uFC	Micro Flow Cache
uRLLC	Ultra-High Reliability & Low Latency Communications
VES	VNF Event streaming
VNF	Virtual Network Function
WAN	Wide Area Network

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.3 – Final report on evaluation results and Proof-of-Concept (PoC) demonstrations presents the final outcome of the DESIRE6G project’s experimental activities, consolidating the evaluation results, testbed deployments, functional validations, and PoC demonstrations performed with the Final Release of the DESIRE6G architecture.

This document reports the final integration activities started with Deliverable D5.2, providing a comprehensive report of the completed integration, the execution of full demonstrators, and the final assessment of KPIs across global and local testbeds.

During Year 3, DESIRE6G partners have completed the deployment of the two global testbeds (5TONIC and ARNO) along with a set of local testbeds specifically designed for PoC, testing the use cases under realistic conditions. The final experimental results validate the feasibility, scalability, and performance of the DESIRE6G architectural components—ranging from service orchestration and federated control to pervasive telemetry, programmable data planes, and AI-driven service assurance. As presented in D5.2, two end-to-end demonstrators provide the backbone of the final evaluation:

- Augmented Reality with Perceived Zero Latency, executed in the ARNO testbed, demonstrating ultra-low-latency streaming, intelligent traffic steering, programmable data-plane control, and multi-agent-based service assurance.
- Real-Time Digital Twin for Robotics, executed in the 5TONIC testbed, showcasing deterministic networking, reliable wireless connectivity, multi-site orchestration, and GPU-accelerated simulation.

In addition, ten PoC evaluations explore technological enablers of the DESIRE6G architecture, including AI-driven optimization, programmable data-plane functionalities, SmartNIC offloading, secure multi-agent systems, workload migration, RAN/CU-UP acceleration, SMO scalability, and blockchain-enabled federated orchestration. Key contributions of this deliverable include:

- Final Testbed Deployment: Complete description of global and local testbeds, integrating DESIRE6G Final Release components and enabling multi-domain experimentation.
- Final PoC Demonstrations: Execution of ten PoCs validating specific innovations in programmable networking, AI, orchestration, security, and RAN/edge acceleration.

- End-to-End Demonstrators: Comprehensive documentation of the final demonstrators, including workflows, KPIs, and system behaviour under realistic conditions.
- Component Integration and Functional Validation: Full integration of architectural components across SMO, IML, programmable data plane, monitoring, and intelligent control layers.
- KPI Evaluation: Final assessment of latency, reliability, scalability, and service assurance across testbeds, revealing strong performance alignment with project targets.
- A synthesis of integration and deployment challenges encountered, along with solutions and recommendations for future 6G system design.

Overall, this deliverable provides the final validation of the DESIRE6G architecture, demonstrating its operational readiness, robustness, and suitability as a building block for next generation 6G network systems. The outcomes reported in D5.3 form the foundation for follow-up activities within the wider SNS ecosystem and pave the way for future innovations in distributed, intelligent, and resilient 6G infrastructures.

1 Introduction

In the DESIRE6G project, Work Package 5 (WP5) is responsible for the integration, functional validation, and experimental evaluation of key technological components developed across the project. Leveraging distributed global and local testbeds, WP5 evaluates the feasibility, performance, and scalability of the DESIRE6G architecture under realistic operational conditions.

Deliverable D5.3 – Final report on evaluation results and PoC demonstrations builds upon the initial evaluation results presented in Deliverable D5.2. While Deliverable D5.2 focused on assessing DESIRE6G Release 1 components and reporting initial PoC demonstrations, D5.3 provides a comprehensive account of the final testbed deployments, integrated PoC executions, and performance evaluation using the DESIRE6G final release. This deliverable consolidates experimental results, functional validation, and KPI assessments, offering a complete picture of the platform’s capabilities. Main objectives of this document are:

- **Document the final testbed setups**, including both global (5TONIC and ARNO) and local PoC environments, and describing the integration of DESIRE6G final release components.
- **Report the final main demonstrators**: this document will report final activities, workflows, hardware and software components related to the first two demonstrators.
 - AR with perceived zero latency demonstrator
 - Real-time digital twin demonstrator
- **Report the final PoC demonstrators**, detailing workflows, hardware/software components, and integration processes for each PoC. Specifically, this document will report activities related to the following PoC:
 - PoC 1 – Offloading of UPF function in BF-3 Smart NIC
 - PoC2 - Intelligent Image Monitoring
 - PoC3 - Software Performance Monitoring
 - PoC4 - SLA-to-Intent Translator
 - PoC5 – Offloading of CU-UP function in in BF-2 Smart NIC and Tofino Switch
 - PoC6 - Inter-slice Radio resource scheduling
 - PoC7 – 5/6G in a backpack – UPF scaling
 - PoC8 - AI inference workload edge offloading
 - PoC9 - Secure MAS deployment and attestation

- PoC10 - SMO scalability
- **Providing a thorough evaluation of KPIs**, including latency, reliability, scalability, and service assurance, based on experimental results from all demonstrators and PoCs.
- **Highlighting lessons learned and insights** for further optimization of the DESIRE6G architecture and its application.

The deliverable is structure to provide a clear, systematic presentation of results:

- **Section 2** presents the final global and local testbeds, their configuration, and deployment status.
- **Section 3** details the integration of use cases with DESIRE6G final release components and functional validation activities.
- **Sections 4 and 5** describe the main demonstrators, including the AR with perceived zero latency and real-time digital twin applications, covering testbed setup, components, KPIs, and execution workflows.
- **Section 6** covers the ten PoCs, describing their goals, implementation, and evaluation results.
- **Section 7** provides a conformance analysis of KPIs across demonstrators and PoCs, and outlines the lessons learnt for future 6G deployments.
- **Section 8** summarizes the final conclusions.

D5.3 represents the final stage of the DESIRE6G experimental and validation efforts, offering final insights into the performance, reliability, and scalability of the integrated platform, and establishing a strong foundation for the whole SNS ecosystem and subsequent project follow up activities.

2 Final Testbeds

This section reports the description of the testbeds utilized for the execution of DESIRE6G demonstrators and PoC evaluations. The final setup of each testbed is reported in order to describe in detail the actual experimental environment used for the DESIRE6G architecture evaluation.

2.1 Global testbeds

The two main global testbeds are 5TONIC and ARNO, both used for the integration of the DESIRE6G architecture. A comprehensive description of the testbed has been provided in D5.1 [1] and D5.2 [2]. However, this final description includes the details referred to the integrated demo environment including the final AR and DT applications.

2.1.1 5TONIC

The 5TONIC testbed¹ has been presented in D5.1 [1], with emphasis on its hardware and software infrastructure, and in D5.2, which detailed its use in the Y2 demonstration of a real-time Digital Twin (DT) system for a quadruped robot, including the integration of early releases of the SMO and IML modules. In this deliverable, we document the final configuration of the testbed and the complete set of hardware and software components employed for the execution of the final integrated demonstration.

The testbed is hosted in the 5TONIC laboratory at the IMDEA Networks Institute in Leganés, Madrid (Spain), and is distributed across two rooms: the Main Lab (X3 Indoor Experimentation Room) and the Edge Data Center.

2.1.1.1 Main Lab (X3 Indoor Experimentation Room)

The Main Lab (shown in Figure 1) is the physical space where the quadruped robot operates autonomously using the DT system developed for this demonstration. The room is equipped with a full commercial 5G Stand Alone (SA) network provided by Ericsson Spain, including the Radio Access

¹ The 5TONIC testbed was officially renamed to NEXTONIC following its 10th anniversary. For consistency with previous DESIRE6G deliverables, we continue to refer to it as 5TONIC throughout this document.

Network (RAN) and the 5G User Plan Function (UPF). This infrastructure provides ultra-low-latency wireless connectivity to the edge data center, which hosts the remaining 5G core functions, the DT application, the data-plane devices, and the DESIRE6G components.

The RAN uses an indoor small-cell Radio Unit (Ericsson Dot 4479) mounted on the upper wall of the lab, which provides radio coverage to the robot and connects to the 5G base station (gNB) and the UPF toward the data center, as illustrated in Figure 2.

FIGURE 1. 5STONIC MAIN LAB (X3 INDOOR EXPERIMENTATION ROOM)

The room hosts the quadruped robot prototype used for the DT demo (shown in Figure 3). The robot is the Unitree Go1 Edu platform equipped with a Leotec N100 Mini-PC, a Logitech C920e Full HD camera, a SLAMTEC RPLIDAR A3 laser scanner, and a commercial 5G User Equipment (UE).

The onboard Mini-PC extends the robot's local computing capabilities by running the camera and LiDAR drivers, together with an application wrapper that exposes robot control and state information (e.g., odometry, joint states, and IMU data) over the Robot Operating System (ROS). The full information regarding the robot platform configuration can be found in D5.2 [2].

FIGURE 2. 5TONIC MAIN LAB: 5G RAN AND CORE USER-PLANE CONNECTIVITY

FIGURE 3. UNITREE GO1 EDU QUADRUPED ROBOT USED IN THE DT DEMONSTRATION

The Mini-PC connects the camera and LiDAR through USB 3.0 and includes two Gigabit Ethernet interfaces: one dedicated to internal communication with the robot using the proprietary Unitree Go1 SDK, and the other connected to the 5G UE to establish wireless access to the RAN. The UE employed

is a commercial NETGEAR Nighthawk M6 Pro, powered by the Qualcomm Snapdragon X65 5G Modem-RF System, supporting high-performance 5G connectivity in the n78 band (3300–3800 MHz).

2.1.1.2 Edge Data Center

The Edge Data Center (shown in Figure 4) includes multiple programmable and deterministic data-plane devices, as well as several server racks providing significant computing capacity and direct connectivity to the 5G network, enabling high-speed data transfer and real-time processing.

FIGURE 4. 5TONIC EDGE DATA CENTER

A Tofino switch, which hosts the Per-Packet-Value Traffic Manager (PPV-TM), provides 10/40 GbE connectivity between the 5G infrastructure and Edge Node 1, a high-performance PC equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU and an Intel X710-DA2 dual-port 10 GbE NIC. Edge Node 1 hosts the DT application, together with the IML and MAS instances. Additional 40/100 GbE interfaces connect the Tofino switch to a Dell PowerEdge R630 server used as a traffic generator for congestion emulation, and to a Ciena 5168 router that provides access to a programmable transport network implementing DetNet Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions (PREOF) for enhanced reliability. This

transport network consists of three Tofino switches implementing the PREOF DetNet components, along with two DPDK-enabled servers where the Ordering function is executed.

The programmable transport network feeds into a Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) Gigabit Ethernet segment built with four RELYUM TSN switches supporting IEEE 802.1AS, 802.1Qbv and 802.1CB DetNet mechanisms. This segment connects to Edge Node 2, a laptop that enables offloading of robot applications from Edge Node 1 during resource-constrained situations.

Pure control-plane components are deployed on three Dell PowerEdge R630 servers forming an OpenNebula cluster with virtual computing infrastructure. This cluster hosts the SMO modules, the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller for the transport network, and the PREDICT-6G orchestrator, all running as Virtual Machines (VMs).

2.1.1.3 Equipment mapping and list

The mapping between the equipment and the main DESIRE6G components integrated into the testbed is shown in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5. 5TONIC: MAPPING BETWEEN EQUIPMENT AND MAIN DESIRE6G COMPONENTS

As described above, the demonstrator is distributed across two co-located facilities on the same floor: the Main Lab and the Edge Data Center. The left side of Figure 5 corresponds to the Main Lab, where the quadruped robot and the 5G radio access network are deployed. The right side represents the Edge Data Center, hosting the data-plane infrastructure and the edge computing resources required to support real-time robot operation.

The programmable data plane is managed by a Tofino switch, which ensures mission-critical robot traffic through the Data PPV-TM module and interfaces with Edge Node 1. Edge Node 1 runs a MAS agent that monitors application resource usage and notifies the SMO in case of congestion; and IML to control the

Tofino switch and to deploy the DT system applications on the Kubernetes cluster spanning Edge Node 1 and the robot. The Tofino switch also connects to the deterministic data plane, composed of a transport network of three Tofino switches implementing PREOF, and a TSN Ethernet network with four switches supporting IEEE 802.1AS, 802.1Qbv, and 802.1CB. This latter network links to Edge Node 2, which runs a single-node Kubernetes cluster used to migrate DT applications from Edge Node 1 through the federation mechanism in response to resource-constrained conditions.

Finally, three control servers host separate VMs running the SMO and PREDICT-6G modules for orchestration and lifecycle management of applications and network functions, and the SDN controller, responsible for configuring the Tofino switches with PREOF to provide a zero-packet-loss transport network between the robot, Edge Node 1, and Edge Node 2.

The full list of 5TONIC equipment used in the demonstrator, together with the corresponding hardware and software specifications, is provided in Table 1.

TABLE 1. 5TONIC TESTBED EQUIPMENT WITH HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SPECIFICATIONS

Equipment	Hardware	Software
Unitree Go1 Edu quadruped robot	12 kg quadruped robot, 4.7 m/s top speed, 588 × 220 × 290 mm, 3-5 kg payload, 6000 mAh battery, 1 GbE port, IMU with joint encoders and contact sensors, onboard computing (Raspberry Pi 4B and 3× Jetson Nano)	Linux (Ubuntu-based) with Unitree Go1 SDK for programming and control
Robot Mini-PC	Leotec N100 Mini-PC, Intel N100 CPU (4 cores @ 3.4 GHz), 8GB RAM	Linux Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-139-generic
Robot Lidar	SLAMTEC RPLIDAR A3, 360-degree omnidirectional laser range scanning, 25-meter range radius, 16 000 samples/s	Slamtec RPLIDAR ROS 1 Noetic package, 2D LiDAR scan acquisition
Robot Camera	Logitech C920e, Full HD 1080p/30fps	GStreamer 1.0 multimedia framework for webcam capture and streaming
Robot UE	NETGEAR Nighthawk M6 Pro, Qualcomm Snapdragon X65 5G Modem-RF System	NTGX65_12.01.54.00 firmware
5TONIC 5G solution	Ericsson Radio Dot 4479 – n78 (3.5 GHz) indoor 5G NR Dot with 4× Tx/Rx branches (4T4R) delivering up to ~2 Gbps user speeds for mid-band indoor coverage. Ericsson IRU 8846 – Indoor Radio Unit that aggregates and powers up to 16 Radio Dots,	Ericsson cloud-native 5G SA RAN and 5G Core Network software, deployed as containerized network functions on Kubernetes.

	<p>uplinks via CPRI/eCPRI to the baseband and provides full macro-feature parity indoors.</p> <p>Ericsson Baseband 6648 – 1U RAN compute/baseband with 12 CPRI/eCPRI ports</p> <p>Ericsson Router 6675 – 1RU cell-site/pre-aggregation router with 320 Gbps switching for 4G/5G access/backhaul, providing 24x 10 GbE (SFP+) and 4x QSFP28 uplinks into the 5TONIC common edge data center.</p>	
Tofino switch (PPV-TM instance)	Edgecore DCS801 switch, Intel Xeon D-1517 CPU (8 cores @ 1.6 GHz), 256GB (32GB x 8), Tofino BFN-T10-032D, 32x 100G QSFP28 ports	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.141-generic x86_64 Barefoot SDE
Edge Node 1 (DT app, IML, and MAS instances)	Gaming PC, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU, AMD Ryzen Threadripper 1950X CPU (16 cores @ 3.4 GHz), 128GB RAM, Intel X710-DA2 dual-port 10 GbE NIC	Linux Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS, kernel Linux 5.4.0-150-generic
Traffic Generator server	Dell PowerEdge R630, 2x Intel Xeon E5-2600 v4 CPUs (16 cores @ 2.1 GHz), 128 GB RAM, Intel X520-DA2 dual-port 10 GbE NIC	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-160-generic
Ciena router	Ciena 5168, 14x 1/10/25GbE SFP28 ports, 18x CPRI ports (modes 3/5/7/8 with L1 offload), 4x 100/200GbE QSFP56/QSFP28 ports	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-160-generic
3x Tofino switches (PREOF instance)	Edgecore CSP-7550 switches, 2x Intel Xeon Gold 5218 (16 cores @ 2.3 GHz), 256GB (32GB x 8), 240GB M.2 SSD, Tofino BFN-T10-064Q-BO, 32x 100G QSFP28 ports	SONiC Enterprise
DPDK servers	Dell PowerEdge R510, Intel Xeon series 5500 CPU, 128 GB RAM	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-160-generic
4x RELYUM TSN switches	RELY-TSN-BRIDGE, IEEE 802.1AS/802.1Qbv/802.1CB, Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC, 1GB DDR3 RAM memory, 4x 10G SFP+ ports	RELY-TSN4 23.1.1C2 firmware
Edge Node 2	Laptop, Intel Core i7-1250U CPU (10 cores @ 4.7 GHz), 16 GB RAM	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 6.8.0-87-generic
3x Control servers (SMO, SDNc, and PREDICT-6G orchestrator instances)	Dell PowerEdge R630, 2x Intel Xeon E5-2600 v4 CPUs (16 cores @ 2.1 GHz), 128 GB RAM	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-160-generic

2.1.2 ARNO

The ARNO testbed has been described in D5.1 [1] with relation to the availability of hardware and software resources, and in D5.2 [2] with relation to the setup and execution of the Y2 demo employing Augmented Reality with pervasive monitoring and the MAS integration. In this deliverable we describe the final setup of the testbed and the hardware and software facilities utilized for the execution of the final Augmented Reality with Perceived Zero Latency integrated demo.

The testbed is located in the CNIT and SSSA laboratories and is distributed within three different rooms: the Main Lab room (floor 1), the Control room and the Drone Facility Room (floor 2).

For logistics reason, all the data plane components and equipment of the demo have been moved to the drone room.

2.1.2.1 Drone Facility Room

This room (shown in Figure 6) enables the drone flying missions. It is equipped with two indoor Benetel Radio Units (RU) (BNTL-RAN550) provided by Accelleran, mounted at the wall top at the two edges of the room (see Figure 7). All the data plane equipment is mounted in this room to facilitate the setup. The server and switches equipment set is shown in Figure 8. Each RU is locally powered and connected to the RAN server provided by Accelleran by means of two 10GbE interfaces through military-grade optical fiber pairs. This server (named Accelleran), hosting the Accelleran virtual DUs (vDU), is equipped with an Intel 10GbE 4-ports NIC interface with time synchronization features (see Figure 8, "RAN vDUs"). The server is connected to a second server (named Desire2) hosting two VMs: one for the RAN RIC and the Centralized Unit (CU), the other running the RAN Core Network (see Figure 8, "RAN RIC, CU, CN"). The data plane connectivity between the two servers is guaranteed by two different 10GbE interfaces, allowing the routing decoupling between different vDU and the CU/CN segment.

The Desire2 server hosting the RAN RIC, CU and CN, is connected to an APS Tofino 1 switch by means of 40/100 GbE interfaces. Additional interfaces are used to connect the Tofino to two additional Dell servers (P4_1 and P4_2, see Figure 8, "SDN network +cluster node"), used to deploy the SDN network and part of the edge cluster. All the servers are equipped with 10, 40 and 100 Gigabit Ethernet interfaces (NVIDIA ConnectX5 NICs). Finally, 4 NVIDIA Jetson ORIN 64 are connected to the servers by means of one GbE interface (see Figure 8, "ORIN cluster nodes"). All these devices have an additional control plane

interface used to interconnect the devices. The Meta Quest 3 is used as final headset, attested to the switch that connects the edge cluster.

FIGURE 6 ARNO: DRONE FACILITY ROOM

FIGURE 7 ARNO: POSITIONING SYSTEM, 5G RADIO UNITS AND DATA PLANE DEVICES

The room hosts the drone prototype used for the AR demo, assembled at the SSSA lab premises, shown in Figure 9. The drone is a quadcopter with dual on-board companion computer and a flight control. The flight control unit (FCU) is hosted within a Pixhawk 6X board. Two companion boards are interconnected by means of a Gigabit Ethernet interface: 1) an ARM-based Jetson ORIN NX with two micro cameras and 2) a x86 Intel NUC Core i7-1185G7. The Jetson board hosts the AR source app, including object detection capabilities, while the NUC is responsible for the DESIRE6G networking configuration (e.g., embedded P4 switch), including the Quectel User Equipment, attached to the NUC via USB-3 interface and equipped with four antennas suitable for the n78 frequency slot (3300-3800 MHz, TDD).

FIGURE 8 ARNO: DATA PLANE DEVICES

FIGURE 9 DRONE QUADCOPTER

2.1.2.2 Control Room and Main Lab Room

The control room is adjacent to the Drone facility room. Through a glass wall, it is possible to view and check all the demo operations taking place in the drone room. PCs and monitors are available for launching the demo tests and workflows with full security.

The main lab room is placed on the first floor of the CNIT/SSSA premises and includes all the lab facilities, including optical devices, packet-optical programmable devices, routers, server racks, etc. The room is connected to the drone and control rooms via internal cabling using a dedicated Gigabit

Ethernet connectivity. In the lab room, pure control plane devices are deployed within dedicated servers. In particular, one R760 Dell server equipped with NVIDIA A16 GPU is used to host the SMO components and the IML instances and components. Additional servers are utilized to instantiate the secure MAS instances along with software attestation capabilities. The two rooms are shown in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10 ARNO CONTROL AND MAIN LAB ROOMS

2.1.2.3 Equipment mapping and list

The mapping between the equipment and the main DESIRE6G components integrated in the testbed is shown in Figure 11. Further explanation about the full demo setup is provided in Section 4.1.1.

FIGURE 11 ARNO: EQUIPMENT-COMPONENTS MAPPING

As shown before, the setup is distributed across two physical locations: the Drone Facility on the second floor and the Main Lab on the first floor. The upper section represents the Drone Facility, where the radio access, data plane, and edge computing infrastructure are co-located to support real-time drone

operations. The programmable data plane is handled by the Tofino switch, the SDN servers and the Drone x86 board, enabling in-network telemetry, traffic steering, and packet manipulation in the whole segments (drone-RAN-SDN-edge). These programmable switch instances interface with the IML and SDN controller, running P4-enabled components and Kubernetes-based orchestration for service deployment. The edge cluster composed of several servers provides computational resources for AI-based analytics, data processing, and AR application hosting. These nodes run Kubernetes workloads and host AR services as well as the Quest 3 headset used for immersive visualization and remote control of drone operations.

The servers of the Main Lab host the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework and the Intelligent Management Layers (IML1 and IML2), responsible for data plane deployment and configuration. Nearby, two servers (MAS1 and MAS2) execute distributed AI multi-agents that perform predictive analytics and multi-agent coordination tasks. All these systems are integrated under a control plane that spans both the edge and core domains.

The full list of the ARNO equipment used in the demonstrator, along with hardware and software specifications, is detailed in Table 2.

TABLE 2 ARNO EQUIPMENT: HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SPECIFICATIONS

Equipment	Hardware	Software
2x Benetel RUs	Benetel SC-705e, 5G Open RAN Remote Radio Unit, eCPRI and Ethernet interfaces	API 6.4.0.14
RAN vDU server	AS -1015A-MT, CPU AMD Ryzen9 7950X 16-cores @3000MHz, RAM 128GB,	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.05 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-1032-realtime
RAN RIC-CU-CN server	Dell PowerEdge R760, CPU Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6438Y+ 128 cores @2000MHz, RAM 251G, GPU NVIDIA A16	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, kernel Linux 6.5.0-41-generic
2x SDN network servers	Dell PowerEdge R7515, CPU AMD EPYC 7262 8-Core Processor 16 cores @3194MHz, RAM 16GB	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, kernel 6.8.0-60-generic
4x ORIN boards	NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin 64GB, edge AI computing module con CPU Arm Cortex-A78AE 12-core, GPU Ampere 2048 CUDA + 64 Tensor Cores, 64 GB LPDDR5, interfaces Ethernet 10 GbE, PCIe Gen4, USB 3.2, e GPIO.	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS
Tofino switch	Hardware: APS Tofino BF2556X, Intel Tofino ASIC (6.5 Tb/s throughput, <400 ns latency), 56 x 10/25 GbE and 6 x 100 GbE ports, programmable packet parser/deparsed, match-	Linux Ubuntu 18.08.5 LTS, kernel Linux 4.15.0-197-generic x86_64 Barefoot SDE

	action pipeline with stateful ALUs, in-band telemetry and traffic metering support, managed via P4Runtime and Barefoot SDE. Control: Intel Xeon CPU D-1548, 2GHz	
Control server	Dell PowerEdge R760, CPU Intel Xeon Gold 6438Y+ 64 core @2000MHz, RAM 256GB, GPU NVIDIA A16	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, kernel Linux 5.15.0-144-low latency
MAS server	Dell PowerEdge R760, CPU Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6238R CPU @2.20GHz, RAM 256GB	Linux Ubuntu 24.04.2 LTS, kernel Linux 6.8.0-87-generic
Drone Jetson NX	Arm® Cortex®-A78E v8.2 64-bit CPU; GPU Nvidia Amps 1024 core; NVDLA v2.0 and PVA 2.0; 8 GB LPDDR5 1289 bit; RAM 8GB, 102.4 GB/s, Power 10-20 W	Linux Ubuntu 24.04.2 LTS; Nvidia JetPack 6.1
Drone x86 board	Intel® companion x86, quad-core NUC Intel® Core i7-1185G7; Intel® Iris® Xe Graphics; Power 28 W;	MAVSDK for Linux
Drone Flight Control Unit	Pixhawk X6 Autopilot Flight Control System. 32 bit Arm® Cortex®-M7 480 MHz, 2MB flash memory, 1MB RAM; ST32F103 IO Processor; 3x accel/gyro on-board sensors ICM-45686 (with BalancedGyro™), ICP20100 & BMP388 barometer, BMM150 magnetometer.	PX4 Flight controller firmware, v1.15.4
Drone external on-board elements	Single point LiDAR range finder, 4S LiPo 6300mAh battery.	Vicon Tracker 4, dedicated to track rigid bodies and provide highly accurate 6-DoF data with low latency.
Meta Quest 3 Headset	Meta Quest 3 Headset, XR standalone headset, SoC Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 Gen 2, CPU Kryo Octa-core, GPU Adreno 740, 8 GB RAM, display dual LCD 2064x2208 px per-eye; interfaces Wi-Fi 6E, Bluetooth 5.3 and USB-C.	Android-base OS; Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 Gen 2; Refresh rate up to 120Hz

2.2 Local Testbeds

Local testbeds are designed to execute, test and collect results of the DESIRE6G PoCs, extensively described in Section 6. Namely, the following PoCs have been evaluated and for each of them a local testbed is reported (see Table 3):

TABLE 3 POC LIST AND LOCAL TESTBEDS

PoC	Title	Host	Description
PoC#1	Offloading of UPF Functions in BF-3 Smart NIC	CNIT, NV	Evaluate UPF offloading using BF-3 SmartNICs; high-performance, low-latency packet processing.
PoC#2	Intelligent Image Monitoring	ELTE	Test intelligent image monitoring and dynamic data plane reconfiguration in industrial scenarios.
PoC#3	Software Performance Monitoring	TSS, ERI-HU	Assess software performance monitoring through timestamp-based metrics for workload execution.
PoC#4	SLA-to-Intent Translator	EBY	Validate SLA-to-Intent translation using LLM-based chatbot and vector database for service identification.
PoC#5	CU-UP Offloading	UVA, ERI-HU	Evaluate CU-UP offloading with SmartNICs and programmable switches in a 5G network environment.
PoC#6	Inter-slice Radio Resource Scheduling	UVA	Test inter-slice radio resource scheduling on a realistic multi-UE, multi-slice 6G RAN/core platform.
PoC#7	5/6G in a backpack - UPF scaling	ERI-HU	Evaluate ERI-HU 6G UPF functionalities (details in section 2.2.7).
PoC#8	AI inference workload edge offloading	UC3M, NEC, NUBIS	Assess AI inference workload offloading at the edge with heterogeneous hardware resources.
PoC#9	Secure MAS Deployment and Attestation	UPC, TSS	Deploy and validate secure MAS agents, attestation, and DLT-based orchestration in a virtualized environment.
PoC#10	SMO scalability	NUBIS	Evaluate SMO microservice scalability and orchestration pipeline performance for large-scale service requests.

2.2.1 PoC#1 Testbed

The ARNO testbed, hosted across the CNIT and SSSA laboratories, provides a high-performance, distributed infrastructure for evaluating User Plane Functions (UPFs) accelerated with NVIDIA BlueField-3 (BF-3) DPUs.

For what concerns PoC#1, the testbed is shown in Figure 12 and integrates programmable networking, edge computing, and RAN/CN elements to address 6G requirements for high throughput, low latency, and large-scale connectivity. Key components employed in PoC#1 include:

- **Edge and UPF Servers:** The Dell PowerEdge servers are equipped with BF-3 DPUs host the UPF functions and offload tasks such as GTP encapsulation and QoS enforcement, leveraging DOCA Flow APIs for hardware acceleration.

- **Edge AI Cluster:** NVIDIA Jetson Orin modules provide computational resources for AI-based analytics, assisting in network monitoring and service management.
- **Traffic Generators:** the commercial VIAVI Traffic Generator is capable to send and receive L2 and L3 traffic up to 400Gbps; the software-based Cisco Trex traffic generator is able to send up to 100Gbps traffic with custom packet protocol stacking.

FIGURE 12 POC 1 TESTBED

This configuration enables PoC#1 to demonstrate a scalable and high-performance UPF architecture. By offloading critical UPF functions to hardware while maintaining full orchestration and monitoring, the ARNO testbed validates DESIRE6G's capability to meet next-generation mobile network performance and reliability requirements.

2.2.2 PoC#2 Testbed

In PoC#2, we use the ELTE site of the NPT-Budapest: Network Programmability Testbed. The testbed was built to support the evaluation and validation of data plane algorithms and methods. The testbed relies on servers, high-speed NICs, programmable NICs and programmable switches (Intel Tofino, and PcEngines APU boxes).

Key components and their deployment in PoC#2:

- **Emulated video sources and robot status traffic:** These traffic emulators run on an x86 server (AMD Ryzen Threadripper 1900X 8-Core, 128GB RAM)
- **Infrastructure and custom data plane NFs at the emulated industrial site:** A PcEngines APU x86-based switch represents the gateway node of the industrial site. This is the only node belonging to the Desire6G domain. The node runs the pre-deployed infrastructure NFs (UE2SM, NFR) and any custom P4- or eBPF/XDP-based NFs to be deployed. In the PoC, it runs the QoSControl NF.
- **Infrastructure data planes at the remote site:** The gateway at the remote site is a Tofino ASIC-based switch (UfiSpace S9180-32X), it only runs the infrastructure NFs at this site.
- **Industrial controller application:** This application is the receiver of the video streams and the robot states. Based on video streams it determines the commands to be sent to the robot. This component runs on another x86 server (AMD Ryzen Threadripper 1900X 8-Core, 128GB RAM) in a container.
- **Local orchestration:** Each site is controlled by a local IML LNFVO instance. At the industrial site, IML runs on the PcEngines APU switch, while at the remote site it is located on the remote server.

This setup enables us to show the on-the-fly data plane reconfiguration capabilities of Desire6G's unified data plane layer and allows us to measure its effect on the traffic flows (loss, outage, throughput) and the application-level requirements.

2.2.3 PoC#3 Testbed

The testbed is set up in TSS's infrastructure. Two workbenches were implemented within TSS's infrastructure to cover both fixed-lifetime and persistent software. Because it is more specific, we designed a dedicated workbench for the L2Fwd network function, driven by the TRex traffic generator, monitored with DPDK, and stressed using worker processes from stress-ng. The testbed is shown in Figure 13. Tests were conducted on the following host machine:

- OS Version: Ubuntu 24.04.3 LTS
- Architecture: x86_64 GNU/Linux
- CPU: Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-1650 v2 @ 3.50 GHz
- CPU min/max MHz: 1200 / 3900
- Important CPU Flags: constant_tsc

- RAM: 32 GB DDR3 1600 MHz
- VirtualBox Version: 7.0.26r168464
- stress-ng Version: 0.17.06

Virtual machines:

- VM 1 (trex): Ubuntu_64, kernel 6.5.0-26-generic, 2 CPUs, 2048 MB RAM
- VM 2 (l2fwd): Ubuntu_64, kernel 6.5.0-44-generic, 3 CPUs, 2048 MB RAM

FIGURE 13 POC 3 TESTBED

2.2.4 PoC#4 Testbed

The PoC was implemented on a VM-based single-node testbed to validate the proposed architecture and workflows as shown in the Figure 14.

FIGURE 14 POC 4 TESTBED

The testbed consists of the following services and functions:

- UI Frontend: Provide frontend components for user input and interaction.
- The UI Backend: Acts as an intermediary layer between the UI frontend components and the core backend services within the VM-based PoC testbed
- Vector Database: Generates embeddings and performs similarity-based retrieval using a similarity index.
- Similarity Check: Evaluates semantic similarity between user inputs and existing services or intents to identify the most relevant matches.
- SLA/SLO Creator: Generates SLA and SLO context based on predefined structures and templates.
- Intent Creator: Constructs intent context in alignment with the defined intent models and templates.
- Agent: Operates as an interaction and reasoning layer between the UI Backend Service and the GPT-mini LLM.

Testing was carried out on the following host system:

- vCPU: 8 vCPU – Supports concurrent UI requests, embedding generation, and LLM inference calls, similarity check
- RAM: 32 GB – Required for in-memory vector database, embeddings, and LLM context handling
- Storage: 200 GB SSD – Model cache, embeddings, vectordb, and service/intent repository
- Network: 1 Gbps (virtual) – Ensures low-latency calls to external models

All components except the external LLM are hosted inside the VM. The vector database runs in-memory with periodic persistence to disk. UI-related components were implemented in Java, while others were developed in Python.

2.2.5 PoC#5 Testbed

The complete PoC#5 is deployed and evaluated at the University of Pampa (UNIPAMPA) testbed in Brazil, in collaboration with the SMART NETworks and ServiceS for 2030 (SMARTNESS) FAPESP Engineering Research Center [3]. The testbed was built to evaluate the potential benefits of offloading tasks from traditional servers to hardware accelerators such as SmartNICs and programmable switches. Figure 15 presents how the testbed is organized and below we detail the components characteristics.

FIGURE 15: SMARTNESS TESTBED AT ALEGRETE

- **Main server** (equipped with BlueField): runs Ubuntu 22.04 on an Intel® Xeon® Silver 4216 CPU and hosts a simplified srsRAN CU implementation for baseline processing.
- **NVIDIA BlueField-2 DPU**: offloads the CU-UP functionality from the main server, using its dual ConnectX-6 Dx SmartNIC capabilities to accelerate packet handling.
- **Programmable switch (Tofino)**: an EdgeCore Wedge 100-32X switch executing a minimal CU-UP pipeline written in P4, enabling in-network processing of selected CU-UP operations.
- **Secondary server**: runs CentOS 7.9 and hosts TRex to generate synthetic DU-like traffic and also the 5G core, powered by an AMD Ryzen™ 7 2700 CPU.

2.2.6 PoC#6 Testbed

The complete PoC#6 is deployed and evaluated within the Keysight O-RAN Architect (KORA) platform [4], as part of KEYSIGHTS's Test and Monitoring portfolio embedded in JUSNS 6G-Sandbox project [5]. KORA provides a controlled environment for multi-UE, multi-slice testing with realistic radio and core-network behavior (see Figure 16), including:

- (i) Keysight RuSIM that emulates the RU and UE PHY/MAC, enabling realistic channel behavior, fading, and time-varying CQI.
- (ii) Keysight AirMosaic software that controls RuSIM, enabling the creation of multiple UEs with customized configurations.
- (iii) Keysight CuSIM that emulates the gNB Central Unit (CU).
- (iv) Keysight CoreSIM that emulates the 5G Core, supporting NAS signaling, registration, PDU-session establishment, and slice selection based on S-NSSAI.

FIGURE 16: 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORM MALAGA²

2.2.7 PoC#7 Testbed

The testbed used for the 5/6G-in-a-backpack scenario is illustrated in Figure 17. It consists of two low-performance laptop devices interconnected through a pair of USRP B210 software-defined radio boards, linked via RF cables to provide a controlled radio environment. The RAN and 5G Core control-plane components were provided by the OpenAirInterface (OAI) open-source community.

The User Plane Function (UPF) was developed by ERI-HU, with all dataplane modules (NF-DP) implemented in P4 targeting both v1model (BMv2) and Tofino TNA architectures. The control-plane modules (NF-CP) were implemented in C++, using P4Runtime for the BMv2 software switch and the BFRT library for the Tofino hardware target.

² <https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/malaga/>

FIGURE 17 POC 7 TESTBED

Infrastructure components were jointly contributed by ELTE and ERI-HU. For scalability testing, ERI-HU deployed a simplified runtime environment based on Docker Compose instead of Kubernetes.

For the scale-up evaluation, the testbed was extended with an AMD EPYC server featuring 24 physical cores / 48 threads. In this configuration, the RAN was fully emulated, and the user equipment (UE) traffic was generated as pcap replay streams on an identical AMD server. This traffic source connected to the system under test through 2x100 GbE interfaces, enabling high-throughput and stress-testing experiments.

2.2.8 PoC#8 Testbed

The 5TONIC testbed provides a high-performance edge-computing environment for evaluating the efficient and transparent execution of AI inference workloads across heterogeneous hardware resources.

In the context of PoC#8, the testbed components involved (highlighted in red in Figure 18) include the robot platform used in the DT demonstration with the commercial 5G SA network deployed at 5TONIC and an edge-computing node in the data center equipped with high-performance processing capabilities (e.g., GPU). This setup enables the optimized execution and offloading of AI-based robotic tasks to the edge to meet the required application-level performance targets.

FIGURE 18: OVERVIEW OF THE 5TONIC TESTBED HIGHLIGHTING THE COMPONENTS USED IN POC#8

Key components employed in PoC#8 include:

- **Robot:** Unitree Go1 Edu platform equipped with a Mini-PC with Intel N100 CPU running an AI computer-vision application (e.g., monocular depth-estimation), a Logitech C920e Full HD camera, and a commercial 5G UE for wireless connectivity.
- **5TONIC 5G solution:** Indoor Radio Unit (Ericsson Dot 4479) operating in band n78, providing high-throughput, low-latency radio access between the robot and the edge data center hosting the 5G UPF and edge compute node.
- **Edge node:** A gaming-class PC equipped with an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 1950X CPU and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU running the DESIRE6G vAccel and SOL components. The baseline depth-estimation model is optimized offline using the SOL compiler, and the resulting accelerated model is exposed through vAccel to enable remote inference execution on the edge node's CPU or GPU.

This configuration allows PoC#8 to demonstrate DESIRE6G's capability for hardware-agnostic AI acceleration and continuum-aware execution using open and cloud-native frameworks.

2.2.9 PoC#9 Testbed

This PoC testbed is located the UPC Campus Nord in Barcelona, Spain and it consists of a collection of compute, storage and network resources used by the UPC research group.

Six Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-13900K CPU @2.20GHz servers with 256GB RAM are available for testing and OpenStack is used as cloud resource manager providing a shared virtualized environment where workloads can be deployed on-demand. Additionally, a number of bare-metal machines are available for

specific cases where virtualization cannot be used. Researchers can deploy and run their experiments inside VMs deployed in the OpenStack cluster.

The setup considers three different locations, where each location includes computing resources, so the local OpenStack virtualized infrastructure manager is in charge of automating the deployment of VNFs. A MLFO decides the locations where agents need to be deployed, how they need to be connected and coordinates their activity. Finally, a DLT infrastructure is also setup using the Geth implementation of Ethereum. The MLFO, the MAS agents and their components, along with their interfaces, are implemented in Python 3.10.4. The MAS agents and their sidecars run inside Docker containers on separate VMs using Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS. The MLFO, the SECaaS and the DLT run on independent VMs using Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS as well. All VMs are running on the OpenStack cluster. MAS Agents VMs have been assigned 4 vCPUs and 8 GB of RAM, while the MLFO, the SECaaS, and the DLT VMs have been assigned 8 vCPUs and 16 GB of RAM each. Figure 19 presents the deployment:

FIGURE 19 UPC POC TESTBED

2.2.10 PoC#10 Testbed

The SMO Scalability Testbed is designed to validate the performance and scalability of DESIRE6G microservice-based SMO architecture, focusing on the end-to-end processing pipeline from service request ingestion to the generation of optimized Service Graphs. The testbed emulates the operational conditions of large-scale 6G deployments, where the SMO must process frequent, heterogeneous service requests with deterministic response times, modular extensibility, and orchestration correctness.

FIGURE 20: NUBIS TESTBED FOR SMO SCALABILITY

For PoC#10, the testbed instantiates the full SMO control loop using containerized microservices that represent key architectural components: the Service Orchestrator (SO), the Optimization Engine (OE), the Topology Module and the Service Catalog. The testbed (Figure 20) is comprised of an 8-core VM, with 16GB of RAM. The vCPUs are statically pinned to the physical cores, so no overcommitment takes place. The VM is QEMU/KVM, adding minimal overhead to user-space tasks such as the service deployment operations of the SMO. The VM features a UBUNTU 24.04 OS, with docker engine and docker compose, able to scale the needed components of the SMO efficiently. Additional software used is essentially the SMO implementation (python microservices using FAST API for REST endpoints, RabbitMQ client code for interaction with the Message Queue as well as requests for interacting with REST endpoints).

Time was measured using the time package of python, with microsecond granularity.

This configuration enables PoC#10 to demonstrate the scalability, modularity, and robustness of the SMO architecture. By isolating each processing stage and quantifying its contribution to the overall response time, up to the point of issuing the request to IML, the testbed validates DESIRE6G's ability to support large numbers of concurrent service requests while preserving orchestrator responsiveness. The results highlight how scaling the Optimization Engine improves throughput and reduces processing latency, confirming the suitability of the proposed microservice-based design for next-generation network automation frameworks.

3 Use Cases Integration and Functional Validation

The integration work presented in this section represents a natural progression from the foundational efforts we documented in Deliverable D5.2. [2] That earlier deliverable captured our initial experiences deploying and validating the DESIRE6G Release 1 components – essentially our first working prototype. Looking back at where we started and comparing it to where we are now with the Final Release, the difference is quite substantial. What began as a collection of promising but incomplete modules has evolved into a cohesive, production-ready platform.

3.1 Use Cases Integration with DESIRE6G Final Release

Throughout the development cycle, there have been several key areas of improvement that collectively define the maturation journey of the DESIRE6G solution:

- **Component maturity:** In Release 1, many components were still in their early stages – functional enough to demonstrate core concepts but lacking the robustness needed for real-world deployment. Over the past year, each module has undergone significant refinement. What were once preliminary implementations have transformed into deployable components supporting final demos and PoCs.
- **Connections between components:** One of the more challenging aspects of building a distributed system like DESIRE6G is ensuring that all the pieces talk to each other effectively. In Release 1, we encountered numerous integration headaches – mismatched data formats, timing issues, and communication bottlenecks between WP3 (control and orchestration) and WP4 (infrastructure and monitoring) components. The Final Release reflects interface refinement, protocol harmonization, and architectural adjustments. Today, these components communicate more seamlessly, with cleaner APIs and more robust error handling than we had originally implemented.
- **Testing multi-site deployments:** Initially, the integration work focused on single-site deployments – getting everything working within one testbed environment was challenging enough. However, real 6G networks will need to operate across distributed, federated infrastructures. Recognizing this reality, we now showcase multi-site deployments for the two

main demos and selected POCs, reflecting the distributed nature of the future 6G network architectures.

- Iterations on system stability: One of the most tangible improvements between Release 1 and the Final Release is overall system stability. During early integration testing, issues—race conditions in control plane operations, memory leaks in monitoring agents, configuration conflicts in programmable switches, and synchronization problems in federated orchestration were identified. The Final Release represents the resolution of these challenges through systematic debugging, architectural refinements, and continuous testing cycles.

3.1.1 Final Release – Progress from Initial Release

The Final Release integration phase spanned roughly nine months, from late 2024 through mid-2025. During this period, the primary objective has been to achieve operational readiness for DESIRE6G’s demonstrators. The focus has been in integration efforts on two distinct use cases; each deployed in its own testbed environment:

- **Demo1** showcases Augmented Reality with Perceived Zero Latency, deployed at the ARNO testbed in Pisa. This demonstrator pushes the boundaries of ultra-low latency communication, combining edge computing, intelligent traffic steering, and in-band network telemetry. More details are provided in Section 4.
- **Demo2** demonstrates real-time Digital Twin capabilities for robotics, hosted at the 5TONIC testbed in Madrid. This use case explores cloud-native orchestration, programmable traffic management, and multi-domain domain federation in dynamic scenarios. More details are provided in Section 5.

As we documented in deliverable D5.2, Release 1 established the fundamental architectural framework for DESIRE6G. That initial integration validated our basic design assumptions—we proved that the Service Management and Orchestration layer could communicate with Infrastructure Management components, that programmable data planes could be controlled through standardized interfaces, and that pervasive monitoring could collect meaningful telemetry data. These foundational achievements, while modest, gave us confidence to proceed with more ambitious integration goals.

The Final Release takes these foundations and builds substantially upon them. Rather than simply validating that components can work together, we now demonstrate that they work together well –

handling complex workflows, recovering from failures, and delivering the performance needed for demanding 6G use cases.

3.1.2 Integration Methodology and Coordination

The integration methodology adopted for the **Final Release (June 2025)** follows the architectural guidelines established in D2.2 [6] and the integration framework defined in D5.1 [7].

FIGURE 21. DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE AND LAYERS - FINAL INTEGRATION STATUS

The Integration methodology involves the following steps.

Component-level integration

Each module developed in WP3 (Service Management and Orchestration) and WP4 (Infrastructure Management and Pervasive Monitoring) underwent standalone functional testing before testbed deployment. This ensured that individual components met their specified interfaces and functional requirements prior to integration activities.

Interface validation

Following component-level testing, interface validation verified communication protocols, data models, and message exchanges between interconnected modules. The integration effort relied on standardized interfaces including:

- REST APIs for control plane interactions (SMO ↔ IML, SO ↔ OE)
- P4Runtime for programmable data plane configuration (IML ↔ switches, NF-CPs ↔ NF-DPs)
- gRPC/Kafka for telemetry data collection (Telemetry Collectors ↔ Agents)
- DLT smart contracts for federated orchestration (SO ↔ remote sites)

Testbed Deployment and Configuration

Validated components were deployed to the ARNO and 5TONIC global testbeds following the infrastructure configurations described in Section 2. Deployment procedures ensured:

- Correct placement of control plane components (SMO, IML instances)
- Proper configuration of programmable data plane elements (Tofino switches, NIKSS nodes)
- Network connectivity verification between sites and across domains (RAN, SDN, edge)
- Resource allocation for containerized workloads (Kubernetes, Docker environments)

End-to-End Functional Validation

After deployment, end-to-end validation verified complete workflows execution from service request through deployment, monitoring, and service assurance. This validation, detailed in subsections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2, confirmed operational readiness for demonstration activities.

Coordination Across Partners

The integration effort involved close coordination among 12 partner organizations, with clearly defined responsibilities:

- NUBIS: SMO orchestration components (DL, SO, SC, Topology)
- UPC: Multi-Agent System and MLFO

- ELTE: IML components and infrastructure NFs (NFR, UE2SM, PPV-TM)
- CNIT/SSSA: Pervasive service and infrastructure monitoring, INT-based telemetry
- UC3M: DLT-based federation mechanisms
- TID: DetNet-PREOF transport network
- UVA: Optimization Engine
- ACC: RAN telemetry and CU-UP functions
- NEC: SOL server integration
- TSS: Security-as-a-Service (SECaaS)

Regular integration meetings, GitLab-based code repositories, and shared documentation ensured alignment across partners and facilitated issue resolution throughout the integration period.

3.1.3 Specific Achievements in the Final Release

Final Release integration accomplishes several critical objectives:

- Deployment of all planned modules from both WP3 and WP4 were completed. While Release 1 included only a subset of components at varying maturity levels, the Final Release brings together the complete architectural stack—from high-level service orchestration down to programmable data plane elements and pervasive monitoring infrastructure.
- End-to-end workflows have been validated, spanning multiple architectural layers, demonstrating complete service lifecycles from initial request through deployment, monitoring, optimization, and eventual teardown. The Final Release integration proves that these multi-layer workflows function correctly across our distributed testbed infrastructure.
- Cross-site federation using blockchain-based (DLT) mechanisms is in place (demo 2). This capability enables service orchestration across geographically separated testbeds, with autonomous sites coordinating deployment decisions through smart contracts rather than centralized control. This federated approach represents a significant architectural advancement over the single-site deployments of Release 1.

- Functional validation of closed-loop service assurance and orchestration was reached. The Final Release includes working implementations of intelligent agents that monitor service performance, detect violations of service-level agreements, and trigger corrective actions automatically. These closed-loop capabilities move us beyond static deployment toward truly adaptive network management.

3.1.4 Challenges Addressed in Final Release

The Final Release integration demonstrated:

1. **Multi-layer orchestration:** SMO-driven service deployment coordinating with IML for infrastructure provisioning and MAS for runtime optimization.
2. **Programmable data plane control:** P4-based switches (Tofino, BMv2, NIKSS) configured dynamically by IML to support NFR, UE2SM, and INT functions.
3. **Cross-domain telemetry:** End-to-end latency visibility from UE (drone/robot) through RAN and SDN domains to edge, enabling closed-loop service assurance.
4. **Federated orchestration:** DLT-based federation enabling service deployment across geographically distributed ARNO and 5TONIC sites.
5. **AI-driven optimization:** MAS agents performing real-time traffic steering decisions based on INT-collected telemetry data.

Integration Challenges Addressed

Several integration challenges were approached during the Final Release phase:

- **Interface Alignment:** Differences in data model representations between WP3 and WP4 components required harmonization efforts. For example, service descriptors from the SO needed transformation to match IML's internal service graph format. This was resolved through adapter logic in the LNFVO component.
- **Timing and Synchronization:** Coordination of control plane actions across multiple components (e.g., SDN controller programming Tofino switches while IML deploys K8s pods) required careful sequencing to avoid race conditions. Implementation of event-driven triggers and state management in the SO addressed this challenge.

- **Testbed Connectivity:** Establishing stable, low-latency connectivity between federated testbeds (ARNO in Pisa, 5TONIC in Madrid) required GRE tunneling and VXLAN overlay configuration. Network latency (~30ms RTT) based on preliminary measurement, impacted MAS reaction times in preliminary tests, addressed by co-locating MAS agents with their monitored domains in the Final Release.

Component Versioning: Managing dependencies between rapidly evolving components across partners necessitated strict version control and compatibility testing. GitLab-based CI/CD pipelines and containerization (Docker) facilitated versioning and deployment consistency.

3.1.5 Component Classification and Final Integration Status

The Final Release encompasses 32 distinct modules spanning four architectural layers, as defined in the DESIRE6G architecture (D2.2). Table 4 presents the classification of integrated components by architectural layer and their integration status **at the end of the project**.

TABLE 4. DESIRE6G FINAL INTEGRATION STATUS

Layer	Module	Responsible partner	Integration Status (%)	Involved Testbeds	Target Demo
SMO Layer	Data Lake (DL)	NUBIS	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	Service Orchestrator (SO)	NUBIS	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	Service Catalog (SC)	NUBIS	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	Topology	NUBIS	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	IBN (SLA-to-Intent)	EBY	50%	5TONIC	Demo2
	DLT-federation	UC3M	100%	5TONIC	Demo2
	Optimization Engine (OE)	UVA	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	SDN Controller	UPM	100%	5TONIC	Demo2
Intelligent Distributed Control	MLFO	UPC	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	MAS Agents	UPC	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	SECaaS	TSS	100%	ARNO	Demo1
IML Layer					

	LNFVO	ELTE	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	Enhanced VIM (EVIM)	NUBIS	100%	5TONIC	Demo2
Unified PDP					
	PPV-TM	ELTE	100%	5TONIC	Demo2
	NF Routing (NFR)	ELTE	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	UE2Service Mapper (UE2SM)	ELTE	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo1, Demo2
	P4 Data Plane Aggregator	ELTE, ERI-HU	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	P4Runtime Proxy	ELTE	100%	ARNO	Demo1
Pervasive Monitoring					
	Telemetry Agent	UPC	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	Telemetry Collector	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	In-band Telemetry (INT+INC)	CNIT, SSSA	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	RAN Telemetry Collector	ACC	100%	ARNO	Demo1
	Infrastructure Kafka Monitoring	SSSA	100%	ARNO, 5TONIC	Demo2
Network Functions					
	CU-UP	UVA, ERI-HU	100%	UVA/UNIPAMPA	PoC5
	UPF	ERI-HU	100%	NPT-Budapest	PoC7
	SOL Server	NEC	100%	5TONIC	Demo1 Demo2
	DetNet-PREOF	TID	100%	5TONIC	Demo2

Modules marked at 100% integration are fully deployed in testbeds and have completed functional validation. The IBN module is integrated at 50% as only selected features (SLA to intent translation) have been employed in the final demonstrators. The entire IBN framework has been integrated in the Ericsson product portfolio.

3.2 Functional Validation of Components

Functional validation of DESIRE6G Final Release components verified that integrated modules perform their intended functions correctly and meet interface specifications. This validation extends beyond the unit testing conducted during component development (WP3/WP4) by verifying behaviour in the integrated testbed environment with realistic workloads and interactions.

3.2.1 Validation Framework

The functional validation framework applied to both Demo1 and Demo2 encompasses four validation dimensions:

1. Interface compliance validation

Each component interface (REST API, gRPC, P4Runtime, etc.) was tested to confirm:

- Correct message format and protocol compliance.
- Proper handling of request/response exchanges.
- Error handling and timeout behaviour.
- Authentication and authorization mechanisms (where applicable).

2. Functional behaviour validation

Each component's core functionality was verified in the testbed environment:

- Data plane components correctly process and forward packets according to configured policies.
- Orchestration components successfully deploy and manage service lifecycle.
- Monitoring components (Telemetry Collectors, Agents) accurately capture and report performance metrics.
- Control components (MAS, SDN Controller) correctly compute and apply optimization decisions.

3. E2E workflow validation

Complete workflows spanning multiple components – as defined in D2.2 – were executed and validated:

- Service deployment workflow: User request → SO → OE → LNFVO → infrastructure provisioning → service activation.
- Service assurance workflow: Performance degradation → Telemetry Agent → MAS → LNFVO → infrastructure reconfiguration.
- Telemetry collection workflow: INT data → Telemetry Collector → aggregation → Telemetry Agent → MAS decision.

Workflow validation confirmed correct sequencing, data propagation, and error recovery across component boundaries.

4. Integration resilience validation

- System behaviour under failure and recovery scenarios was validated.

- Component restart and reconnection.
- Network connectivity interruption and restoration.
- Resource exhaustion and graceful degradation.
- Configuration error detection and correction.

These validation dimensions were applied systematically to both Demo1 and Demo2 integrations, with specific test scenarios adapted to each demonstrator's architecture and use case requirements.

3.2.2 Cross-Component Integration Testing

Beyond individual component validation, cross-component integration testing verified correct interaction patterns between modules from different architectural layers. Key integration points tested include:

SMO ↔ Optimization Engine Integration

The Optimization Engine (OE) enhances service deployment decisions:

- SO sends an aggregated and end-to-end service request to OE.
- OE fetches topology information from Topology Module.
- OE computes optimal placement of service components across sites.
- OE returns optimized service partitions to SO for deployment.

Integration testing validated:

- Correct topology representation and consumption by OE.
- Optimization algorithms produce feasible placement solutions.
- Optimized deployments achieve better KPIs than unoptimized baselines.
- OE response latency achieves near-real-time requirements (<100ms).

SMO ↔ IML Integration

The Service Orchestrator (SO) interacts with the Local NFVO (IML) to deploy service components:

- SO sends a service descriptor containing application functions and network function requirements.
- LNFVO provisions infrastructure resources (compute pods with infrastructure NFs, site-internal network paths).

- LNFVO deploys required AFs and NFs on the selected resources.
- LNFVO optionally deploys infrastructure NFs (NFR, UE2SM) via the infrastructure NF APIs (note that deployment is optional as some infrastructure NFs are pre-deployed, e.g., on a gateway switch).
- LNFVO configures infrastructure NFs (NFR, UE2SM) to implement the forwarding logic described in the service descriptor provided by SO.
- LNFVO reports deployment status to SO (success, partial success, failure).

Integration testing verified this interaction across various scenarios:

- Simple service deployment (single application, single site).
- Distributed application components coordinated by SO across multiple sites.
- Service modification (scaling, migration).
- Service termination and resource cleanup.

IML ↔ Programmable Data Plane Integration

The IML orchestrates lifecycle and configuration of P4-based data plane resources that are available on a site:

- IML LNFVO deploys infrastructure NFs (NFR, UE2SM and optionally Load Optimizer) and custom NFs on the allocated resources.
- IML LNFVO computes high-level forwarding rules according to the service graph and configure the infrastructure NFs.
- IML LNFVO uses different plugins for the deployment of custom NFs on hardware data plane targets (e.g., Intel Tofino).
- IML LNFVO deploys and configures the IML Control Plane Proxy (P4Runtime Proxy) between NF data and control planes.
- IML Control Plane Proxy translates logical P4 entries to actual P4 table entries available on the running hardware or software target.
- IML provides an API for the definition of flexible performance isolation policies among traffic aggregates. IML translates the high-level policies to low level configurations (throughput value functions) of the PPV traffic management method.

- PPV Traffic Management provides congestion-level information in terms of packet value threshold level to a Throughput-SLA watchdog process running on the CPU of the data plane target. The watchdog process is configured by IML according to the configured policies. If a policy is violated (i.e., the guaranteed minimum throughput cannot be satisfied) it triggers IML.
- IML triggers the activation of INT components in the data planes.
- Flow-level telemetry is collected separately by telemetry collectors for MAS consumption.

Integration testing validated:

- Correct rule translation from resource sharing policy to P4 table entries.
- Consistent state between control plane (e.g., IML Control Plane Proxy) and data plane (switches).
- Dynamic rule updates without service interruption.
- Dynamic forwarding graph reconfiguration after AF migration.
- Near real-time Throughput-SLA violation detection and policy reconfiguration.

MAS ↔ Pervasive Monitoring Integration

Multi-Agent System (MAS) agents consume telemetry data and make service assurance decisions:

- Telemetry Collectors aggregate INT reports from data plane.
- Telemetry Agents process and filter telemetry for MAS consumption.
- MAS agents analyze telemetry to detect SLA violations or performance anomalies.
- MAS agents trigger corrective actions via LNFVO or SDN Controller.

Integration testing verified:

- Timely delivery of telemetry data (sub-second latency).
- Correct interpretation of telemetry metrics by MAS agents.
- MAS decision-making logic produces valid reconfiguration requests.
- Closed-loop execution (detection → decision → action → verification).

These cross-component integration tests, conducted across both testbeds, confirmed that the DESIRE6G architecture operates as an integrated system, not merely as a collection of individual components. The functional validation results specific to Demo1 and Demo2 are detailed in sections 4.3 and 5.3, respectively.

4 Demo 1: AR with Perceived Zero Latency

4.1 Introduction, testbed and components

This demonstrator showcases the integrated 6G-ready DESIRE6G architecture designed to enable real-time telemetry, adaptive control, and AI-assisted service assurance for latency-critical applications such as Augmented Reality (AR) and autonomous systems. The demo validates a cloud-native, multi-domain framework that combines data plane programmability, advanced and multi-layer in-band network telemetry (INT), IML supported by local Kafka-based service monitoring with forecast engines, secure multi-agent systems (MAS) to achieve fine-grained monitoring and closed-loop control across edge, cloud, RAN, and x-Haul domains. The architecture promotes a unified telemetry and control model capable of dynamically reconfiguring network functions and services in response to changing conditions, ensuring continuous optimization and adherence to strict latency requirements.

The demonstrator is deployed on the federated ARNO testbed in Pisa, Italy, integrating an AR application deployed into distributed equipment (i.e. a drone, an edge node and an AR/VR headset) programmable switches, AI-assisted orchestrators, and distributed telemetry agents across multiple infrastructure layers. The showcased use case focuses on an AR-based mission scenario involving drones and AR headsets, where components are distributed across the user device, edge, and cloud to balance computation, latency, and bandwidth. Through real-time INT data collection and MAS-driven adaptation, the system guarantees end-to-end latency budgets even under network or service degradation. The results highlight the seamless integration of cloud-native orchestration, programmable data plane enforcement, and AI-enhanced telemetry analytics, demonstrating the DESIRE6G vision for resilient, autonomous, and performance-aware 6G infrastructures.

From a system perspective, the main features of this demo, differently from the Real-Time DT demonstration are the following: 1) the execution of an **end-to-end network service deployment, including network functions at the User Equipment**, and 2) the end-to-end deployment and service assurance in **a multiple DESIRE6G set of sites**.

4.1.1 Demo deployment

The demonstrator has been fully implemented and deployed in the ARNO integrated testbed. It has been deployed across two interconnected DESIRE6G sites, forming a federated multi-segment and multi-technology testbed that integrates RAN, SDN metro, and edge computing resources under unified telemetry and orchestration. The setup validates the DESIRE6G architecture using data plane programmability, AI-assisted monitoring, and multi-agent control for end-to-end service assurance in latency-sensitive AR applications. In particular, from the point of view of the DESIRE6G architecture framework, it covers deployment and service assurance of an end-to-end latency critical service, spanning two physical sites (Site 1, Site 2) and three logical sites (including the User Equipment and the drone as special Site 0).

FIGURE 22 HIGH-LEVEL VIEW OF DEMO 1 TESTBED SETUP

Site 0 hosts the drone and the associated AR app component (s-App) supported by programmable P4 switch and the User Equipment.

Site 1 hosts the RAN domain including the Benetel 5G radio units connected to the dRAX™ RAN platform. The secure Multi-Agent System (MAS1) provides telemetry collection and analysis. The Infrastructure Management Layer (IML1) is responsible for network functions deployment and re-optimization (e.g., scaling and placement, rerouting).

Site 2 represents the main orchestration domain, also including an Edge Cluster composed of Kubernetes-based compute nodes and programmable switches. It hosts the AR edge app providing augmented video to the Meta Quest 3 headset, as well as secure MAS2 and IML2 agents for continuous telemetry and analytics and network function deployment and re-optimization, respectively. The Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) layer is responsible for service deployment and coordinates the IML instances, as well as the distributed agents and interfaces with the SDNc to enforce adaptive service control policies.

Site 2 also includes an SDN-based metro network, enabling advanced in-band network control (INC) to capture latency performance metrics inside the SDN domain and react autonomously in case of deviation, thanks to a dedicated data plane active collector (DPAC). The overall system supports cross-site coordination between the MAS components and the SMO, ensuring that XR traffic meets stringent end-to-end latency requirements even under dynamic network conditions. In a real-life deployment it is likely that the SDN transport will belong to a standalone “site” (domain), but in our case since they are physically co-located, handling them inside site 2 made sense.

The details of the testbed and the mapping of the service within each single device is shown and explained in Section 4.5.1.

4.1.2 Components

The list of the DESIRE6G modules and components, designed and developed in WP3 and WP4 and integrated in Demo 1 is detailed in Table 5, along with the software repository pointers in the internal DESIRE6G repository and in Zenodo. The integration flavour and methodology, along with the high-level architectural mapping, are explained in Section 4.3.

TABLE 5 DEMO 1: LIST OF MODULES

System component	Module name	Module ID	Responsible	Project Repository pointer	Zenodo pointer
SMO	Data Lake	3.001	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Service Orchestrator	3.002	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Service Catalogue	3.003	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Topology	3.004	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369

SMO	Optimization Engine	3.010	UVA	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Optimization_Engine	https://zenodo.org/records/1577184
Intelligent Distributed Control, SMO	MLFO	3.007	UPC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/MLFO	Not open source
Intelligent Distributed Control	MAS Agents	3.008	UPC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/Multi-Flow%20Agent https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/RAN%20Agent	Not open source
Intelligent Distributed Control	SECAAS	3.009	TSS	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/tss_update_30062025/SECaaS_DLT	https://zenodo.org/records/15780450
IML	Local NFVO	4.1001	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
InfraNF	NFR	4.2002	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev/infra-nfs	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
InfraNF	UE2SM	4.2003	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev/infra-nfs	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
IML	P4RTProxy	4.3002	ELTE	https://github.com/P4ELTE/p4runti-me-proxy/tree/asyncio	https://zenodo.org/records/15773554
IML	P4DPA	4.301	ELTE	https://github.com/FBrisch/t4p4s	https://zenodo.org/records/15773693
Intelligent Distributed Control	Telemetry Agent	4.401	UPC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/Telemetry%20Agent	No open source
Pervasive Monitoring	Telemetry Collector	4.402	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA	https://github.com/zoxerus/desire6g	https://zenodo.org/records/15778438
Pervasive Monitoring	UE-INT+INC	4.403	CNIT, SSSA, UVA	https://github.com/zoxerus/desire6g	https://zenodo.org/records/15778438
Network Functions	RAN Telemetry Collector	4.404	ACC	Not open source	Not open source
Network Functions	CU-UP	4.501	ACC	Not open source	Not open source
Pervasive Monitoring	Infrastructure Kafka Monitoring	4.406	SSSA	https://github.com/asqamb/mon_manager/tree/main	https://zenodo.org/records/1577349

4.2 Goal of the Demonstrator and KPIs

In this section we report the main goals of the AR demonstrator and the KPI that have been evaluated.

4.2.1 Objectives

Objective 1 - Validation of a multi-layer, cloud-native 6G architecture integrating AI, telemetry, and serverless function orchestration.

The demonstrator aims at validating the DESIRE6G reference architecture presented in D2.2 [6] by showcasing the seamless integration of intent-based orchestration (SMO), distributed AI-based monitoring (MAS), and network function programmability (IML) across federated sites. The system leverages cloud-native and serverless principles to dynamically instantiate, scale, and migrate network and application functions on demand. This enables adaptive distribution of processing tasks across the RAN, transport, and edge domains while maintaining strict latency and reliability guarantees.

Objective 2 - Demonstration of hierarchical service assurance mechanisms with multi-layer triggers

The demo illustrates the multi-layer service assurance framework of DESIRE6G, highlighting the different reaction paces, visibility scopes, and granularities offered at each architectural layer, applied to the end-to-end one-way latency requirement. It targets three levels of service assurance through different multi-timescale control loops, as shown in Figure 23.

FIGURE 23: CONTROL LOOPS IN DIFFERENT LAYERS / TIME SCALES (FROM D2.2) AND THE ONES DEMONSTRATED IN DEMO1

At the data plane, the In-Network Control (INC) function reacts within microseconds (real-time model at data plane traffic management) to congestion or link degradation, autonomously rerouting affected traffic to pre-set backup paths: using pre-determined routing policies enforced in network functions.

At the infrastructure layer, IML modules enable millisecond-level response (near real-time model, local optimization) through workload scaling or migration in Kubernetes and serverless environments, with the help of Pervasive monitoring components (Kafka-based).

At the service layers, MAS utilizes service monitoring information (i.e., INT, RAN xApp metrics) and coordinates cross-site optimizations at sub-second timescale (near real-time model, service optimization), ensuring sustained SLA compliance and global service stability.

This demonstrates the hierarchical assurance concept of DESIRE6G, where fast local reactions and slower, broader optimizations operate in synergy for end-to-end resilience.

Objective 3 – Deployment of secure, distributed multi-agent systems for autonomous monitoring and reconfiguration

The demonstrator validates the use of securely attested Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) for autonomous decision-making and performance optimization. Each agent operates close to its monitored domain—RAN, SDN, or edge—processing real-time telemetry to detect anomalies and initiate localized reconfiguration. The D-MUTRA continuous runtime verification framework guarantees trustworthy coordination across agents and sites, while AI-based logic enables adaptive, self-healing behaviour guided by SMO policies.

Objective 4 – Realization of a distributed, serverless AR surveillance application as an end-to-end validation scenario identified as a key use case in WP2

The demonstrator employs a distributed Augmented Reality (AR) application as a real-world validation of the DESIRE6G architecture, as identified by WP2 in D2.1. The application uses serverless computing principles to deploy lightweight AI-based functions (e.g., object detection, pose estimation, and 3D reconstruction) dynamically across the drone, edge cluster, and AR headset. Each component—AR1, AR2, and AR3—can be elastically instantiated or migrated according to network and compute conditions. The system exploits real-time telemetry and hierarchical service assurance triggers to preserve an end-to-end latency below 10ms even under congestion, resource exhaustion, or RAN degradation. This

demonstrates DESIRE6G's capacity to sustain latency-critical, distributed serverless applications in a programmable 6G environment.

4.2.2 Target KPIs

Table 6 shows the KPI evaluated in Demo 1. We report the use case KPI identified in D2.1 [7] related to the AR/VR use case, with optional target evaluation, and the DESIRE6G Objectives KPI, identified in the project's proposal [8], related to O7 (demonstration), with mandatory target evaluation.

TABLE 6 DEMO 1 KPI

KPI type	KPI target	Measurements
AR/VR use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI1 -E2E latency: 5ms for the network, <20ms total (ideal), <50 ms total (tolerated)	End-to-end service latency
AR/VR use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI2 - Bandwidth (per-flow): 50-100Mbps (uplink), 130Mbps-960Mbps (downlink)	Service Throughput
AR/VR use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI3 - Reliability: 99%	Reliability
AR/VR use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI4 - Scalability. Number of drones per service: 1/10. Number of users per service: 100	Scalability
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.1: >1000 real/emulated devices, simultaneously requiring > 100 heterogeneous realistic services (including ultra-low latency-bounded services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMO scalability in the service orchestration of more than 100 AR services
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.2: all services handled with no manual intervention, including creation and suppression, based on the defined MAS system, with knowledge transfer among MAS for perceived infinite capacity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMO computation times of each module • IML computation times • IML instantiation times • IML/SDN flow entry enforcement times • Reconfiguration automation (IML, MAS, PDP)
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.3: <100ms AI-driven decision making (leveraging on appropriate HW acceleration) and re-optimization, guaranteeing the defined KQIs, including end-to-end latency from terminal to edge under varying traffic and service conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment: AI-driven deployment decision (OE) • In-band: reconfiguration at PDP • IML: forecast and reconfiguration • MAS: AI-driven decision
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.4: Dynamic serverless function placement with function redundancy and replication, and topology reconfiguration for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serverless app deployment placement

	application resilience with perceived zero-latency, in the sub-second scale.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IML-based serverless scaling/migration delay
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4.3 Demo1 Functional Validation

Demo 1 implements the Augmented Reality use case in the ARNO testbed and integrates all the main DESIRE6G architecture components. Specifically, as shown in Figure 24, it integrates software modules belonging to all the architectural layers (i.e., SMO, MAS, IML, infra NF, physical infra-layer). In Demo 1, the functional validation has been exploited by finalizing the integration of each involved component with a validation test against all its interacting components and the preliminary execution of all the planned workflows to check that all the steps are correctly handled by each component as planned and implemented.

FIGURE 24 DEMO 1: INTEGRATION OF THE ARCHITECTURAL LAYERS AND MODULES

Table 7 reports the integration map of demo 1, where each green cell represents the full bidirectional integration of two peer modules through an interface (I), each orange cell represents the master-slave module dependency in terms of parameter or function (F), each blue cell represents a deep integration through code or internal dependency (C). Up to 33 integration pairs between modules are enforced and tested in demo 1.

- The SMO part has been first validated in its northbound modules, with tests involving the SO, the service catalogue, the data lake, and the optimization engine. The aim was to check that the input service graph of demo 1 is correctly handled and processed, producing correct network

4.4 Implementation of the application

The demonstrator integrates a distributed Augmented Reality (AR) application designed to show real-time collaboration between aerial and human-operated agents through a 6G-enabled network infrastructure. The use case, fully described in deliverable D2.1 [7] represents a remote surveillance and situational awareness scenario, in which a drone and an AR-equipped operator cooperate to inspect and monitor an inaccessible or obstructed area, leveraging multi-site computing resources and AI-assisted analytics. Using AR Headset, the operator may have an augmented AI-enriched view of the occluded area, with the possibility of detecting objects, persons with their pose (e.g., identifying if they are alive and how they are moving).

4.4.1 Distributed AR application workflow

The application workflow is distributed across both Site 1 (RAN domain) and Site 2 (Edge domain), providing the required level of latency and computational efficiency to guarantee immersive experience and real-time involvement. The AR distributed service is depicted in Figure 25 Distributed AR application. The drone, connected via the 5G RAN, captures real-time video streams and transmits them to serverless function AR1, which performs object detection and initial pre-processing using AI models deployed at the drone payloads. The processed video and metadata are forwarded through the RAN and the SDN network to serverless function AR2, hosted in Site 2, where advanced pose estimation, segmentation, and data fusion are performed to refine the visual analysis.

At the final stage, AR3, executed on a Quest 3 AR headset, receives the reconstructed scene and semantic overlays, providing the surveillance operator with immersive situational awareness. The operator can visualize detected objects, obstacles, and human movements within the environment in real time. Control feedback, such as drone navigation adjustments or camera focus commands, is sent back to Site 1, closing the interactive control loop between the drone and the operator.

FIGURE 25 DISTRIBUTED AR APPLICATION

This distributed processing chain—spanning AR1 (object detection), AR2 (pose estimation), and AR3 (3D reconstruction and feedback)—demonstrates the low-latency, high-reliability, and AI-driven capabilities of the DESIRE6G architecture. The experiment validates how programmable networking, real-time telemetry, and multi-agent orchestration can sustain XR applications requiring sub-20 ms end-to-end latency, even under dynamically changing network or compute conditions.

4.4.2 Application Hardware and Software components

The following section details software and hardware components employed for the AR application: although it is a detailed description of any involved tool, this report goes besides the main objectives of Demo 1.

4.4.2.1 Application tools and software

The application system performs real-time visual analysis by using YOLO and ResNet deep neural network models to detect objects within a video feed. Concurrently, it employs a PoseNet model to estimate the body pose of any detected humans. To achieve maximum performance on its NVIDIA Jetson edge computing hardware, all models are optimized using NVIDIA TensorRT, which accelerates inference. Finally, the resulting data, such as bounding boxes and pose keypoints, is efficiently broadcast over the network using the low-latency Zenoh message system.

The system utilizes the GStreamer multimedia framework to manage and transmit the video feed efficiently. A flexible GStreamer pipeline is constructed to capture the raw video stream, often directly from a camera source. This raw data is then immediately processed by an encoder element to compress the video, reducing the bandwidth required for transmission. Then, the feed is packetized using RTP (Real-time Transport Protocol) and finally streamed over the network via a UDP sink, allowing other network-connected applications to receive and decode the live video feed with minimal latency.

The user wears a Meta Quest VR device running a native Unreal Engine 5 application on the headset, configured for augmented reality using the Meta XR Plugin and OpenXR. This setup enables the headset's passthrough cameras, allowing the user to see their real-world environment; the application uses a custom C++ network receiver to get bounding boxes and keypoints, that are rendered as a 2D overlay that appears perfectly "locked" onto the real-world objects and people visible through the headset's passthrough cameras.

4.4.2.2 Data Flow and Latency Management

The AR application relies on a multi-segment data flow that traverses the RAN, SDN transport network, and edge domains, supported by INT and AI-assisted control loops to ensure end-to-end latency compliance. Video frames and sensor data captured by the drone are processed at AR1, where telemetry tags are embedded using P4-programmable data plane functions. These metadata-carrying timestamps, queue occupancy, and hop latency—are propagated across the SDN network and collected at the edge for real-time MAS analysis. Further internal SDN latency metadata are processed in-network to minimize the latency of the SDN segment with in-network active control.

Within Site 2, the Kafka Monitoring and Service Multi-Agent System (S-MAS) continuously analyse the cluster state and the telemetry feedback, respectively. When network congestion, resource contention, or delay spikes are detected, the different layer triggers adaptive actions such as traffic rerouting, function migration, or dynamic resource scaling across edge and RAN domains.

This closed-loop control mechanism guarantees that the cumulative latency budget—comprising wireless transmission and transport delay time—remains within 6G service constraints. By coupling real-time INT monitoring with AI-driven orchestration decisions, the system maintains stable frame rates and low motion-to-photon delay, guaranteeing a seamless XR experience for surveillance operators.

4.4.2.3 Drone platform design, implementation and integration

This section details the design, development, integration, and validation of the Unmanned Aerial System (UAS) platform designed for the AR application. The main objective was to deploy a customized aerial platform equipped with computation capabilities, onboard sensing and autonomous flight capabilities. The 6G_UAS resulted in an autonomous quadcopter platform designed with a dual onboard computing architecture combining ARM- and x86-based companion computers. The flight control stack is built upon PX4 v1.15 and integrated with the MAVSDK library.

4.4.2.4 UAS Design, Configuration, and Component Selection

The development process started with a review of the state-of-the-art and an analysis of commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) components available to meet the specific project requirements.

- **Configuration Analysis:** A comparative analysis of different multi-rotor configurations was performed. The quad-rotor configuration was selected as the optimal solution, providing the best trade-off between payload capacity, size, and energy efficiency for the mission profile.
- **Airframe and Customization:** A commercial carbon-fiber frame kit (Holybro X500) was procured as the baseline frame. This frame has been modified to meet the project-requirements, primarily to ensure the correct housing and integration of the specific hardware components.
- **Avionics and Computation Architecture:** The use-case scenario set requirements for the computing architecture. The final design integrates:
 1. A Flight Control Unit (FCU) for the flight stabilization and the real-time drone control.
 2. An x86-based companion computer, dedicated to managing high-bandwidth and low latency 5G radio communications.
 3. An NVIDIA Jetson Orin NX ARM-based companion computer, featuring accelerated GPU computation, dedicated to executing real-time, onboard inference tasks (e.g., computer vision, AI inference and sensor fusion).

In particular, the Holybro Pixhawk Jetson Baseboard Bundle has been selected which embeds in a single board both the FCU and the NVIDIA companion computer (see Figure 26).

FIGURE 26 HOLYBRO JETSON BASEBOARD BUNDLE

4.4.2.5 Mechanical design, procurement and prototyping

To ensure the physical integration of the components onto the customized X500 airframe, several custom mechanical parts were required. These components were designed in-house (CAD) and then built using FDM 3D printing with tough PLA material. This approach speeds up the development process allowing for rapid iteration among improved components versions.

In Figure 27 a detail on the attachment for the vision module (a wide FoV stereo camera) payload is provided, along with the enclosure and attachment for the 5G communication module.

FIGURE 27 DRONE DETAILS OF THE CUSTOM-BUILT MECHANICAL SUPPORTS

The components were stacked vertically: the NVIDIA Orin NX and FCU are mounted on an upper plane, while the Intel NUC is setup at the bottom part and the drone power distribution layer has been organized in the middle of the two plates. The following components have been integrated on the 6G_UAS platform:

- Flight Control Unit (FCU): Pixhawk 6X

- ARM-based companion computer: NVIDIA Jetson Orin NX
- x86 companion computer: Intel NUC (Intel Core i7-1185G7)
- Power distribution board with nominal current capacity of 60A and Voltage and Current sense.
- Single point LiDAR range finder
- 4S LiPo 6300mAh battery
- Radio telemetry
- WiFi and 5G communication modules.

4.4.2.6 Low-level flight control unit (FCU) configuration

The PX4 open-source autopilot firmware (firmware version v1.15.4) was selected and configured on the FCU. This involved setting up basic parameters, sensor calibration, safety protocols and conducting flight tests in a controlled environment to tune the Roll, Pitch, and Yaw PID gains.

A series of flight tests were conducted to validate the platform's fundamental airworthiness and performance envelope. Data was collected to analyse key metrics, among them the most important are the control loop stabilization performance and current consumption

The attitude control loop was analysed, and control loop tuning have been performed and later the resulting drone stabilization capability has been validated. The validation tests showed how the estimated pitch closely tracks the provided setpoint (Pitch Setpoint in green) (Figure 28).

FIGURE 28 CLOSED LOOP CONTROL OF THE DRONE PITCH ANGLE

The correct operation of the propulsion system was verified to ensure that enough power was available to lift the platform and that the generated thrust was properly distributed among the motors. Figure 29 shows that the prototype can hover at around 60% throttle value providing a 40% thrust margin for

manoeuvrability. Also, the motor outputs were observed to be well-balanced confirming the proper weight distribution and proper mass allocation of the developed prototype.

FIGURE 29 ACTUATOR ANALYSIS

The power consumption analysis has been done to assess the proper design of the power distribution module as well as to estimate the flight time capability provided by the prototype. Figure 30 shows the recorded power consumption during a flight test (without payload). The current drawn in hovering was around 18A-19A with a 6300mAh 4S battery. The initial level increase is due to hysteresis of the battery.

FIGURE 30 DRONE POWER CONSUMPTION ANALYSIS

4.4.2.7 Autonomous flight software and high-level control

The autonomous navigation capability is provided to the drone by the NVIDIA companion computer exploiting the MAVlink protocol with the PX4 running on the FCU.

The MAVlink bridge has been implemented over ethernet connection between the two components (i.e. the FCU and the Jetson Orin NX): the FCU and the Orin NX IPs has been manually set to 192.168.0.3 and 192.168.0.4, respectively. Then on the FCU side, we started a MAVlink instance to send traffic to the Orin NX with the following command:

```
mavlink start -o 14540 -t 192.168.0.4
```

On the companion computer side, we installed the MAVSDK library and we designed a software Python-based software stack to enable high-level autonomous navigation. More in details, the implemented software can trigger offboard flight mode on the FCU and to interface with external devices to acquire drone pose information in real-time. The whole software modules have been developed with the NVIDIA JetPack 6.1. This architecture allows the Jetson Orin NX to receive pose data from the Vicon Tracker 4 motion capture system (via WiFi) and translate it into MAVLink setpoint commands sent to the FCU.

4.4.2.8 System integration and testing

The final development phase involved the full integration of the UAS platform within the designated flight arena, encompassing both hardware and software components.

The hardware activities included the installation and configuration of the complete payload on the drone, as well as the integration of VICON markers for precise pose tracking within the indoor test environment. This phase also comprised the deployment and configuration of the required telecommunication infrastructure, such as the 5G antennas.

FIGURE 31 FINAL DRONE PAYLOADS DIAGRAM

Figure 31 shows the final payloads diagram. The software integration focused on establishing communication between the UAS and the VICON Tracker software, as well as the telecommunication subsystems. Validation flights were subsequently performed to test the end-to-end system (i.e., steady state workflows). During these flights, all relevant data streams—including flight logs, telemetry, sensor

data from the companion computers, and inference results—were recorded for subsequent offline analysis.

4.5 Demonstration startup and workflows

The demonstration includes the setup and the execution of different workflows.

First, a startup and steady state workflow is considered (**W0**). This workflow considers the AR application working and running in the testbed, with the full DESIRE6G network functions already deployed and working. Detailed results about the application, including the drone metrics, the video streaming and artifacts are reported. Moreover, the steady state performance of the network is reported.

Two workflows are related to service deployment (**W1**) and MAS attestation and runtime verification through the SECaaS platform (**W2**). Service deployment involves all the architectural layers, from SMO down to the data plane. Secure MAS runtime verification involves the SECaaS modules and the MAS modules.

TABLE 8 DEMO 1 WORKFLOWS

Workflow	Title	Type	Involved layers
D1-W0	Steady state	Runtime	AR app, infra-NF, PDP
D1-W1	Service Deployment	Deployment	SMO, IML, infra-NF, PDP
D1-W2	Secure MAS Attestation and Runtime Verification	Runtime	MAS, SECaaS
D1-W3	Combined In-band control- MAS Service Assurance	Closed loop	PDP, MAS
D1-W4	IML-driven Service Assurance	Closed loop	Pervasive Monitoring, IML
D1-W5	MAS-driven Service Assurance	Closed loop	MAS

Additional three workflows are related to service assurance loops due to service degradations due to end-to-end latency violation (i.e., congestions, resource exhaustion at the edge, unexpected network rerouting), involving different DESIRE6G architectural layers. Workflow **W3** focuses on network congestion at the SDN network, with a double-layer service assurance provided by the programmable data plane through in-band control (real-time) and by the MAS (near real-time). Workflow **W4** focuses

on resource exhaustion forecast by the Kafka Pervasive Monitoring, recovered by IML LNFVO through service scaling, involving a single site. Workflow **W5** focuses on anomaly extra-latency induced in different network segments and sites (i.e., SDN network in Site 2 and the RAN in Site 1), detected and recovered by the MAS agents.

FIGURE 32 DEMO 1 WORKFLOWS MAPPED IN THE DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE

4.5.1 Startup and steady state

4.5.1.1 Site 0 and Site 1

In this section we describe the Site 0 and Site 1 mapping of each service chain component (application and network functions) within the testbed equipment and how it is realized. The mapping is shown in Figure 33. The details of the mapping in the different segments of Site 0 (drone) and Site 1 (RAN, control plane) are explained in the next subsections.

Site 0 - Drone setup

The drone is equipped with two independent payloads P1 and P2: a Jetson NX card, hosting the AR source app, and the x86 NUC, hosting the network functions and the 5G UE modules. Specifically, the Jetson run YOLO-based object detection on the images detected by the two cameras onboarded in the drone. Stream is passed to the x86, hosting the first DESIRE6G network function.

The NUC is equipped with an external Quectel GL-500 User Equipment modem, connected via USB-3 interface. Moreover, it hosts a P4 NIKSS instance with two interfaces. The NIKSS receives the application

traffic from the Jetson board and applies the first DESIRE6G network functions, i.e., the traffic enters here into the DESIRE6G domain. The UE to Service Mapper function (UE2SM) is employed first to create the D6G header. Then, a first UE-INT header is attached to store the traffic timestamps collected at the drone. This way, the drone acts as the data generation and measurement endpoint, embedding in-band telemetry (INT) capabilities at the UE via the definition of an end-to-end service.

FIGURE 33 SITE 0 AND SITE 1 MAPPING OF CONTROL AND DATA PLANE COMPONENTS

Site 1 - RAN setup

Site 1 includes the radio access level. The two Benetel radio units (RU1 and RU2) provide 5G connectivity for the drone-based AR application. The RUs connect via 10 Gbit/s links to distributed units (DU1 and DU2) running on the Accelleran dRAX™ platform, which in turn interface with the centralized unit (CU) and core network (CN) hosted on the node desire2 (10.30.7.12). This setup employs a fully disaggregated and cloud-native Open RAN (O-RAN) configuration developed by Accelleran, allowing flexible orchestration and integration with the intelligent control framework.

The internal details of the RAN are shown in Figure 34.

FIGURE 34 RAN DEPLOYMENT: INTERNAL NETWORKING DETAILS

On the left, the Accelleran server hosts two virtual Distributed Units (DU1 and DU2), each interfacing with a dedicated Radio Unit (RU) via front-haul interfaces (f1 for RU1, f2 for RU2). Additional 10GbE interfaces (i.e., f0 and f3) connect the vDUs to the mid-haul transport network, which bridges the RAN domain with the centralized processing layer. The transport network hosts a P4 switch used to create latency violations for specific service assurance experiments (see Workflow 5). This setup allows concurrent operation of multiple DUs, representing separate 5G cells or sectors, while maintaining centralized coordination through the CU.

On the right, the DESIRE6G2 server hosts two virtual machines: the RIC/CU (RAN Intelligent Controller and Centralized Unit) and the 5G Core Network (VM core). These are interconnected through a virtual bridge (br0) to the DESIRE6G control plane network and physically linked to the transport network via interface eno12409np1. A further interface, not shown in the figure, connects the server with the Tofino switch to connect the RAN with the SDN domain. This configuration provides an end-to-end functional chain from the radio interface to the 5G core, enabling testing and validation of O-RAN-compliant interfaces (F1, E1, and NG) and control loops. For the scope of the MAS workflow, the DU1 traffic (RAN control + user plane) is steered to interface f0, while DU2 traffic is steered to f3. The full RAN setup software versions, relevant configurations and interfaces specifications are reported in Table 9 and in Table 10.

TABLE 9 ACCELLERAN RAN FEATURES

Accelleran RAN features	Value
Split type	Split 7.2
dRAX software version	13.1.2

CU version	7.0.6
DU	4.1.0
Radio Channel	50MHz
TDD pattern	DSUUU [5ms]
Tx power	24 dBm

TABLE 10 ACCELLERAN RAN INTERFACES SPECIFICATIONS

Accelleran RAN interfaces	Value/Standard
FH MAC	3GPP TS 38.321 version 16.13.0
FH PHY, General description	3GPP TS 38.201 version 16.0.0
FH PHY, Physical channels and modulation	3GPP TS 38.211 version 16.10.0
FH PHY, Multiplexing and channel coding	3GPP TS 38.212 version 16.11.0
FH PHY, Physical layer procedures for control	3GPP TS 38.213 version 16.15.0
FH PHY, Physical layer procedures for data	3GPP TS 38.214 version 16.14.0
FH PHY, Physical layer measurements	3GPP TS 38.215 version 16.6.0
FH M-plane	O-RAN.WG4.TS.MP.o-R004-v17.01, RFC8071 for Call-Home
N2 NGAP	3GPP TS 38.413 v15.6.0
N2 Signalling transport - SCTP, IP	3GPP TS 38.412 v15.4.0
E1 - E1AP	3GPP TS 38.463 v15.6.0
E1 - Signalling transport - SCTP, IP	3GPP TS 38.462 v15.6.1
F1-C - F1AP	3GPP TS 38.473 v15.7.0
F1-C - Signalling transport - SCTP, IP	3GPP TS 38.472 v15.6.0
F1-C PDCP (for control plane only)	3GPP TS 38.323 v15.6.0
F1-C RRC	3GPP TS 38.331 v15.6.0
N3 Data Transport	3GPP TS 38.414 v15.2.0
N3 GTPv1-U	3GPP TS 29.281 v15.7.0
N3 PDU Session User Plane Protocol	3GPP TS 38.415 v15.2.0
E1 E1AP	3GPP TS 38.463 v15.6.0
E1 Signalling transport - SCTP, IP	3GPP TS 38.462 v15.6.1
F1-U - Data Transport	3GPP TS 38.473 v15.9.0
F1-U GTPv1-U	3GPP TS 29.281 v15.7.0
F1-U SDAP	3GPP TS 37.324 v15.1.0
F1-U PDCP	3GPP TS 38.323 v15.6.0
F1-U NR User Plane Protocol	3GPP TS 38.425 v15.6.0
E2	O-RAN.WG3.E2SM-KPM-R003-v05.0; O-RAN.WG3.E2SM-R003-v05.00; ORAN.WG3.E2SM-RC-R003-v06.00; O-RAN.WG3.E2AP-R003-v05.00; O-RAN.WG3.E2SM-CCC-R003-v04.00

FIGURE 35 ACCELLERAN DRAX DASHBOARD

FIGURE 36 ACCELLERAN XAPP DASHBOARD

Figure 35 shows the Accelleran dRAX dashboard configured for Demo 1. The dashboard shows the CU-UP configuration and the double DU/RU configuration with startup/reset/stop commands, along with the current state of each component. Figure 36 shows the xApps deployed in the dRAX. The UPC DESIRE6G xAPP performing Handover request is visible and its status is “Running” (see Workflow 5).

Site 1 DESIRE6G control plane and Tofino-based data plane

At the management and control plane, the secure MAS and the IML operate within a virtualized environment. S-MAS is deployed in dedicated virtual machine, while IML is deployed in the Kubernetes environment. The S-MAS interfaces with both the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) – responsible for near-real-time control of RAN behaviour – and the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) layer, which coordinates cross-site connectivity with Site 2.

The programmable P4 switch (Tofino instance 1) serves as edge point between Site 1 and Site 2, in the data plane space. It is connected to the RAN and the transport SDN network through multiple high-speed interfaces (100 Gbit/s and 40 Gbit/s), enabling per-packet monitoring and forwarding optimization. One instance of Tofino runs Network Function Routing (NFR) and telemetry insertion point (INT). Thus, a first one-way latency measurement on the application packets is available between the drone and the Tofino, acting as full RAN latency measurement point.

4.5.1.2 Site 2

In this section we describe the Site 2 mapping of each service chain component (application and network functions) within the testbed equipment and how it is realized. The mapping of the different subsections is shown in Figure 37 and Figure 38. And the technical details are explained in the next subsections.

SDN network

Site 1 is connected to Site 2 by means of a 40Gb/s link connecting the Tofino switch instance 1 to a SDN network, composed of different P4 software switches. The SDN network provides a programmable and telemetry-enabled transport layer for end-to-end 6G service orchestration. The infrastructure is composed of a set of P4-programmable switches (N1-N4) managed by an SDN controller (SDNc), monitored by MAS2 and handled by the IML2 layers.

Each node in the fabric (P4 N1-N4) implements in-band network telemetry and control (INC) functions, allowing extra metadata insertion and real-time path-level latency monitoring. The INC modules report latency and queue occupancy to the last node of the domain (i.e., N3), which implements the Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC). In fact, this node aggregates and analyses latency data of the SDN domain to detect performance degradations or anomalies. These insights are then used by the DPAC to trigger adaptive configuration updates—for instance, rerouting traffic or rebalancing loads—to maintain the required end-to-end latency and reliability guarantees. It is worth to note that INC functionality is handled fully in-network, in the data plane space, without resorting to IML or MAS for service assurance. In Workflow 3, we show the double-layer assurance performed by DPAC (real time) in the microseconds time granularity and by the MAS (near-real time) in the tens of milliseconds time granularity.

FIGURE 37 SITE 2 SDN DOMAIN IMPLEMENTING IN-BAND TELEMETRY AND CONTROL

The network topology follows a partially meshed layout, where P4 N1, N2, and N3 form the primary data path, and P4 N4 provides an alternative route for redundancy or congestion mitigation. The SDNc, implemented in Python, maintains real-time communication and flow rule configurability with each P4 node over dedicated control channels, while MAS2, SMO and IML2 modules operate at a higher orchestration layer, ensuring closed-loop feedback between telemetry, deployment, and control. The border interfaces em0 and em1 connect the SDN segment respectively to Site 1 and to the edge cluster of Site 2, creating a continuous monitored data plane across the entire demonstrator infrastructure.

Edge cluster

Site 2 hosts the Edge Cluster, which provides the execution environment for latency-sensitive AR applications, telemetry aggregation, and service orchestration functions.

At the infrastructure level, the cluster is interconnected through a P4-programmable Tofino switching fabric, consisting of two nodes:

- P4_1 (10.30.7.45), operating as a collector branch for in-band telemetry (INT) data generated along the end-to-end path (from RAN to edge across the SDN domain).
- Tofino1 instance 2 (10.30.7.53), enabling NFR and real-time INT.

The collected INT data are reported to the collector and processed by the s-MAS to detect and localize latency deviations along the end-to-end path (see Workflow 5).

FIGURE 38 SITE 2 CLUSTER NODE AND MANAGEMENT/CONTROL MODULES

The edge compute layer is composed of one server (P4_2), acting as final DESIRE6G NFR with D6G header decapsulation and packet forwarding to the edge app, and two NVIDIA Orin nodes (orin3 and orin4) running AI-enabled AR Edge Application (E-app). All the nodes run within a Kubernetes cluster environment and are attested to a local L2 switch. These E-apps receive the augmented streaming from the drone and apply further AR processing (i.e., pose estimation and 3D reconstruction), supporting adaptive rendering and quality adjustment for the Quest 3 headset connected locally to the cluster.

At the control and management plane, additional nodes host the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework coordinates all distributed components, including the secure MAS (S-MAS), IML, and orchestration submodules such as Service Orchestrator (SO), Data Lake (DL), Topology Manager, Optimization Engine (OE), and Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO). The SMO also maintains northbound interfaces to Site 1's MAS and IML, ensuring cross-site synchronization. The pervasive Kafka module oversees monitoring the state of the cluster containers and predict any future resource exhaustion (see Workflow 4).

4.5.2 Workflow 1: Service Deployment

The service deployment describes the initial procedure to orchestrate, compute and instantiate the application and the network functions along the sites to allow the full service operativity. This workflow

is shown in Figure 39 and describes the initialization process from the tenant request to when the network and the app is in full operational mode.

FIGURE 39 DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 1

Step 1 – Tenant request

The tenant sends a request to the Service Orchestrator (SO) for the initialization of the network service (1).

Step 2 – Get service description and topology

The SO issues a request to get the service description from the service catalogue (SC) (2) and the topology from the topology descriptor (3). This information is then used to generate the service graph.

Step 3 – Decomposition

The service graph is sent to the Optimization Engine (OE), which is issued with a decomposition request, runs the optimization algorithms (4) and provides all the pre-site network service descriptors at the end of the decomposition and optimization process (5).

Step 4 – Transport Connectivity and NF-graph deployment

The service orchestrator feeds the SDN controller with the descriptors and issues a request for starting transport connectivity (6), gets notified at the end of the initialization (7) and send sub-graph and NF flow rules to all the IMLs included in the network (8, 10). The IMLs deploy the required functionality and reply to the SO (9, 11). Note that steps 8 and 10 can be started in parallel.

Step 5 - Deployment ready

With its components initialized and working in standard mode **(12)**, the network is now ready to operate, providing a closed-loop communication channel between the drone and the AR headset, through the RAN, the three P4 switches and the Kubernetes Edge Cluster.

4.5.2.1 SMO modules functionality and service graphs

Demo 1 is structured across three sites. For the sake of deployment phase, the AR service is designed as end-to-end service including the User Equipment and the Drone. Thus, from the point of view of the deployment, the service spans three sites: Site 0 (drone and User Equipment), Site 1 (RAN site) and Site 2 (Edge Cluster site).

Initial Service Graph

The initial service graph, shown in the corresponding YAML NSD service graph structure is illustrated below, defines the full logical structure of the service before deployment.

```
lnsd:
  ns-instance-id: "11223344"
  ns:
    name: "ARVR Demol Scenario"
    id: "dl"
    vendor: "D6G"
    descriptor-version: "1.0"
    location-id: 40
    default-service-id: "30"
    infra-nfs: []
    network-functions: []
    application-functions:
      - instance-id: "edge"
        id: "arvredge"
        name: "AR edge app"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-nfids: [44,45]
        static-ips: ["10.30.7.213"]
        is-scalable: true
        instances: 2
      - instance-id: "src"
        id: "predeployed"
        name: "AR source app"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        is-ue: true
      - instance-id: "ran"
        id: "predeployed"
        name: "RAN"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "internal"
        is-ue: true
        static-nfids: [42, 43]
        static-ips: ["192.168.1.4"]
    forwarding_graphs:
      - graph-name: "upstream"
        direction: "upstream"
```

```

links:
  - id: "upstream-1"
    connection-points:
      - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
      - if-id-ref: "edge:0"
  - graph-name: "downstream"
    direction: "downstream"
    links:
      - id: "downstream-1"
        connection-points:
          - if-id-ref: "edge:0"
          - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
e2e_delay_budget: "25ms"

```

The descriptor begins with the identification and general metadata of the service, specifying the vendor information and the descriptor version to enable consistent version tracking.

```

nsd:
  ns-instance-id: "11223344"
  ns:
    name: "ARVR Demol Scenario"
    id: "d1"
    vendor: "D6G"
    descriptor-version: "1.0"
    location-id: "40"
    default-service-id: "30"
  ...

```

It then enumerates all types of functions required for the service, including infrastructure network functions, software network functions, and application functions.

```

infra-nfs: []
network-functions: []
application-functions:
  - instance-id: "edge"
    id: "arvrege"
    name: "AR edge app"
    version: "1.0"
    domain: "external"
    static-nfids: [44,45]
    static-ips: ["10.30.7.213"]
    is-scalable: true
    instances: 2
  - instance-id: "src"
    id: "predeployed"
    name: "AR source app"
    version: "1.0"
    domain: "external"
    is-ue: true
  - instance-id: "ran"
    id: "predeployed"
    name: "RAN"
    version: "1.0"
    domain: "internal"
    is-ue: true
    static-nfids: [42, 43]
    static-ips: ["192.168.1.4"]

```

The final part of the YAML representation includes the forwarding graphs assigned to the service and defines the total SLA end-to-end delay budget.

```

forwarding_graphs:
  - graph-name: "upstream"
    direction: "upstream"
    links:
      - id: "upstream-1"

```

```
      connection-points:
        - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
        - if-id-ref: "edge:0"
    - graph-name: "downstream"
      direction: "downstream"
      links:
        - id: "downstream-1"
          connection-points:
            - if-id-ref: "edge:0"
            - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
e2e_delay_budget: "25ms"
```

This representation defines how the logical components interact and defines the full scope of the service requirements.

In Demo 1, the service descriptor is sent from the Service Orchestrator (SO) to the Optimization Engine (OE) with a decomposition request.

Pre-Deployment Optimization

The objective of the OE is to compute the way a service graph should be deployed (decomposed) across the DESIRE6G sites including decomposing the corresponding SLO constraints, for example latency. It uses the constraints, abstracted resource availability from the infrastructure, and the service request specification, as presented in Figure 39.

When the OE receives the initial service graph in YAML format, it converts it into an internal graph representation using NetworkX [9]. This structure allows the OE to merge real-time site (aggregated resources) and topology information made available to the DESIRE6G SMO, shown in (Step 3 and 4) in Figure 39.

As described in Deliverable D3.2, Section 3.2, the OE uses a local Large Language Model (LLM)-based mechanism to select the most suitable optimization algorithm for this specific case. Specifically, the Algorithm Pool submodule contains a list of curated optimization algorithms in Python and additional metadata, such as Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) analysis, complexity analysis and numerical results of previous performance analysis, available in text format. The Prompt Generator submodule concatenates internal agentic pre-prompts, algorithm code analysis and previously evaluated performance, and an optional user defined prompt to guide the selection. The LLM Selector submodule is responsible for the communication with the LLM and handles cleaning the output, retries and re-prompting in case of an invalid response. Posterior of the selection, the graph is forwarded to the selected algorithm from the Algorithm Pool for optimization.

For Demo 1, the optimization scenario corresponds to service partitioning under latency constraints, and the OE decides between multiple simplified greedy service graph partitioning strategies to demonstrate the selection process, however in a real-life deployment the Algorithm Pool could be populated and

interfaced with any graph partitioning algorithm via the NetworkX [9] graph structure. A realistic scenario was demonstrated publicly by the University of Amsterdam in the SuperComputing 2025 conference in St. Louis, USA [10] and experimented with multiple partitioning strategies replicated from the recent literature, most notably [11] [12] [13] [14].

The OE executes the optimization process. The decomposed graph is then translated back into YAML service descriptors. These descriptors correspond to the respective subgraphs (partial service requests), mapped to DESIRE 6G sites designated by the OE. An example dedicated to the second DESIRE6G site is shown below.

```
lnsd:
  ns-instance-id: "55667788"
  ns:
    name: "Demol scenario partition site2"
    id: "d1"
    vendor: "D6G"
    descriptor-version: "1.0"
    site-id: "site2"
    location-id: "40"
    default-service-id: "30"
    infra-nfs: []
    network-functions: []
    site-connections:
      - id: "site1"
        application-functions:
          - instance-id: "ran"
            static-nfids: [42,43]
            static-ips: ["10.10.10.44"]
            is-ue: true
            network-functions: []
        application-functions:
          - instance-id: "app"
            id: "arvredge"
            name: "AR edge app"
            version: "1.0"
            domain: "external"
            static-nfids: [44,45]
            static-ips: ["10.30.7.213"]
            is-scalable: true
            instances: 2
            static-instance-ips: ["10.30.7.213", "10.30.7.214"]
    forwarding_graphs:
      - graph-name: "upstream"
        direction: "upstream"
        links:
          - id: "upstream-1"
            connection-points:
              - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
              - if-id-ref: "app:0"
      - graph-name: "downstream"
        direction: "downstream"
        links:
          - id: "downstream-1"
            connection-points:
              - if-id-ref: "app:0"
              - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
```

Each subgraph retains the structure of the original descriptor including its metadata fields and functional blocks but has been adjusted to match the resource capabilities of each DESIRE6G site to achieve the specified defined latency budget.

Once the OE finalizes the decomposition process, it returns the partial service NSDs to the SO as depicted in (Step 5). Then the SO forwards each subgraph to the corresponding IML instance, which then instantiate the required network functions and application components locally. The initial service is now deployed in an optimized and SLA-compliant way across the DESIRE6G testbed.

4.5.2.2 IML modules functionality and the network service chain

Two IML instances are used in this workflow; the first controls the resources at Site 1 while the second is responsible for Site 2. We assume that the service at Site 0 is pre-deployed (i.e., by executing a DESIRE6G app or a sidecar that includes required features and functionalities).

On Site 1, SMO sends the service subgraph as a local network service description (LNSD) to the first IML instance. This LNSD is simple, it interconnects the RAN to Site 2. In upstream (UE to edge) direction, in-band telemetry is turned on along the path, while in downstream (edge to UE) telemetry is not set. IML processes the logical subgraph, determines the physical path and configures the NFR and INT data plane components via the REST API of infraNF control planes to setup connectivity.

On Site 2, the logical subgraph contains the application function to be deployed on the local K8S cluster. IML first determines the node for the AF, deploys the application and then creates NFR and UE2SM instances (software instances of the infraNFs) on the K8S cluster connected to the AF and the local D6GGateway. Then IML configures the infraNFs' data planes including NFR, UE2SM and the in-band telemetry components through their REST-based control plane API. In upstream direction, the INT and DESIRE6G headers are eliminated before reaching the AF. The INT reports are also collected and forwarded to the pre-deployed telemetry collector of the site. In downstream direction, the AF traffic is first sent to the UE2SM instance running in the K8S cluster as a software infraNF. It extends the packets with the DESIRE6G header and pass the packets to the NFR data plane component for forwarding. In downstream direction, telemetry is turned off. IML acts as an intermediate layer between SM and K8S (used as VIM), deploys the AF and infraNFs - if needed - and configures the data plane path from the entry points of the site to the exit point (i.e., ingress of the AF).

4.5.2.3 SDN controller

The SDN controller is responsible for the configuration of the programmable switches. In deployment phase it receives requests for connectivity from the SMO, triggering the calculation of network routes and the activation of required network paths. The SDN controller tries always to calculate a primary and a backup path. The SDN domain uses a Layer-2.5 (L2.5) forwarding protocol based on labels, where each label identifies a set of flows (one or more flows) that share the same source and destination as well as a priority value. This L2.5 header is inserted into each packet at the ingress of the SDN domain and is removed at the egress domain so that the routing within the domain is transparent to the packet. This L2.5 header contains also a cumulative field for collecting the queuing delay at each of the switches along the path, where each switch adds its queuing delay to the value already present in the header, this allows the last node in the path to check each packet at line speed for latency violations making it act as a Data Plane Active Collector where immediately an In-band Network Control (INC) message is sent to the first node in the current path to change the routing of the packets to the backup path with a delay on the order of the forwarding delay of the switch itself allowing the SDN domain to react in real time to traffic bursts.

4.5.3 Workflow 2: Secure MAS Attestation and Runtime Verification

This workflow describes the MAS attestation and runtime verification procedure and starts after the MAS deployment and initial mutual attestation workflow, demonstrated in PoC9 (Section 6.9). For this reason, the messages in this workflow start from step 15 after the secure MAS communication procedure.

This workflow has been implemented, tested and validated at the ARNO testbed.

FIGURE 40 DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 2 ON SECURE MAS ATTESTATION RUNTIME VERIFICATION

Runtime Verification

In runtime mode, the agent is free to start immediately, without waiting for any attestation result. The verification process is **continuous, on-demand, and non-blocking**.

The sidecar acts as an independent *runtime attestator*:

1. It continuously inspects the agent's process memory and extracts the .text section from the memory pages actually loaded by the CPU at runtime.
2. It computes a fresh SHA-256 measurement at high frequency.
3. To avoid any performance impact on the agent, we limit the CPU usage of the attestator to **10% using Linux cgroup v2**. This guarantees that:
 - the agent always has full CPU availability,
 - attestation progresses continuously in the background,
 - the system maintains integrity monitoring with **zero latency penalty**.

Because memory hashing is significantly faster than a full blockchain attestation cycle, the sidecar aggregates multiple consecutive fresh measurements. Once an aggregated measurement is ready, it is submitted to the DLT together with the attestor measure **(15)**.

Upon receiving the measurement:

- The smart contract elects a verifier node. If this is the first attestation cycle, the **SECaaS** acts as verifier **(16)**.
- The verifier retrieves the trusted reference measurement and compares it against the fresh aggregated measurement.
- If any deviation is detected, the anomaly is immutably recorded on the DLT **(17)**.

As soon as the verification cycle finishes, a new cycle automatically begins, maintaining *continuous* runtime assurance without ever disturbing the agent's execution. The agent continues running normally, while the attestator ensures real-time detection of tampering or code modification attempts **(18)**.

4.5.3.1 SECaaS and Sidecar implementation

This complete remote attestation architecture designed for distributed, multi-agent environments such as edge computing, robotics, and cloud-native systems. Its goal is to ensure continuous runtime integrity verification of software agents operating in untrusted environments. The system relies on three tightly

integrated components: a **SECaaS wrapper**, a **Go-based attestation sidecar**, and a **blockchain smart contract**.

1. SECaaS Wrapper (Python)

The wrapper serves as the central authority for onboarding and preparing agents for attestation. Its main tasks include:

- Extracting the .text section from ELF binaries and computing SHA-256 code fingerprints.
- Computing expected reference signatures using digest aggregation rules, simulating what the prover will do at runtime.
- Analyzing the sidecar binary and incorporating its hash into the integrity chain.
- Producing JSON configuration files that include text section size and blockchain parameters.
- Persisting binary metadata and signatures in PostgreSQL.

This “reference signature generation” enables later runtime comparisons against fresh measurements.

2. Attestation Sidecar (Go)

The sidecar is deployed next to each agent (container or process) and performs **continuous, low-latency** runtime attestation. Its responsibilities include:

- Locating the agent’s .text memory segment (using prefix matching).
- Continuously hashing the agent code through `/proc/<pid>/mem`.
- Aggregating 300 consecutive identical digests by default (the *prover threshold*) before submitting evidence.
- Performing **self-integrity**: hashing its own .text section at runtime and embedding it into the combined attestation digest.
- Acting as both **prover** and **verifier** depending on the role assigned by the blockchain.
- Interfacing with the blockchain client and emitting Prometheus-ready metrics.

Self-integrity ensures that not only the agent binary, but also the verifier itself, remains trustworthy.

3. Blockchain Smart Contract (Hyperledger Besu)

The blockchain acts as immutable, decentralized evidence storage. It coordinates the attestation workflow through defined states:

1. *Open* – evidence submitted.
2. *ReadyForEvaluation* – reference signatures available.
3. *Closed* – attestation completed.

It also elects the verifier and stores both reference and fresh signatures. The smart contract ensures non-repudiation, prevents replay attacks, and provides tamper-proof traceability.

4. End-to-End Attestation Workflow

The full cycle works as follows:

1. The prover continuously hashes agent memory and aggregates digests.
2. After reaching the threshold, the sidecar computes the combined digest (agent + sidecar).
3. Evidence is submitted on-chain as signatures.
4. The blockchain notifies the SECaaS oracle or elected verifier.
5. Reference signatures are submitted.
6. The verifier compares fresh vs. reference signatures.
7. The smart contract records the result and closes the attestation.

4.5.4 Workflow 3: Combined In-band control-MAS Service Assurance

This workflow describes how the network counteracts a latency increase exploiting a double layer service assurance, first with a rapid real-time in-band control service to assure the maintenance in the quality of service, then using the near-real time control provided by MAS. The service is aimed to activate when, during the AR app working, latency increase spikes would compromise quality of service. The workflow is illustrated in Figure 41 and described below.

FIGURE 41 DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 3

Step 1 - INT processed at DPAC and MAS

Application traffic packets with latency metrics are analyzed at the sink node equipped with DPAC (INC labels reporting SDN hop latency metrics), while segment INT reports are exported to the Telemetry Collector (1) aggregating per-flow latency and congestion indicators. The Telemetry Collector processes INT generating performance anomaly reports forwarded to the MAS (2). INT reports are locally analyzed and communicated to the other agent in the MAS (3).

Step 2 - DPAC extra-latency detection and intervention

The SDN network is fed with extra traffic spikes, specifically targeting N1 and N2 with extra traffic generation affecting N1-N2 link. The induction of this extra traffic determines congestion at N1 and a latency increase. The latency increase is immediately detected by the INC-DPAC service, deployed at Node 3 (sink). DPAC provides immediate feedback to Node 1 using INC message, communicating the involved traffic label and the N1 backup port indication (see D4.3 section 7.2 [15]).

Step 3 - MAS Notification and PDP reconfiguration

Network and flows changings are communicated to the MAS agents in the same way as Step 1 through the Telemetry Collector (5, 6) to grant distributed awareness about the current configuration and traffic status in the network. In the case of sub-optimal flows placement due to the local INC reconfiguration, the MAS decides to trigger PDP reconfiguration communicating with the SDN Controller, in charge to configure the optimal flow and traffic distribution along the network. The reconfiguration may take place

in a different network segment (as depicted for the sake of generality in Figure 41). In the specific test execution, the re-optimization takes place at the same SDN domain in Site 2.

4.5.4.1 INC modules functionality and operation

The In-band Network Control (INC) is implemented in the programmable data plane using the P4 language and it works in the SDN transport domain leveraging the L2.5 label forwarding. It uses two distinct headers, one is for performing the routing and monitoring of queuing delays (named SDN INT) and the second is for performing the control and rerouting of the packets (called INC) within the domain. The first header is the routing and monitoring header and is defined in P4 in the following way shown in Figure 42.

```
header sdn_int_t {  
    bit<16> sdn_label;  
    bit<16> original_ether_type;  
    bit<48> sdn_latency;  
}
```

FIGURE 42 P4 DEFINITION OF THE IN-BAND INT HEADER

The SDN INT header is added to the packet right after the ethernet header by the ingress node in the SDN domain and the header contains three fields as shown in Figure 42, the first field is the `sdn_label` which is a 16 bit field, this label is assigned by the controller and is globally unique, furthermore, it is recognized by all nodes in the path. The label itself represents a set of flows which can be one or more flows grouped by source and destination as well as priority, meaning that if two sets of flows share the same source and destination but differ by priority, they will get assigned two different labels. Subsequent nodes in the SDN that come after the ingress node will read the label field and perform the routing based on the label. While the egress node will remove the L2.5 header and forward the original packet outside the domain. When the SDN INT header gets inserted the ethernet-type field of the ethernet header will be changed to indicate the presence of the SDN INT header, therefore it is necessary to preserve the original ethernet-type field, this is done by storing the ethernet-type field of the original packet in the 16-bit `original_ether_type` field of the SDN INT packet, so when the packet exits the SDN domain the value of this field is copied back to the ethernet-type field of the original packet. The third and last field of the SDN INT header is the 48-bit `sdn_latency`, which starts at zero when the SDN INT header is first inserted and then gets updated (by adding queuing delay) by each node in the network path including the ingress node which inserted the SDN INT header, The SDN controller then

at each egress node of different network paths (identified by different labels) configures a latency threshold that get checked for each packet at the SDN Egress node which also acts as the Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC), when a violation of the set threshold is detected, an In-band Network Control message is generated immediately by the DPAC from the packet where the violation has happened and is forwarded to the ingress node, the definition of this INC header is shown in Figure 43 and is composed of three fields, first one is a 16-bit `sdn_label` which is the backward control label that serves for sending the control message to the ingress node. Then there is a 7 bit reserved field filled with zeros as it is not used and serves to give the header a length that is a multiple of an integer number of bytes, then finally there is the `output_port` field which has a length of 9 bits and basically it tells the ingress switch where to reroute the traffic of the monitored flow (the flow that is suffering from an increase in queuing delay). The ingress switch knows which flow to reroute based on the received INC `sdn_label`.

```
header sdn_inc_t {
    bit<16> sdn_label;
    bit<7> reserved;
    bit<9> output_port;
}
```

FIGURE 43 P4 DEFINITION OF IN-BAND NETWORK CONTROL PACKET

Test results of the SDN In-band Network Control show the possibility of performing the reroute on the order of the speed of packet forwarding by the switch. This framework of in-band network telemetry and control is achieved by using P4 tables and registers to assign the output port of the incoming packets. Where a table assigns labels to incoming packets to identify their destination and priority (latency threshold) and then by mapping the label to a register number it is possible to read and write the output port in the data plane itself without the direct controller interaction enabling real time packet forwarding and rerouting. After the rerouting in the data plane happens which serves as an immediate remedy to the congestion problem caused by traffic bursts, the SDN controller is informed about this new configuration by the egress node that triggered the In-band Network Control so the controller can update its network description and recalculate the routing in the SDN domain.

4.5.4.2 MAS modules functionality and operation

The MAS consists of two distinct agents: the Multi-Flow Agent (deployed at Site 1) and the Telemetry Agent (deployed at Site 2).

The Telemetry Agent is responsible for collecting, processing, and transmitting INT data to the Multi-Flow Agent. The Telemetry Agent integrates with the P4 Telemetry Collector by exposing a REST API through which telemetry data is periodically injected. The data processing workflow typically involves summarizing the collected information and reducing the number of forwarded measurements when no significant variations are detected. Additionally, the telemetry data is forwarded to an InfluxDB instance for long-term storage, visualization, and further analysis. The Telemetry Agent exposes the following endpoint:

- **/collector**: receive INT reports from the Telemetry Collector.

The Multi-Flow agent is responsible for monitoring the different segments of the network to ensure the QoS requirements of the service. In this case, it receives the INT collected by the Telemetry Agent to feed a DRL algorithm that computes the optimal percentage of traffic that the ingress route should send to each path of the packet network. Upon the arrival of a rerouting notification, the Multi-Flow agent sends a petition to the SDN Controller to apply a new routing policy. The Multi-Flow agent exposes the following endpoint:

- **/QoS**: receive processed INT reports from the Telemetry Agent.

4.5.5 Workflow 4: IML-driven Service Assurance

This workflow describes how the DESIRE6G architecture counteracts a CPU overload in its main channel, deploying traffic and requests to different nodes, assuring service through IML-driven intervention, by means of the Infrastructure Monitoring provided by Kafka Monitoring and Forecast Engines. Thus, with the AR application pod running in the Kubernetes cluster at the Edge, a load increase is induced in the hardware currently involved in the traffic, determining an alert to the IML which triggers the application scaling request, exploiting the P4 switch to re-route the traffic through a different application pod in the cluster. It is worth to note that IML-based service assurance operates inside its controlled site (Site 2). The workflow is depicted in Figure 44 and described below.

FIGURE 44 DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 4

Step 1 - CPU load increase

While the network is working in standard mode, a CPU load is induced **(1)** to the ORIN currently involved in the traffic: the CPU load increase is collected by the Pervasive Kafka monitoring service.

Step 2 - Forecasting, prediction and alarm

Due to the CPU load, the Pervasive Kafka service processes monitoring data and predicts a violation in the app SLA **(2)**, feeding an alarm notification to the IML.

Step 3 - IML migration/scaling

As the IML is alarmed, it issues a command to start the recovery. Recovery may consider either migration or resource scaling.

In the case of app migration, the IML (LNFVO) communicates with the involved cluster nodes to first instantiate a replica pod in Node 2 **(3a)**, following the make-before-break approach. Once notified about the successful operation **(3b)**, the IML sends traffic steering command to the cluster internal P4 switch to deviate the traffic towards the new pod **(4)**. In the figure, the IML talks with a SDN controller for sake of generality **(5)** and receives an outcome ack **(6)**. In this specific workflow, the LNFVO sends forwarding flow rules directly to the P4 switch resorting to its deployed network service graph (i.e., 4 and 5 are

collapsed in a single message). After steering, traffic is recovered and the IML can delete the old pod instance (7a, 7b).

In the case of resource scaling, two instances of the pod are pre-instantiated in the cluster (primary and backup). After the alarm for CPU load is raised, the IML skips instantiation/deletion operations and directly performs traffic steering from the affected (primary) pod instance to the backup one (4, 5, 6).

4.5.5.1 Service Kafka Monitoring functionality and operation

The Kafka-based service Monitoring component has been adopted in the demo to collect periodically and in real-time the relevant metrics (CPU and RAM occupation). In this case the Monitoring Manager component is exploited. The module offers a REST-based API to trigger the activation of a new monitoring job pertaining to a specific pod running in the cluster. More specifically, Figure 45 shows the details of the APIs exposed by the Monitoring Manager, respectively (top down), to get details of active jobs, to start a new monitoring job or to deactivate an active job. To start a new monitoring job few parameters are needed, including “service-name”, “namespace” and “pod-name”.

FIGURE 45. MONITORING MANAGER API.

The monitoring system has a period of 5s and provides data in a csv-like format, including timestamp, cpu (mcore), RAM and number of connected clients.

Another relevant component, adopted for this purpose, is the forecasting manager, shown in Figure 46. Also in this case, a REST-based module has been developed to spawn forecasting jobs. In particular, the

API allows to trigger the activation of a new forecasting job, to deactivate an existing one or to retrieve the details of existing jobs.

To start a forecasting job, three parameters are needed: the “service-name”, the “namespace” and the “pod-name”. The module reads from a dedicated Kafka topic (with topic name “service-name”_”namespace”_”pod-name” data sent by the monitoring job and computes the CPU forecasted version. When the forecasted CPU exceeds a threshold, an alert is sent to the IML.

FIGURE 46. FORECASTING MANAGER API

Figure 47 shows the trend of forecasted CPU and real CPU during the system validation. In particular, the plot shows how the orange curve (the forecasting of the CPU) anticipates the trend of the real CPU. For the validation, the the load of the CPU has been realized in the pod with a ad-hoc designed process, causing the 10% CPU load increase.

FIGURE 47. FORECASTING PLOT OF THE CPU (IN ORANGE) VS THE REAL CPU (IN BLU).

Figure 48 reports the overall integration of the three relevant components for this procedure. The IML-LNFVO, after the service instantiation, triggers the activation of a new pervasive monitoring with forecasting capability. For this purpose, a new forecasting job is activated, sending a REST PUT to the forecasting engine, providing “service-name”, “namespace” and “pod-name”. The forecasting engine, acting as single endpoint, triggers the instantiation of a specific monitoring job, sending a REST PUT to the monitoring Manager component (using the received input parameters). Under normal conditions, the forecasting CPU is computed by the forecasting job, by consuming input metrics read from the Kafka topic related to this job. Once a critical condition is detected, an alarm is sent, using a REST POST towards the IML-LNFVO triggering the scaling of the pod instances.

FIGURE 48. IML-LNFVO, FORECASTING ENGINE AND SERVICE MONITORING MANAGER INTERACTIONS.

4.5.5.2 IML LNFVO functionality and operation

The local IML instance in Site 2 first starts a forecasting job that automatically starts the required monitoring task. During operation, IML gets a notification on SLA violation via a REST API, indicating that the worker node hosting the application pod has started overloading. As a reaction, IML replicates the pod on a less loaded node via generating the manifests by its internal Helm-based template system and do the deployment through the standard K8S APIs. This step also includes the creation of a virtual network link to the D6GGateway (aggregated NFR and UE2SM) instance handling the node where the AF is running. Then it reconfigures the table entries in the NFR instance running in the K8S cluster (the last hop before the application) via its REST API (SDN Ctrl in Figure 44). The NFR then forwards the traffic to the new pod. Finally, IML deletes the old pod via the standard K8S API. In case of stateless transport protocols (e.g., UDP streams) this process works seamlessly, and the migration does not cause notable performance drops (1-3 packets were dropped in our experiments). This workflow only uses Site 2.

4.5.6 Workflow 5: MAS-driven Service Reconfiguration

In this workflow, AR service assurance is evaluated against a latency anomaly event occurring at different sites and network segments, i.e., the SDN network and the RAN, assuming that these portions of the end-to-end data plane are not served by real-time in-band telemetry and control (INC), as in Workflow 3.

INT metadata collected from the UE to the edge node are exploited to trigger the intervention of the MAS agents, the third layer of the D6G architecture, that supervises the deployed AR service SLA along the different data plane segments.

Latency anomaly events are created in the SDN domain using extra congestion traffic as in Workflow 3, while latency events are created in the RAN domain in more sophisticated way. Most latency anomaly events occurring inside the RAN are particularly difficult to detect, locate and notify to service assurance layers. In fact, if the anomaly occurs inside the DU, CU and CN containers (CPU overloading, resource exhaustion), the RIC has the capability to intervene along with the internal Kubernetes agents with migration or scaling operations, similarly to Workflow 4 related to the edge application. However, if the latency anomaly affects the internal RAN subnet, for example the mid-haul segment, the RIC may not be aware and failure localization is not trivial.

FIGURE 49 DELAY TUNER AT THE RAN MID-HAUL

Latency anomaly events at the RAN are created as follows. Figure 49 shows how the user-plane latency anomaly occurrences are created within the disaggregated RAN architecture. A P4-programmable switch is placed in the mid-haul path between the DUs and the CU. This switch hosts the User Plane Delay Tuner, a custom P4 network function that emulate controlled latency impairments and evaluate the responsiveness of the service assurance mechanisms. The Delay Tuner allows the injection of deterministic delays into user-plane traffic, simulating real-world congestion or processing bottlenecks.

It is worth to note that the RAN control plane traffic is not affected by any additional delay, since flow rules are configured to trigger delay only to user plane flows, identified by different subnetting. Such delay is not intercepted by any of the RIC metrics, thus the RAN cannot intervene directly. Instead, UE-INT metadata collected at the MAS allows to detect the cumulated delay at the RAN segment, at the SDN segment and e2e. This allows the MAS to identify the problem at the RAN network excluding container-based issues, suggesting the handover from DU1 to DU2 to circumvent the issue in the mid-haul segment.

FIGURE 50 DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 5

Figure 50 shows the workflow steps involving the relevant DESIRE6G components. This workflow demonstrates the reaction loop of the DESIRE6G architecture when a network degradation (e.g., link congestion or increased latency) occurs, involving both data-plane telemetry triggers and control-plane corrective actions coordinated through the MAS. The steps correspond to the numbered interactions in the figure.

Step 1 - In-band Telemetry Degradation Detection

The P4 programmable nodes communicate the latency metadata degradation event through UE In-Band Network Telemetry (INT) and the Telemetry Collector module. INT metadata is immediately exported to the Telemetry Collector, which aggregates per-flow latency and congestion indicators. At the same time, RAN telemetry metrics are exported to the Site 1 MAS.

Step 2 - Data Collection and Reporting

The Telemetry Collector processes and correlates the received INT packets, generating performance anomaly reports. These reports include time-stamped latency metrics, including e2e latency, RAN latency and SDN latency. The collector then forwards summarized information to the MAS Agent.

Step 3 – Event Detection by the MAS Agent

Upon receiving the telemetry report, the MAS Agent performs AI-based anomaly detection and confirms that a service degradation has occurred. Depending on the severity and scope of the issue, the MAS may choose between triggering a direct corrective action (involving -service level functions) or escalating to a higher orchestration layer (SMO). This step represents the near-real time assurance reaction with hundred millisecond-level responsiveness. Interaction with MAS agents of different sites is performed to detect, localize the anomaly and take the most appropriate countermeasure to recover the end-to-end latency.

Step 4a – Transport Path Reconfiguration via SDN Controller

When the degradation is localized within the SDN network, the MAS Agent notifies the SDN Controller, requesting a path reconfiguration. The controller interacts with the P4 switches using P4Runtime or switch CLI (e.g. Thrift), computing an alternative route that bypasses the affected link or node. The new forwarding rules are pushed to the P4 nodes, restoring optimal performance.

Step 4b – RAN Reconfiguration through the RIC xApp

If the anomaly originates from the RAN segment, the MAS Agent communicates with the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) via its xApp interface. The xApp may initiate a handover procedure (e.g., from RU1-DU1 to RU2-DU2) to mitigate congestion or interference.

Step 5a – Feedback from SDN Controller to MAS Agent

In case of SDN reconfiguration, once the SDN Controller completes the reconfiguration, it sends a status notification to the MAS Agent confirming the successful rerouting. The MAS updates its local knowledge base and triggers telemetry verification to validate the new path's performance metrics. This ensures that service continuity and SLA compliance are fully restored.

Step 5b – End-to-End Re-optimization and Confirmation via RIC xApp

In case of RAN reconfiguration, the RIC xApp receives feedback from the MAS confirming service recovery and updates its policy models. This closes the multi-layer assurance loop, linking fast data-plane reactions, infrastructure-level corrections, and control-plane optimization in a hierarchical manner. The workflow thus demonstrates DESIRE6G’s ability to achieve MAS-layer service assurance, achieving hundreds-of-milliseconds-level optimizations. The tests and results are reported and discussed in Section 4.6.

4.5.6.1 UE-INT and Telemetry collector functionalities

The picture of Figure 51 shows the end-to-end application and network functions across the three sites, along with the protocol stack used in each segment. The figure shows the details of the uplink (drone->Headset), similar treatment is applied to the downlink. Many packet manipulations are performed on the app packets. In this specific workflow, three INT probe points are considered. Probe 1 is performed at the drone, when the packet enters the DESIRE6G domain. Probe 2 is performed at the end of Site 1, just after the Core Network at the Tofino switch. Probe 3 is performed at Site 2 just before the cluster. Thus, at the collector, the end-to-end network latency is available, including the delay details of T2-T1 segment (RAN latency) and T3-T2 segment (SDN segment). This information is provided to the MAS for latency anomaly detection and localization.

FIGURE 51 DEMO 1 NF FLOWS, LABEL STACKING AND INT PROBES

The DESIRE6G end to end telemetry starts with from the User Equipment (UE) by inserting the D6G INT header right after the Desire6G main header, with timestamps taken at three different points in the network to identify the location of the congestion. The P4 header definition is shown in Figure 52 where the header carries four fields, first one is a 16 bit next_header field used to restore the ether_type field of the ethernet header when the d6g_int header is removed from the packet at the end of the end to end path. Then, three timestamp fields follow, they serve to take the timestamps of the packet as it traverses the network, first timestamp is filled by the UE while the second timestamp is filled by the Tofino switch in the RAN segment (Site 1), and the last timestamp is filled by the Tofino switch in Site 2.

```
header d6gint_t {
    bit<16> next_header;
    bit<48> t1;
    bit<48> t2;
    bit<48> t3;
}
```

FIGURE 52 P4 DEFINITION OF THE D6GINT HEADER

For the synchronization of the clocks between the UE and the Tofino switch in Site 1, we use a special clock_sync packet, this packet is defined in P4 in Figure 53 . This packet is bounced back and forth between the UE and the Site 1 Tofino, where at each bounce the 8 bit count field is incremented and the relevant timestamp field is filled. The process is initiated by the INT collector which sends the clock_sync packet to the Tofino with count = 0. At which point the Tofino checks the count field and finds that its value is equal to zero so it inserts its timestamp in field t0 and increases count to 1, and then forwards the packet to UE which in its turn checks the value of count and finds it to be equal to 1, so it inserts its timestamp in the field t1 and increments count to be equal to 2, and sends the packet to the Tofino, which checks the count field and finds that its value is equal to 2 so it inserts its timestamp in the field t2, increments the count field, and then sends back the packet to the UE which updates the remaining t3 and count fields, and at this point with the four timestamp fields all filled, the packet is sent to the INT collector.

```
header clock_sync_h {
    bit<8> count;
    bit<48> t0;
    bit<48> t1;
    bit<48> t2;
    bit<48> t3;
}
```

FIGURE 53 P4 DEFINITION OF THE CLOCK_SYNC HEADER

By repeating this clock_sync process every couple of seconds the INT collector can calculate to a sufficient accuracy the variance between the clocks of the UE and the Tofino, and by calculating this difference the INT collector can make sense of the absolute timestamps recorded in the D6G-INT header (Figure 52). And can normalize the values before sending them to the MAS Telemetry agent for the verification of QoS and SLA parameters.

4.5.6.2 Telemetry Agent, MAS and RAN xAPP functionalities

An xApp has been developed to perform two primary functions:

- i) monitoring various performance metrics generated by the RAN stack and publishing them in a Kafka bus, and
- ii) exposing a RESTful API that enables external systems to initiate a handover procedure for a selected UE.

The xApp exposes the following endpoint:

- **/handover**: Triggers the handover of UE connected to the RAN

The same MAS deployment as the one described in Section 4.5.4.2 is considered in this workflow. The Telemetry Agent receives the delay metrics from the packet network while the Multi-Flow Agent receive the delay metrics from the RAN by subscribing to a Kafka bus. The Multi-Flow Agent aggregates metrics from multiple sources to detect and evaluate any changes within the network. Specifically, it monitors delay variations across both the radio and packet segments to identify the root cause of service degradation. In case of detecting an anomaly on the packet network segment, it can issue a reconfiguration petition to the SDN controller to increase the bandwidth capacity. On the other hand, if the anomaly is detected on the radio segment, the agent issues a request to the RIC to handover the UE to another location where the QoS requirements can be ensured.

4.6 Test and results

In this section we report the main test executions related to each workflow. Results are reported inside each test execution table, including plots related to bulk executions of tests to retrieve significant statistics.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-Wo	Workflow o (Steady State) Main Test	1	CNIT, SSSA
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	AR App, UE-INT+INC, Telemetry Collector, NFR, UE2SM, CU-UP, RAN Telemetry	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the performance of the network and of the AR app in steady state conditions, with all the DESIRE6G data plane already deployed.		
Test requirements	The tests require the presence of the drone human operator checking the correct operation in real time. All the devices need to be configured and activated manually. AR application is pre-deployed in the drone and in the edge node. RAN is operating. VXLAN tunnels are established to allow end-to-end communication between the drone UE and the RAN, the RAN and the Tofino instances and the SDN network. The Kubernetes Cluster is active and runs one pod instance of the edge app and a pre-deployed BMv2 switch to allow communication from the Tofino to the app.		
External tools	Drone Controller (manual, VICON).		
Measurement	Network throughput and latency, APP throughput and latency, drone flying mission metrics.		
Related Project KPIs	KPI AR/VR 1-4, KPI 7.4		

Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	The network, the drone and the Headset are booted and active. The RAN is configured, The VXLAN tunnels are configured.
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Deploy and configure all the data plane network functions in Site 1 and Site 2 (UE2SM, NFR, INT+INC) 2- Activate the UE at the drone 3- Activate the source app, the edge app 4- Send iperf3 probes from the drone to the RAN Core Network to test the RAN performance 5- Send AR app video and commands from the drone to the edge app 6- Activate a drone flying mission with the AR app fully operating

Test results

FIGURE 54 RAN PERFORMANCE

The plot shows the uplink (TX-C) and downlink (RX-C) throughput over a 30-second iperf3 test on UDP traffic, along with jitter and packet loss rate measured at the UE side. Downlink (DL) throughput remains quite stable around 95–100 Mbit/s, indicating consistent RAN downlink capacity and good scheduling performance. Occasional dips (e.g., around 17 s → ~74 Mbit/s) correspond to temporary loss bursts or radio scheduling interruptions. Uplink (UL) throughput fluctuates between 35 Mbit/s and 65 Mbit/s,

averaging roughly 50 Mbit/s. The average jitter ≈ 0.13 ms, is extremely low – excellent for real-time or low-latency services. Downlink packet loss averages around 4–5 %, with spikes up to 25 % (notably at 17 s), due to RLC retransmission switch off using UM mode. After the spike, the link recovers quickly, showing good link adaptation and error correction efficiency.

End-to-end results with iperf3, all D6G data plane active

FIGURE 55 END-TO-END RTT IN THE DESIRE6G SITES – DATA PLANE DEPLOYED

The graph in Figure 55 represents the latency behaviour of the end-to-end communication path measured between the drone and the edge node when all the DESIRE6G data plane is configured and active. It shows how Round-Trip Times (RTTs) are distributed within the 10–50 ms range – the region where most latency samples occur.

The histogram (bars) captures the frequency of RTT occurrences. The main RTT occurrences lie between 15 ms and 25 ms. The narrow distribution and low jitter imply that both the wireless link, SDN and the edge compute chain are well-optimized (e.g., short MAC scheduling window, low buffer queuing). Occasional longer RTTs up to ~40 ms correspond to transient medium congestion, PHY retransmissions, mainly at the RAN side. Typical RTTs under 30 ms meet requirements for tactile Internet, remote piloting, or edge-assisted XR. The small right tail (35–45 ms) suggests rare but detectable delay spikes – worth monitoring when ultra-low latency (< 20 ms) consistency is a hard constraint.

AR App performance

Figure 56 shows the main performance of the AR app when launched. Two video versions have been considered: a) motion JPEG 1280x768 resolution and b) h264 1280x720. In version a) the throughput is 20Mb/s uplink, in version b) the throughput is variable between 5 and 12 Mbit/s. The video shows the performance of the motion JPEG version. In all the cases, the one-way latency of the end-to-end path, from the drone to the edge app, is 9-11 ms. The RAN latency accounts for 8-9 ms, including the wireless link. The SDN and cluster accounts for 1-2 ms. The Tofino latency is negligible (around 4us), thus the contribution is given by the BMv2 switches and the data plane path of the Kubernetes cluster.

FIGURE 56 APP PERFORMANCE

Drone Flying mission

In this step the Drone controller enforces the flying mission. The drone start flying following the trajectory imposed by the MAVLink system and continuously monitored by the VIACON system. The AR app fully operates with bidirectional transmission of video, artifacts and commands. Figure 57 shows the parallel video recordings obtained during the flying mission. The top-left video is the output of the s-App running in the Jetson payload of the drone, implementing object detection. The artifacts show a person identification with the accuracy level. The bottom-left video is the output of the e-App running in the

Kubernetes cluster. The video received by s-App is enriched with the pose artifacts of the person. The output of this function is sent to the Quest 3. The Quest 3 Unity engine performs the 3D reconstruction and localization of the detected object and draws the red skeleton of the person in the environment. This way, AR artifacts are added to the bypass camera video of the Quest. The result is the detection of a moving person behind the obstacle. Videos are transmitted and received with a >30 frames per seconds. The latency of the AR app stages is around 8 ms. The total end-to-end one-way latency, including the app, is around 26ms, a value that allows live interaction. The main latency bottlenecks are the AI processing at each AR app stage and the RAN latency.

FIGURE 57 AR APP ARTIFACTS AT THE DRONE, AT THE EDGE AND AT THE QUEST3 HEADSET

The drone flying mission detailed results and metrics are reported in the plots of Figure 58. Figures show the path inside the laboratory that the drone is tasked to follow. More in detail, Figure 58 a) shows the drone 3D trajectory, while Figure 58.b) shows velocity and position vectors components, which presented very few fluctuations during flight, indicating steadiness and control. Figure 58.c) also represents velocity vectors over laboratory's X and Y coordinates and Figure 58.d) shows the battery status during tests, which also presented no issue or fluctuation.

FIGURE 58: A) DRONE TRAJECTORY B) DRONE LOCALIZATION, C) DRONE VELOCITY VECTORS, D) DRONE BATTERY STATUS

Test outcome comments

The RAN test shows stable DL throughput around 95–100 Mbit/s, with brief dips linked to short scheduling or fading events. UL throughput varies between 35–65 Mbit/s, averaging ~50 Mbit/s, while jitter stays extremely low (~0.13 ms). DL packet loss is generally 4–5%, with occasional spikes up to 25% that recover quickly. End-to-end RTTs with the full DESIRE6G data plane fall mostly in the 15–25 ms range, with a tight distribution and rare peaks up to 40–45 ms caused by transient RAN-side congestion. Typical RTTs <30 ms meet XR/remote-control requirements. The network maintains 9–11 ms one-way latency regardless of encoding; Motion JPEG needs ~20 Mbit/s UL, while H.264 uses 5–12 Mbit/s. RAN contributes 8–9 ms of this delay, SDN+cluster 1–2 ms, with negligible Tofino latency. Drone telemetry (localization, trajectory, velocity, battery) confirms stable flight and consistent data delivery. The total e2e latency including the app stages is around 26ms.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-W1	Workflow 1 Main Test (Service Deployment)	2	CNIT, SSSA; NUBIS, UVA, ELTE, ERI-HU
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	SO, OE, Service Catalog, IML LNFVO, NFR, UE2SM, UE INT+INC	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Validate the full service deployment of the AR app in the ARNO testbed spanning three sites. Measure the overall deployment time and the time contribution of each component and module.		
Test requirements	The SMO and all components need to be deployed and fully working. Drone, RAN, SDN, Tofino switch and cluster need to be connected and configured (interfaces) to support e2e flowing.		
External tools	No external tools are used.		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SMO processing time - OE and SC processing time - IML/LNFVO processing time at each site - Deployment time contributions due to SMO, IML and K8S - Deployment time of FaaS e-App 		
Related Project KPIs	KPI 7.2, KPI7.3, KPI 7.4		
Test execution			

Initial setup/assumptions	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Deploy and activate all the SMO and IML subsystems in the sites to run in steady state. 1. Check that the AR traffic is not flowing and services are not instantiated. 3. Start the workflow by sending the service deployment request from the tenant with the required service graph and the E2E latency requirement 4. Check the SC and the OE reply with the available service images and the service decomposition NSDs for each site 5. Check the SO sends the NSDs 6. Check the IML LNFVOs receive the NSD and parse the request 7. Check the IML LNFVO instantiate application pods and NFs 8. Check the IML LNFVO configure the NFs CP 9. Check the IML LNFVO returns the deployment outcome at each site 10. Check the SO receives the ack message from all the IMLs 11. Check the e2e traffic is flowing 12. Measure all the time contributions at SMO and IML.
Test results	
<p>The experimental results provide a breakdown of the execution time contributions across SMO and Non-SMO components. The measurements shown in Figure 59, taken at the SMO level, are divided into the service request and composition steps at the SMO (red bars) and the SO calls to the IML in the different sites. The figure shows that all SMO-related operations, including SO, SC, and OE, consistently operate within the millisecond range. Specifically, SMO processing never exceeds a few tens of milliseconds, confirming that control and management functions introduce negligible latency in the end-to-end workflow. In particular, as shown in Figure 60, the service catalogue retrieval takes around 5ms. The decomposition request and reply, including communication, between the SO and the OE takes 27ms. The net OE processing outcome is around 13ms. The OE outcome is processed by the SO to compose the NSD YAML files (13 ms) and to retrieve the IML endpoints (9ms). The total contribution of the SMO is around 54ms. The figure shows the time seen by the SMO when calling the IML instances and receiving the reply. These contributions are not inclusive of the time spent by K8S to enforce the deployment of software pods. The figure shows the time spent in Site 1 that includes the enforcement of the Tofino instance and the flow rules (around 122ms). Thus, from the SMO point of view, the entire control plane operation (without K8S) operation is concluded after around 175ms.</p>	

FIGURE 59 DEPLOYMENT: SMO AND NON-SMO PROCESSING TIMES

FIGURE 60 DEPLOYMENT: SERVICE DECOMPOSITION TIME CONTRIBUTIONS

FIGURE 61 DEPLOYMENT: IML TIME CONTRIBUTIONS INCLUDING K8S IN SITE 2

From the IML perspective, Figure 61 shows the time contributions measured by the IML LNFVO API in Site 2, the most complex one. When receiving the NSD, the IML performs its computation in less than 500µs, then it prepares the pod instance configurations in 25ms., invoking the K8s API calls. Actual pod instantiations are run in parallel and take some seconds for 4 pods (e-App1 in orin3, e-App2 in orin4, NFR and edge monitoring engine used to run Workflow 4). At the end of deployment, control plane rules are

computed and sent to NFR and monitoring engine in less than 1.5s. The total IML deployment time takes around 16 seconds.

Test outcome comments

The obtained results confirm that the SMO/IML architecture meets the targeted automation, decision-making, and resilience KPIs. Service creation and deployment triggering were executed fully autonomously, with no manual intervention required. This directly validates KPI7.2. The measured execution times of SMO components (SO, SC, and OE) consistently remain in the millisecond range, with OE-based AI-driven optimization and re-optimization phases well below the 100 ms threshold. This confirms compliance with KPI7.3. Notably, the end-to-end SMO control-plane latency remains negligible compared to execution-layer delays, ensuring timely reactions under varying traffic and service conditions. Regarding KPI7.4, results show that FaaS placement and redundancy are computed within sub-second timescales, if K8S-based deployment phase is not considered.

The IML LNVFO exhibits low computation and calling times, in the order of tens of milliseconds. Control plane commands depend on the considered NFV backend. For Tofino, around 100 ms are required, while for software-based NFV more time is needed (around 1 s). The overall deployment time is dominated by the K8S API calls and actual pod deployment phase, requiring some seconds depending on the pod image type.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-W2	Workflow 2 Main Test (MAS agent Runtime Verification)	3	CNIT, SSSA, UPC, TSS
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	MAS Agents, D-MUTRA Sidecar & DLT Verifier, SECaaS/Blockchain Connector	Continuous attestation of MAS agents during runtime

Description of the test

Main function	Validate the mutual remote attestation of distributed MAS agents ensuring runtime code integrity and trust establishment through D-MUTRA blockchain-based signatures.
Test requirements	Agents wrapped via SECaaS; DLT access enabled; verifier nodes reachable.
External tools	-
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Duration of attestation (from request to verification result) - Duration overhead of the agent over attestation process.
Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Performance overhead - Attestation cycle duration
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<p>All MAS containers deployed with sidecar; reference signatures anchored on SECaaS database; verifier registered in DLT nodes.</p> <p>Setup</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prover Agents: Two agents, <i>multiflow</i> and <i>telemetry</i>. Each extracts the .text section of its binary, computes a SHA-256 hash, and submits this measurement to the blockchain as attestation evidence. • SECaaS Verifier • Sidecars and Metrics Collection: Each agent is paired with an attestation sidecar. • Sidecars record all timing probes locally and push them to Redis, while a per-instance exporter periodically ships aggregated metrics to a centralized Prometheus instance via Pushgateway. • Blockchain Configuration: The experiment uses a 10-node Besu Proof-of-Authority (PoA) network to guarantee low-latency, deterministic block finality.

Steps
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initialize the Blockchain Network Deploy the Besu PoA network and instantiate the attestation smart contract that manages evidence submission and verifier election. 2. Register Agents and Generate References Each agent is registered through the SECaaS wrapper, which computes its reference signature and stores it in the off-chain database. 3. Launch Agents and Sidecars Prover agents and their associated sidecars are started. Attestation cycles are executed automatically and continuously in background. 4. Collect Metrics Over 100 Attestation Cycles Timing probes and resource usage metrics are exported to Prometheus. After completing 100 cycles, metrics are extracted as CSV files using <code>export_prometheus_to_csv.py</code>. 5. Analyse Per-Instance Behaviour The exported data is analysed to compare performance.

Test results

The following table (Table 11) details the obtained measurement values.

TABLE 11 WORKFLOW 2 RESULTS

Category	Metric	Value	Explanation
Attestation Cycle	End-to-End Attestation Time	4.0613 s	Total time from measurement to final verdict;
	Measurement Time	0.001110 s	Very fast hashing of the code section performed locally.
	DLT Commit Time	0.0078 s	Time for the blockchain to accept and anchor the measurement.
	Verification Time	0.0025 s	Time for the verifier to recompute and validate the measurement.
System Overhead	Agent CPU Usage	0.01 %	Negligible CPU cost for the protected agent.

	Sidecar CPU Usage	6.73 %	Overhead from hashing, network calls, and attestation protocol.
agent : multi-flow.bin			
Category	Metric	Value	Explanation
Attestation Cycle	End-to-End Attestation Time	4.0886 s	Total time from measurement to final verdict;
	Measurement Time	0.001106 s	Very fast hashing of the code section performed locally.
	DLT Commit Time	0.0125 s	Time for the blockchain to accept and anchor the measurement.
	Verification Time	0.0020 s	Time for the verifier to recompute and validate the measurement.
System Overhead	Agent CPU Usage	0.00 %	Negligible CPU cost for the protected agent.
	Sidecar CPU Usage	8.94 %	Overhead from hashing, network calls, and attestation protocol.
agent : telemetry.bin			

Test outcome comments

- The experiment **successfully validates zero-touch runtime attestation** of MAS agents using D-MUTRA sidecars.
- Both tested agents (*multiflow-agent1* and *telemetry-agent2*) exhibited **correct and consistent verification results**.
- Runtime overhead on agents is **negligible (0.0–0.01% CPU)**, while the sidecar contributes **6–9% CPU usage**, depending on workload activity cgroup limit.
- Measurement overhead is extremely low (≈ 1 ms), confirming the efficiency of hashing and local verification.
- **End-to-end attestation time ≈ 4 s** in our setup, driven mainly by network latency and asynchronous DLT propagation.

- This confirms that startup-onboarding attestation (SoA) would have introduced unacceptable delays.
Instead, the **“Attest After Starting”** mechanism eliminates startup latency and enables MAS agents to operate instantly.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-W3	Workflow 3 Main Test (In-band control-MAS Service Assurance)	4	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA, UPC
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	INT-UE+INC, Telemetry Collector (DPAC), MAS Agent	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Validate the in-band control functionality at the programmable data plane. Validate the subsequent MAS re-optimization. Validate the double layer service assurance approach.		
Test requirements	AR app is flowing with INT+INC functionalities. INT Reports are generated only for the considered flow from the sink node to the Telemetry Collector and aggregated to the Telemetry Agent.		
External tools	Spirent Traffic Generator generating traffic spikes.		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In-band control reaction and data plane recovery - INT telemetry processing duration - MAS control loop duration 		
Related Project KPIs	KPI 7.2, KPI 7.3		
Test execution			

Initial setup/assumptions	A service has been already created; traffic flows through the Packet Network; the MAS is deployed.
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Activate all the subsystems to run in steady state. 1. Check that the traffic is flowing from source to destination and steady state parameters at collector and MAS with standard latency values 2. Activate Spirent spike traffic affecting N1-N2 link. 3. Check and measure the congestion impact in terms of latency and queue length at the involved nodes 4. Check the INC reaction. It should react with an immediate reroute of traffic in the data plane. 5. Measure the time to inform the N1 about the anomaly with INC message 6. Measure the time needed by the MAS to perform the re-optimization suggestion 7. Measure the re-optimization enforcement time 8. Check that e2e latency is recovered 9. Evaluate the overall recovery time (INC + MAS + enforcement)

Test results

INC reaction and assurance

FIGURE 62 INC RESULTS: THROUGHPUT DUE TO CONGESTION

Figure 62 shows the throughput of the AR flows detected at node N4 with (left plot) and without (right plot) the in-band control functionality. The two charts in Figure 62 show the change in throughput of two flows over the experiment time, the first one is plotted in blue colour which represents the monitored flow that must meet the low-latency requirements, while the second flow is plotted in orange colour and represents a non time-sensitive flow that is served on best-effort basis.

FIGURE 63 SDN TOPOLOGY

Figure 63 shows the topology used in the test, where there is one main path (in blue) and one backup path (in green) at the beginning each of the two flows mentioned in Figure 62 takes the main path (blue). Then at the 30th second of the experiment time a heavy background burst is inserted at switch number 2 causing a congestion saturating the output queues of its interface towards N4. The experiment is repeated in two iterations, using two different In-band Telemetry frameworks, one framework for each iteration. The effects on the throughput are compared between the two iterations starting with In-band control (Figure 62 left) with complete degradation of the throughput of the low-priority flow (in orange) while the monitored (blue) flow is virtually unaffected. And the second iteration with the In-band Telemetry report being batch processed by the SDN controller (Figure 62 right) resulting in longer reconfiguration times on the order of 100s of milliseconds for the monitored flow (blue) to be sent on the backup path, while the low-priority flow (orange) is not reconfigured.

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol
1 0.00000000	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
2 0.000581627	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
3 0.000905135	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
4 0.001470817	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
5 0.006427700	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
6 0.006857274	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
7 0.007067128	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
8 0.007512695	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
9 0.008866481	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
10 0.009274830	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
11 0.011685122	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
12 0.012062401	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
13 0.014509292	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
14 0.014888520	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
15 0.017075873	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
16 0.017480101	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
17 0.019900604	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
18 0.020202465	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC
19 0.022494229	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INT
20 0.022856332	00:00:00 00:00:01	00:00:00 00:00:04	SDN_INC

INC reaction: 0.58ms
Queue empty time: 22 ms

```

Frame 1: 1474 bytes on wire (11792 bits), 1474 bytes captured (11792 bit)
on Ethernet II, Src: 00:00:00 00:00:01 (00:00:00:00:00:01), Dst: 00:00:00 00:00:04
SDN_INT Header
  SDN Label: 0x0065
  Original EtherType: 0x0800
  SDN Latency: 6302
    
```

```

Frame 2: 1468 bytes on wire (11744 bits), 1468 bytes captured (11744 bits) on
Ethernet II, Src: 00:00:00 00:00:01 (00:00:00:00:00:01), Dst: 00:00:00 00:00:04
SDN_INC Header
  SDN INC Label: 0x03e9
  New Output Port: 3
    
```

FIGURE 64 INC RESULTS: INC REACTION AND QUEUE EMPTYING OPERATION

Figure 64 shows packet 1 carrying out a cumulated SDN hop latency of 6302us. The threshold mechanism at the DPAC triggers the generation of packet 2 after 0.58ms. In the meanwhile, node N4 continues to receive packets that have been in the queue of N1. The queue empties after 22ms. In order to measure the rapidity of the recovery (the time elapsing from the generation of the INC message at N4 and the rerouting at node N1),

Figure 65 shows the Wireshark capture of node N4 combining different interfaces. The first INC message is generated 1,47ms before the reception of recovered packets at the interface of the backup path (N3-N4) (i.e., packets in red). Thus, the full recovery time, including the generation of INC message, the transmission to N1 and the steering at N1 takes less than 1,50ms. Note that operation is performed with software switches. In the case of hardware switches the recovery would have taken tens of microseconds.

Figure 65 shows packet captures with timestamps centred around the moment of the reroute (timestamp 0) at different interfaces in the network. The packets in white represent the packets of the monitored flow going over the main path with violations of latency, we can see that the first packet that carries a violation arrives at the N4 at moment -0.00178s. this packet carries the latency violation that is detected by N4 acting as a Data-Plane Active-Collector (DPAC) which sends back its In-band Control message SDN_INC (highlighted in light blue colour at timestamp -0.00147s) to the ingress node (N1). Upon the reception of the SDN_INC, switch 1 reconfigure the monitored flow to go over the backup path. We can see the packets of the monitored flow appear on the backup path which are highlighted in orange. The time taken from the detection of the violation to the traffic appearing on the backup path takes a total of around 1.78ms.

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol
174	-0.001784480	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INT
175	-0.001567896	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INT
176	-0.001470084	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
177	-0.001251432	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
272	-0.001060293	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
178	-0.001039283	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
273	-0.000968305	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
274	-0.000842913	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INC
1	0.000000000	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INT
2	0.000637267	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:04	SDN_INT

FIGURE 65 INC RESULTS: RECOVERY TIME

MAS assurance

The Processing time of INT measurements received at the Telemetry Agent is ≈ 2 ms.

```
13:02:51.138 Processing INT measurement: {'flow_id': '10', 'paths': {'p1': {'delay': {'max': 5.3, 'min': 4.0, 'avg': 10000000000.0}, 'jitter': {'max': 1.1, 'min': 0.2, 'avg': 0.8}}, 'p2': {'delay': {'max': 10.2, 'min': 2.0, 'avg': 7.5}, 'jitter': {'max': 2.1, 'min': 0.3, 'avg': 1.1}}}, 'init_time': 1763470971.138865}
13:02:51.139 Elapsed time for processing INT measurement: 1.9690990447998047 milliseconds
13:02:51.139 Sending processed measurement to Multi-Flow Agent
```

FIGURE 66 MAS AGENT INT PROCESSING LOGGING

The MAS reaction time including the delay added for the MAS communication is ≈ 20 ms.

```
13:02:51.151 Received QoS measurement: {'flow_id': '10', 'paths': {'p1': {'delay': {'max': 5.3, 'min': 4.0, 'avg': 10000000000.0}, 'jitter': {'max': 1.1, 'min': 0.2, 'avg': 0.8}}, 'p2': {'delay': {'max': 10.2, 'min': 2.0, 'avg': 7.5}, 'jitter': {'max': 2.1, 'min': 0.3, 'avg': 1.1}}}, 'init_time': 1763470971.1375415}
13:02:51.154 QoS measurement processed
13:02:51.155 Setting new policy: {'flow_id': '10', 'policy': {'p1': 0, 'p2': 0, 'p3': 100}}
```

FIGURE 67 MAS AGENT REROUTING CONFIGURATION LOGGING

Test outcome comments

From the obtained results the double assurance mechanism is validated. The INC mechanism is able to intervene at the millisecond time granularity using software switches (the assurance is even faster if hardware switches are employed). Latency due to congestion may anyway produce trains of packets that are delayed. In this experiment we notice a train of packets delayed due to the N1 internal queue storage with duration around 20ms. This can be avoided by employing temporary high priority queues. Moreover, the INC recovery may not be optimal since it performs the complete flow re-direction over a pre-planned backup path. The MAS intervention is in the order of tens of milliseconds (around 20ms) and is able to restore the flows in an optimal way to guarantee the e2e latency. The two assurance mechanisms do not interfere each other due to the different time trigger granularity.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-W4	Workflow 4 Main Test (IML-driven Service Assurance)	5	CNIT, SSSA, ELTE, ERI-HU
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	Kafka Monitoring, IML LNFVO, NFR	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Validate the pervasive service monitoring using Kafka-based IT metrics of the FaaS pod. Validate the forecast engine prediction of future resource exhaustion at the service pod. Validate the IML/LVNFO scaling re-optimization at single site.		
Test requirements	FaaS AR app is deployed and flowing end-to-end. Kafka monitoring is activated on the e-App pod running in the ORIN board in the K8s cluster.		
External tools	No external tools are used.		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forecast Engine prediction measurements - API generation time from the - IML/LNFVO alarm reception and processing time 		

	- IML-driven Enforcement time
Related Project KPIs	KPI 7.2, KPI7.3, KPI 7.4
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	The service has been deployed and configured. Infrastructure monitoring has been activated by IML.
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Activate all the subsystems to run in steady state (deployed service, deployed monitoring, deployed network functions). 1. Check that the traffic is flowing from s-App to e-App. 2. Activate the extra CPU processing in the e-App pod at orin3 board. 3. Check pod CPU metrics are collected by Kafka monitoring 4. Check periodic CPU occupancy prediction is computed by the Forecast Engine – measure the forecast inference time. 5. Check the Alarm sent to the IML when predicted CPU load is greater than a defined threshold. 6. Check the IML computed and enforces the scaling. 7. Measure the scaling processing and enforcement time. 8. Check traffic is flowing to the new E-app pod.
Test results	
<p>The screenshot displays two terminal windows. The left window shows a continuous stream of network traffic logs, such as '4 bytes from 10.30.7.213: icmp_seq=7886 ttl=63 time=24.9 ms'. The right window shows monitoring logs from the IML engine, including CPU and RAM metrics for pods, a scaling API response indicating a change in instance count, and Kafka messages being delivered to various pods.</p>	
<p>FIGURE 68 WORKFLOW 4 EXPERIMENT SCREENSHOT</p> <p>Figure 68 shows the execution of the experiment through terminals. On the left side, the terminal displays the application traffic at the pod level, while on the right side the terminals correspond to the monitoring and intelligence engines, including metric collection, forecasting, and control actions.</p>	

The monitoring engines continuously receive metric samples from the working pod, including CPU utilization, RAM usage, and number of active clients. These samples are collected at a **1-second** granularity. **Every 6 seconds**, the collected metrics are aggregated and fed to the Forecast Engine, which generates a new prediction sample representing the anticipated system behaviour under the current load conditions. The monitoring platform evaluates both raw metrics and forecasted values. When the predicted behavior indicates a potential service degradation, an alarm message is generated and propagated to the IML. This alarm represents a semantic trigger, as it is not based solely on instantaneous threshold violations, but on predicted trends that may compromise service performance. Upon alarm reception, the IML computes a scaling decision and enforces it through the control plane. In the experiment, the scaling action consists of installing a flow rule at the Network Function Router (NFR), steering the application traffic towards an alternative pod deployed on the Jetson Orin4 board, which is not affected by the high CPU load observed on the original instance. The successful enforcement of this action is confirmed by the Scaling API response, reported as “Current instance changed to 1”.

The end-to-end scaling time, measured as the interval between sending the Alarm POST message and receiving the final Scaling API response (“Current instance changed to 1”), is **215 ms**. This duration includes: 1) Alarm reception and interpretation by the IML, 2) Computation of the scaling decision, 3) Enforcement of the control action via flow rule installation.

The inference latency of the Forecast Engine was analyzed in detail (see distribution in Figure 69), by isolating the execution times corresponding exclusively to inference operations at the GPU, excluding data ingestion and scaling procedures. The results show a highly stable and deterministic behavior, characterized by median inference latency of **44 ms** and standard deviation below 1.5 ms. This narrow distribution demonstrates that the Forecast Engine can operate reliably in real-time Service Assurance loops, without introducing significant computational overhead or timing jitter. Such stability is important in edge environments, where control decisions must be taken within tight latency constraints.

FIGURE 69 FORECAST ENGINE INFERENCE TIME DISTRIBUTION

Test outcome comments

The monitoring platform reliably collected FaaS service metrics (CPU, RAM, and number of clients) at a 1-second granularity and correctly delivered them to the Forecast Engine. Prediction samples were generated at the expected 6-second interval, confirming the proper synchronization between metric ingestion and forecasting components. The Forecast Engine demonstrated stable and deterministic inference performance (median value of 44 ms) and a standard deviation below 1.5 ms. This confirms that the forecasting process introduces negligible overhead and is suitable for real-time and continuous Service Assurance operations at the edge.

When predicted conditions indicated an imminent overload, the monitoring system correctly generated an alarm and forwarded it to the IML. The IML successfully computed and enforced a scaling decision, steering traffic to an alternative FaaS instance not affected by the high CPU load. The complete scaling reaction time, measured from alarm emission to confirmation of scaling enforcement, was 215 ms, demonstrating fast and effective closed-loop control. The observed reaction time confirms that the closed-loop control chain—from monitoring to prediction, decision, and enforcement—operates within sub-second timescales, making it suitable for proactive and predictive service assurance scenarios.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D1-W5	Workflow 5 Main Test (MAS-driven Service Assurance)	6	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA; UPC, ACC
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO	Demo 1	INT-UE+INC, Telemetry Collector,	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the capability of the pervasive telemetry + the MAS Agents to react promptly to different latency anomalies induced in the network. In this test the anomalies are congestion events occurring at one of the P4 switches (with no INC functionality) and at the RAN using the P4 Delay Tuner. Measure the times of the components and the full loop reaction time		
Test requirements	AR app is flowing with INT functionalities. INT Reports are generated only for the considered flow from the sink node to the Telemetry Collector and aggregated to the Telemetry Agent.		
External tools	Spirent Traffic Generator generating traffic congestion at the SDN domain (as in W3), InfluxdB and Grafana at the Collector to visualize time series.		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MAS packet network anomaly detection time - MAS reaction time on network anomaly detection - MAS RAN anomaly detection time - MAS reaction time on RAN anomaly detection 		
Related Project KPIs	KPI 7.2, KPI 7.3		
Test execution			
Initial setup/assumptions	AR service has been already deployed; traffic flows through the end-to-end path; traffic flows through the radio segment; the MAS is deployed, the xApp is running, the Telemetry Collector is already configured to process AR traffic flows.		

Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Activate all the subsystems to run in steady state. 1. Check that the traffic is flowing from source to destination and steady state parameters at collector and MAS 2. For SDN failure: Activate Spirent traffic (with significant issues on congestion/latency). For RAN failure: Activate the Delay Tuner 3. Check and measure the congestion impact in terms of latency and queue length at the involved nodes 4. Check the MAS reaction (it should react with a suggested change) 5. Measure the time to inform the MAS about the anomaly 6. Measure the time needed by the MAS to perform the re-optimization suggestion 7. Measure the re-optimization enforcement time 8. Check that e2e latency is recovered 9. Evaluate the overall recovery time (collector+MAS+enforcement)
--------------	---

Test results

MAS agent processing

- The MAS packet network anomaly detection time is < 10 ms
- The MAS reaction time including the delay added for the MAS communication on packet network anomaly detection is ≈ 25 ms

```

13:04:29.001 Received QoS measurement: {'flow_id': '10', 'paths': {'p1': {'delay': {'max': 5.3, 'min': 4.0, 'avg': 1.000000000000.0}, 'jitter': {'max': 1.1, 'min': 0.2, 'avg': 0.8}}, 'p2': {'delay': {'max': 10.2, 'min': 2.0, 'avg': 7.5}, 'jitter': {'max': 2.1, 'min': 0.3, 'avg': 1.1}}}, 'init_time': 1763471068.9889543}
13:04:29.004 QoS measurement processed
13:04:29.013 Anomaly detected, setting capacity for flow 10
13:04:29.013 Setting new capacity: {'flow_id': '10', 'bandwith_Gb/s': 10}
    
```

FIGURE 70 MAS AGENT PACKET NETWORK ANOMALY PROCEDURE

- The MAS RAN anomaly detection time is < 10 ms
- The MAS reaction time including the delay added for the MAS communication on RAN anomaly detection is ≈ 25 ms

```

13:06:28.319 Received QoS measurement: {'flow_id': '10', 'paths': {'p1': {'delay': {'max': 5.3, 'min': 4.0, 'avg': 1.000000000000.0}, 'jitter': {'max': 1.1, 'min': 0.2, 'avg': 0.8}}, 'p2': {'delay': {'max': 10.2, 'min': 2.0, 'avg': 7.5}, 'jitter': {'max': 2.1, 'min': 0.3, 'avg': 1.1}}}, 'init_time': 1763471188.308243}
13:06:28.322 QoS measurement processed
13:06:28.329 Anomaly detected, sending petition to handover the UE
    
```

FIGURE 71 MAS AGENT RAN ANOMALY PROCEDURE

INT collector and SDN results

- D6G INT Collection and aggregation of 4 packets:

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol
2	1.659390439	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:02	D6G_INT
3	1.662103903	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:02	D6G_INT
4	1.663389321	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:02	D6G_INT
5	1.664780988	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:02	D6G_INT
6	1.665062689	00:00:00_00:00:01	00:00:00_00:00:02	D6G_INT REPORT


```

Frame 6: 64 bytes on wire (512 bits), 64 bytes captured (512 bits) on interface
Ethernet II, Src: 00:00:00_00:00:01 (00:00:00:00:00:01), Dst: 00:00:00_00:00:02
D6G_MAIN Header
D6G_INT Report
  RAN Latency: 7579
  SDN Latency: 282
    
```

FIGURE 72 WIRESHARK CAPTURE OF COLLECTOR INTERFACES

FIGURE 73 A GROUP OF 4 INT PACKETS AND P4 COLLECTOR SUMMARY

- Time taken to send collector report ~220us
- INT server time to process and send aggregated and summarized reports to MAS ~ 10ms
- Time for reconfiguration of P4 switch is < 1ms

Overall loop

Figure 74 summarizes the timings at each configuration step for reconfiguring P4 switches to go on the backup path.

FIGURE 74 CLOSED LOOP INDIVIDUAL TIMES IN MS FOR P4 RECONFIG

Figure 75 shows the Grafana time series of the latency values of AR App packets in the RAN segment during the tests. In steady state the latency is around 10ms with some spikes due to the RAN. When the Delay Tuner is configured, latency increases up to around 90ms. When the complete loop is executed and the Handover is forced, latency is restored to the nominal value. The shown recovery time (around 8s) is mainly due to the time needed by the RIC to force the Handover from DU1 to DU2. The time needed by the DESIRE6G data plane and the MAS to perform the Handover request is below 100ms. Thus, the remaining time is due to the xAPP command and by the RIC internal commands to enforce Handover, requiring synchronization with the UE.

FIGURE 75 INT VALUES AT THE TELEMETRY COLLECTOR (RAN SEGMENT)

Test outcome comments

The results obtained confirm that the MAS agents achieve very low anomaly detection times (<10 ms) for both packet-network and RAN-level anomalies, demonstrating their suitability for near real-time

feedback loops in 6G-aligned architectures. The end-to-end MAS reaction time (~25 ms), including communication overhead, remains well below the 100 ms envelope typically required for near-real-time control, validating the efficiency of the MAS-to-data-plane signaling path. The INT measurements further support this by highlighting precise, segment-level latency traces that can be exploited for adaptive control. The overall loop analysis shows that while the MAS + data-plane handover trigger completes within ~100 ms (i.e., below 50ms), the dominant contributor to total recovery time (~8 s) lies in the RIC/xAPP execution and UE synchronization. This separation clearly highlights the difference between system-internal overheads and control-plane orchestration delays. Grafana time-series results demonstrate that the AR application maintains a stable 10 ms RAN latency, increasing only when the Delay Tuner is intentionally activated, and returning to nominal values after the forced handover. These findings collectively show that the DESIRE6G data plane and MAS operate within stringent real-time constraints, and that remaining optimization opportunities lie primarily in RIC/xAPP orchestration latency.

5 Demo 2: Real-Time Digital Twin

5.1 Introduction, testbed and components

This demonstrator showcases the integrated 6G-ready DESIRE6G architecture, designed to enable automated and secure orchestration, and efficient traffic management for low-latency applications such as Digital Twins (DTs) for robotics and autonomous systems. The demo validates a cloud-native, multi-domain framework that integrates programmable and deterministic data planes, IML-driven service assurance, and an intent-based orchestration layer supported by zero-trust, dynamic federation mechanisms. Together, these capabilities enable closed-loop control and decision-making across the edge-cloud continuum, while supporting interoperability with other 6G frameworks operated by independent administrative domains. The architecture implements a distributed control model spanning three independently operated domains, each with heterogeneous infrastructure. This model enables the dynamic deployment, reconfiguration, and federation of network and application services in response to changing operational conditions, ensuring continuous optimization and compliance with strict latency requirements.

The demonstrator is deployed on the 5TONIC testbed in Madrid, Spain, and integrates a DT application distributed across heterogeneous equipment, including a quadruped robot, edge nodes, programmable and TSN switches, and intelligent orchestrators spanning multiple infrastructure domains. The showcased use case represents a robotics DT system, where robots perform autonomous, real-time operations in industrial environments. The system architecture distributes robot functions across the device, edge, and cloud layers to effectively manage balance computational load, latency, and bandwidth demands. Through programmable traffic management and cross-domain federation at the orchestration layer, the system maintains strict end-to-end latency guarantees, even under network or resource degradation. The results demonstrate the seamless integration of cloud-native orchestration and programmable data-plane control, embodying the DESIRE6G vision of resilient, autonomous, and performance-aware 6G infrastructures.

5.1.1 Demo deployment

The demonstrator has been fully implemented and deployed within the 5TONIC integrated testbed (shown in Figure 76Figure 76). The testbed includes three interconnected administrative domains, each

with different hardware and software resources, representing a multi-domain, multi-technology 6G-enabled edge infrastructure. The setup validates the DESIRE6G architectural framework by combining programmable data planes, deterministic networking, and multi-domain federation to achieve end-to-end service assurance for latency-critical DT robotic applications.

FIGURE 76. 5TONIC TESTBED SETUP FOR DEMO 2

Domain 1 hosts the Unitree Go1 mobile robot equipped with a Mini-PC, camera, LiDAR, and 5G UE. The UE connects the robot to the indoor radio unit, which interfaces with the RAN and the 5G Core Network located in the 5TONIC edge data center. A programmable Tofino switch interconnects the 5G infrastructure with Edge Node 1 and a traffic generator that injects industrial traffic to emulate congestion scenarios. An SMO, with all its subcomponents, manages the deployment and lifecycle of the DT system in coordination with the IML. The robot's Mini-PC and Edge Node 1 form a Kubernetes cluster hosting the DT application and key DESIRE6G components, including the pervasive Kafka infrastructure-monitoring module (to collect and analyze application and infrastructure metrics), a MAS agent (to detect resource congestion and notify the SMO for reaction), and the IML (to manage the local virtualized infrastructure on Kubernetes and control the programmable switch). The Tofino switch implements the infra network functions (NFs) that form the forwarding graph between the robot and edge applications, as well as the Per-Packet-Value Traffic Manager (PPV-TM) module to ensure the quality of the mission-critical robotic data flows during network congestion.

Domain 2 provides a deterministic transport network managed by a centralized SDN controller, linking Domain 1 with Domain 3. The network ensures reliable, low-latency connectivity through programmable Tofino switches implementing DetNet Packet Replication, Elimination and Ordering Functions (PREOF).

Domain 3 hosts the PREDICT-6G architecture, comprising a TSN Ethernet network with its control-plane modules and a second edge node. The TSN switches forming this network implement the IEEE 802.1AS, 802.1Qbv, and 802.1CB standards to provide precise time synchronization, scheduled traffic, and frame replication and elimination for enhanced reliability.

All three domains include an orchestration layer that integrates the DESIRE6G DLT federation module, enabling dynamic and secure migration of robot applications across domains in response to resource degradation. A private Ethereum blockchain is deployed where all domains participate by running a blockchain node. Federation procedures are implemented on a smart contract serving as a distributed authority during the process. The blockchain is built using the open-source Go-Ethereum (Geth) [16] client and the smart contract is developed using the Solidity [17] programming language. The use of a private blockchain enables faster transaction processing times (i.e., validation and inclusion in the network), and lower operational costs (i.e., fees for executing transactions) compared to public, permissionless blockchains, while offering controlled membership and secure interactions among domains—key requirements for enabling efficient and trustworthy federation in mobile network infrastructures like DESIRE6G.

From the perspective of the **DESIRE6G architectural framework**, the demonstrator addresses the **deployment and service assurance** of an **edge-to-edge, latency-critical service** spanning a local physical domain (Domain 1) and its **federation** with two previously unknown external domains (Domain 2 and Domain 3). During federation, part of the service is dynamically deployed on external edge infrastructure, while high-reliability transport connectivity is maintained across all application and network functions.

5.1.2 Components

Table 12 details the DESIRE6G modules and components developed under WP3 and WP4 and integrated into Demo 2, along with references to their software repositories in the internal DESIRE6G platform and on Zenodo. The integration flavour and methodology, as well as the high-level architectural mapping are explained in Section 3.2.4.

TABLE 12. COMPONENTS AND MODULES INTEGRATED IN DEMO 2

System component	Module name	Module ID	Responsible	Project Repository pointer	Zenodo pointer
SMO	Data Lake	3.001	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Service Orchestrator	3.002	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Service Catalogue	3.003	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Topology	3.004	NUBIS	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/SMO	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776369
SMO	Optimization Engine	3.010	UVA	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Optimization_Engine	https://zenodo.org/records/1577184
SMO	IBN	3.005	EBY	Not open source	Not open source
SMO	DLT-federation	3.006	UC3M	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/DLT-Federation	https://zenodo.org/records/15744106
Intelligent Distributed Control, SMO	MLFO	3.007	UVA	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/multi-agent-system-uva	https://zenodo.org/records/1577141
Intelligent Distributed Control	MAS Agents	3.008	UVA	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/multi-agent-system-uva	https://zenodo.org/records/1577141
IML	Local NFVO	4.1001	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
Unified PDP	Per Packet Value Traffic Manager	4.2001	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/PPV-TM	https://zenodo.org/records/15776278
IML/intraNFs	NF Routing	4.2002	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev/intra-nfs	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
IML/intraNFs	UE2Service Mapper	4.2003	ELTE	https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO/tree/dev/intra-nfs	https://zenodo.org/records/15773623
Transport Network between D6G sites (external)	DetNet-PREOF	4.504	TID	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/PREOF	https://zenodo.org/records/15744258
Controller	SDN controller	3.012	UPM	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/TeraFlow-SDN	https://zenodo.org/records/105281/zenodo.1578182
Pervasive Monitoring	Infrastructure Kafka Monitoring	4.406	SSSA	https://github.com/asgamb/mon_manager/tree/main	https://zenodo.org/records/1577349

5.2 Goal of the Demonstrator and KPIs

5.2.1 Objectives

Objective 1 - Validation of a multi-layer, cloud-native 6G architecture integrating multi-domain orchestration, data-plane programmability, and AI-driven telemetry

The demonstrator validates the DESIRE6G reference architecture defined in D2.2 [6] by showcasing the coordinated operation of programmable network functions (IML), AI-driven telemetry and monitoring (MAS), and intent-based orchestration (SMO) for the automated deployment, configuration, and lifecycle management of the DT system. The framework leverages cloud-native technologies and advanced orchestration mechanisms (e.g., DLT-based federation) to dynamically instantiate and migrate network and application functions across multiple administrative domains. This enables adaptive placement of computation across the device–edge–cloud continuum while meeting the DT system’s stringent latency, availability, and reliability requirements.

Objective 2 - Automated deployment of a robotic DT system as a latency-critical end-to-end scenario identified as a key use case in WP2

The demonstrator employs a robotic DT system as a real-world end-to-end validation scenario for the DESIRE6G architecture, as identified by WP2 in D2.1 [7]. The system follows cloud-native and serverless principles, executing containerized robotic functions (e.g., sensor data processing, autonomous remote control, localization, mapping, and real-time DT simulation) distributed across the robot and edge infrastructure. These functions are dynamically instantiated or migrated according to current network and compute conditions. Runtime decisions rely on real-time telemetry and hierarchical service-assurance triggers to preserve latency, reliability, and compute-budget requirements even under congestion. This showcases DESIRE6G’s capability to support real-world, latency-critical, distributed serverless robotic workloads within a programmable 6G environment.

Objective 3 - Evaluation of hierarchical service-assurance mechanisms with coordinated multi-layer reactions

The demonstrator evaluates the DESIRE6G multi-layer service-assurance framework, highlighting the different reaction speeds, visibility scopes, and control granularities available at each architectural layer to satisfy the end-to-end latency and resource requirements of the DT service.

FIGURE 77. SERVICE-ASSURANCE LOOPS PRESENTED IN DEMO2

In this demo, two assurance levels are validated as shown on Figure 77:

- **Infrastructure layer:** the IML reacts within milliseconds to network congestion by autonomously reconfiguring the PPV-TM module running on the programmable Tofino switch, ensuring prioritization of mission-critical robot flows and maintaining the required service performance.
- **Control and orchestration layers:** the MAS performs cross-layer anomaly detection using pervasive telemetry (Kafka), identifying resource degradation at the application-level and escalating SLA violations to the SMO, which automatically triggers an application-migration request toward an external domain using its DLT-based Federation module.

Together, these mechanisms demonstrate the DESIRE6G hierarchical assurance model, in which rapid local reactions and higher-level orchestration decisions work in synergy to ensure end-to-end service continuity and resilience.

Objective 4 - Validation of zero-trust, dynamic federation across multiple administrative domains using distributed ledger technologies

The demonstrator validates DESIRE6G's capability to use Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) as a zero-trust mechanism to enable dynamic federation between the different administrative domains at the orchestration layer. Each domain integrates the SMO with a DLT-based Federation module, which uses blockchain and smart contracts to enable secure, privacy-preserving, fast, and distributed interactions during the federation process.

The blockchain-based federation mechanism is exercised in a dynamic scenario where resource congestion is intentionally introduced in one of the DT service application functions. In response, the system (acting as the consumer domain) automatically establishes two on-the-fly federation agreements with independent and previously unknown service providers: one to host the migrated application function on an external edge infrastructure with sufficient resources, and another to ensure reliable data-plane connectivity between the migrated function and the remaining DT components. This validates the integration of blockchain technology into the DESIRE6G architecture, enabling the creation of secure, dynamic federation agreements that allow service providers to interact and share services without prior trust relationships.

5.2.2 Target KPIs

Table 13 summarizes the KPIs evaluated in Demo 2. It includes the use-case KPIs defined in D2.1 [7] for the DT use case (with optional target values), as well as the DESIRE6G Objective KPIs associated with Objective O7 (demonstration), for which target evaluation is mandatory.

TABLE 13. KPIS EVALUATED IN DEMO 2 FOR THE DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE AND DESIRE6G OBJECTIVE O7

KPI type	KPI target	Measurements
DT use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI1 - E2E latency: 1-100 ms	End-to-end service latency
DT use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI2 - Bandwidth: 1-1000 Mbps	Service Throughput
DT use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI3 - Reliability: 99.999%	Reliability
DT use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI3 - Availability: 99.999% to 99.999999%	Availability
DT use case KPI (D2.1)	KPI4 - Scalability: 1-50 nodes	Scalability
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.1: >1000 real/emulated devices, simultaneously requiring > 100 heterogeneous realistic services (including ultra-low latency-bounded services)	1000 concurrent emulated users with their traffic efficiently managed and prioritized by the IML/PPV-TM in the programmable data plane.
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.2: all services handled with no manual intervention, including creation and suppression, based on the defined MAS system, with knowledge transfer among MAS for perceived infinite capacity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMO computation times of each module • IML computation time • SMO/SDN controller flow entry enforcement times • Reconfiguration automation (IML, PDP) • Multi-domain service federation automation (SMO)

DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.3: <100ms AI-driven decision making (leveraging on appropriate HW acceleration) and re-optimization, guaranteeing the defined KQIs, including end-to-end latency from terminal to edge under varying traffic and service conditions.	AI-driven deployment and federation decision (OE)
DESIRE6G Objectives KPIs (O7)	KPI7.4: Dynamic serverless function placement with function redundancy and replication, and topology reconfiguration for application resilience with perceived zero-latency, in the sub-second scale.	SMO-based serverless app deployment placement and migration during federation process

5.3 Demo2 Functional Validation

Demo 2 implements the Digital Twin use case within the 5TONIC testbed and integrates all key components of the DESIRE6G architecture. As illustrated in Figure 78, it includes software modules spanning all architectural layers, namely the SMO, MAS, IML, infrastructure NFs, and the physical infrastructure layer. In Demo 2, functional validation is carried out by completing the integration of all involved components and systematically verifying their interactions through targeted validation tests. Additionally, all planned workflows are executed to ensure that each step is correctly handled by the corresponding components, in accordance with the design and implementation.

FIGURE 78 DEMO 2: INTEGRATION OF THE ARCHITECTURAL LAYERS AND MODULES

Table 14 summarizes the bidirectional integration relationships established in Demo 2: green cells indicate full peer-to-peer integration via a defined interface (I), orange cells represent master-slave dependencies involving parameter exchange or function invocation (F), and blue cells denote tight integration through shared code or internal dependencies (C). In total, 24 inter-module integration relationships have been implemented and validated in this demonstrator.

- The SMO components were initially validated at the northbound interface, building on baseline integration from the Y2 demonstration (see D5.2). Validation focused on the SO, SLA-to-Intent-Translation, SC, DL, OE, and MLFO, confirming that intent-level service graphs are correctly processed into deployable network service descriptors by the IML.
- Further tests verified the correct handling of intent-based service requests by the SLA-to-Intent-Translation, site-decomposition decisions by the OE using live topology information, and the automatic generation of MAS pipeline descriptors at the MLFO based on service monitoring requirements. Validated service graphs were then submitted to the IML (LNFVO), confirming correct deployment of network functions, application components, and MAS agents, including placement, ordering, and configuration.
- The MAS integration with the Kafka-based monitoring infrastructure was validated by verifying the availability and consistency of application-level and infrastructure metrics collected from the Kubernetes cluster. It is important to note that the MAS used in this demonstration differs from the one employed in Demo 1. In this case, a simplified MAS implementation developed by UVA is adopted, consisting of a single monitoring agent. Its role is to detect resource congestion and SLA violations affecting DT application functions and to notify the SMO layer for corrective actions. Tests confirmed that the monitored metrics were correctly ingested and made available to the MAS, enabling timely anomaly detection and escalation.
- The interaction between IML and PPV-TM, building on Y2 integration, was tested under congestion scenarios. Results confirmed that the IML dynamically reconfigures PPV-TM policies in response to SLA violations, validating the service-assurance loop. Further validation of the programmable data plane included extensive testing of UE2SM and NFR functions, ensuring proper packet (de)encapsulation, D6G header handling, and forwarding behaviour across the testbed.
- Significant validation effort was also dedicated to the DLT-based Federation module within the SMO. Tests verified correct interactions between the SO and the federation module via the

east/westbound interface, including the creation and submission of blockchain transactions and the correct handling of smart-contract event notifications during inter-domain federation procedures.

- Finally, the SDN controller was validated through integration tests with both the programmable Tofino switches (via the BFRT API) and the SMO (via REST-based northbound interfaces). These tests confirmed correct control of the transport network, including PREOF/DetNet P4 table loading and dynamic switch configuration driven by SMO instructions.

TABLE 14 DEMO 2 INTEGRATION MAP

Module	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1 DL																
2 SO	I															
3 SC	I	I														
4 Topology	I	I	I													
5 SLA-to-Intent-Translation	-	I	I	-												
6 OE	-	I	I	I	I											
7 DLT-Federation	-	I	-	-	-	-	I									
8 MLFO	-	I	-	-	-	-	-									
9 MAS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I								
10 LNFVO	-	I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
11 PPV-TM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I						
12 NFR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	F	-					
13 UE2SM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	F	-	C				
14 SDN controller	-	I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
15 DetNet-PREOF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I		
16 Infrastructure Kafka Monitoring	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I	-	-	-	-	-	-	

5.4 Implementation of the application

The demonstrator integrates a distributed DT application designed to showcase real-time collaboration between a robot and a human operator over a 6G-enabled network infrastructure. The use case, fully detailed in Deliverable D2.1 [7], represents an industrial warehouse scenario in which a remote operator uses the DT application to assign autonomous tasks (e.g., object delivery or inspection) to a mobile robot. During operation, the robot continuously sends joint states, LiDAR data, odometry, and camera feeds upstream to the edge computing platform, where applications process this information and generate safe control commands downstream that guide the robot throughout its mission. As the robot moves,

its behaviour is mirrored in the virtual environment in real time, enabling continuous monitoring and allowing the human operator to intervene when necessary.

5.4.1 Distributed DT application workflow

The distributed DT application workflow spans the robot, the 5TONIC-provided 5G SA network (including both RAN and Core), the programmable data plane, and the edge computing infrastructure, together providing the low latency, high bandwidth, and computational capacity required for real-time autonomous operation.

As illustrated in Figure 79, the workflow is conceptualized within an industrial warehouse scenario, where the mobile robot has previously mapped its environment using Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithms and can autonomously perform intralogistics tasks such as transporting payloads between designated locations. First, the remote operator uses the DT application to assign an autonomous mission to the robot (Figure 79-A). Next, upon receiving the goal, the Auto Navigation Stack running on the edge computes a global path to the target position and continuously generates safe motion commands for the robot, taking into account obstacles and dynamic environmental changes (Figure 79-B). Finally, the robot executes these control commands locally and continuously streams sensor data (e.g., joint states, LiDAR scans, odometry, and camera feeds) to the edge node hosting the DT application, which processes this data in real time to synchronize the virtual model with its physical counterpart (Figure 79-C). As a result, the operator can see the robot's movements mirrored live in the virtual space, visualize its trajectory on the dynamic map, and monitor the video feed simultaneously, achieving a real-time and safe closed-loop collaboration between human and robot.

FIGURE 79. DISTRIBUTED DT APPLICATION WORKFLOW: (A) MISSION ASSIGNMENT BY THE REMOTE OPERATOR; (B) EDGE-BASED ROBOT AUTONOMOUS NAVIGATION AND CONTROL; (C) DT SYNCHRONIZATION

5.4.2 Application tools and software

The robot software is implemented using the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework, specifically the ROS 1 Noetic [18] distribution, while the DT application is developed using the NVIDIA Isaac Sim [19] robot simulator. All components of the distributed application are fully containerized and deployed as Pods and Services across a two-node Kubernetes cluster within Domain 1 (shown in Figure 80).

The cluster is built using the K3s [20] lightweight Kubernetes distribution (version 1.28.8 + k3s1). Edge Node 1 operates as the K3s server (control-plane node), while the robot's mini-PC acts as the K3s agent (worker node). Pod-to-pod communication is implemented through Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network (VXLAN) encapsulation protocol, manually configured via the Linux iproute2 [21] package. Each Pod is attached to the overlay network using the Multus [22] Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin, allowing seamless communication between the robot and edge applications.

The distributed DT application consists of several key software modules:

- **Go1 ROS Wrapper (robot):** Provides a high-level ROS interface for controlling the Unitree Go1 robot and publishing its state (odometry, joint states, and IMU data) over ROS topics. The interaction uses the Unitree Go1 SDK [23] in high-level control mode, enabling velocity, orientation, and gait commands for full-body motion control.
- **LiDAR (robot):** Implements ROS drivers for the SLAMTEC RPLIDAR A3 laser scanner, offering a range of up to 25 m, a scanning frequency of 20 Hz, and millimeter-level precision. This component provides real-time mapping and obstacle detection, supporting navigation and SLAM in dynamic environments.
- **Camera (robot):** Runs a video-streaming sender application that captures frames from the Logitech C920e UVC webcam. The video is encoded in MJPEG format and streamed in real time over UDP (User Datagram Protocol) to the Video Receiver component at a resolution of 720p and 30 FPS.
- **Video Receiver (edge):** Receives the MJPEG stream, decodes it, and re-encodes it into H.264 at the target bitrate and resolution. The processed video is transmitted via SRT (Secure Reliable Transport) to a MediaMTX [24] media server, which redistributes the feed to web clients using the WebRTC protocol, allowing live visualization through a browser interface. Both the sender

and receiver applications are written in Python and use GStreamer [25] multimedia framework, accessed via the PyGObject API, for video capture, encoding, and streaming.

- **ROS Master (edge):** Provides naming and registration services for all ROS nodes in the DT system, enabling seamless inter-module communication through ROS topics and service registry.
- **Digital Twin (edge):** Implements a high-fidelity virtual replica of the physical Unitree Go1 robot using NVIDIA Isaac Sim 2023.1.0, accelerated through the NVIDIA Container Toolkit [26] for GPU-based physics simulation. The ROS Bridge extension enables Isaac Sim to subscribe to real-time sensor data (e.g., joint states) and accurately reproduce the robot's movements within the simulated environment.
- **Auto Navigation Stack (edge):** Integrates the ROS navigation stack to enable autonomous motion planning and control of the robot. It performs SLAM using the Google Cartographer [27] algorithm to build and continuously update a two-dimensional occupancy map of the environment in real time. Based on this map, the stack computes a global path toward the target goal defined by the remote operator, while a local planner dynamically generates real-time velocity commands to avoid obstacles and ensure smooth, safe navigation.

FIGURE 80. KUBERNETES CLUSTER ARCHITECTURE FOR THE DISTRIBUTED DT APPLICATION

5.5 Demonstration startup and workflows

The demonstration comprises a startup phase followed by the execution of three workflows, each designed to validate specific capabilities of the DESIRE6G architecture under different operational

conditions. An overview of the startup phase and workflows, and their mapping to the DESIRE6G architectural layers, is shown in Figure 81.

The startup and steady-state phase (**W0**) establish the baseline operational conditions of the demonstrator. In this phase, the DT application is assumed to be already instantiated and running in the testbed, with all DESIRE6G network functions deployed and operational, in order to characterize steady-state system behaviour. This phase provides baseline measurements of robot traffic throughput and end-to-end communication performance.

The first workflow focuses on service deployment (**W1**) and involves the full architectural stack, from the SMO layer down to the programmable data plane. It validates the coordinated interaction of orchestration, control, and infrastructure components required to instantiate the DT service.

The second workflow (**W2**) addresses the service-assurance loop under service degradation conditions, in particular network congestion at the programmable data plane. This workflow involves the IML, which detects the degradation and autonomously restores service performance by reprogramming the PPV-TM deployed on the Tofino switch. Appropriate QoS policies are enforced to prioritize mission-critical robot traffic over emulated background services and users.

Finally, the third workflow (**W3**) validates the DLT-based multi-domain federation capabilities of DESIRE6G in a dynamic scenario triggered by application-level resource congestion. In this workflow, federation enables the on-demand migration of the affected serverless application function to an external administrative domain without prior bilateral agreements, thereby extending local infrastructure capabilities and ensuring service continuity. This workflow involves all architectural layers, with particular focus on the orchestration layer, which leverages blockchain technology to support secure and distributed control-plane interactions across domains during the federation process.

FIGURE 81. DEMO 2 WORKFLOWS MAPPED IN THE DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE

5.5.1 Startup and steady state

This section describes the mapping of each service-chain component, including both application and network functions, within the 5TONIC testbed infrastructure. The focus is on Domain 1, which acts as the primary DESIRE6G site hosting the DT system, and on the end-to-end data path spanning the robot, the 5G RAN, the programmable data plane, and the edge node, which carries most of the workflow executed during the experimental validation.

The mapping is shown in Figure 82. The DT network service deployed in this domain includes the distributed DT application (described in the previous section) and a firewall NF running on the edge node (as a containerized NF), both executed as containerized services within the Kubernetes cluster. During normal operation, the robot continuously transmits sensor data (LiDAR, camera, odometry, and state information) upstream to the edge node to update its virtual model, while receiving control commands downstream from the edge for navigation and actuation. The complete service chain, implemented using DESIRE6G data-plane components, operates as follows:

Uplink direction:

1. The robot sends sensor data streams through the 5TONIC-provided 5G network toward the Tofino switch acting as a DESIRE6G Gateway that implements the UE2ServiceMapper (UE2SM), Network Function Routing (NFR) functions (including transport adapter functions) and the PPV-TM traffic management solution. We also created an artificial bottleneck between two ports of the switch. All the traffic (robot traffic and the background traffic generated by a traffic generator) is directed through this link to demonstrate the PPV-TM traffic management approach. For RAN traversal, the robot traffic is encapsulated in a VXLAN tunnel. The tunnel is terminated by Tofino switch and the decapsulated packets are handed over to the UE2SM.
2. The UE2SM attaches the D6G header to encapsulate flow metadata for service and UE identification and steering. The encapsulated packets are then forwarded by the Tofino switch's NFR module to the NFR running on the local Kubernetes node that then forwards the packets to the firewall NF deployed on the same Kubernetes system (the edge node).
3. On the edge node, the firewall NF inspects the traffic before handing it over to the DT applications. The processed packets are then sent back to the NFR running on the Kubernetes node.
4. The NFR performs D6G header decapsulation and carries out the final packet forwarding to the destination DT application modules running on the Kubernetes cluster (edge node). The application pod cannot handle DESIRE6G headers and thus it is external to the DESIRE6G domain and thus the removal of the special header is needed.

Downlink direction:

1. The DT application modules running as AF pods on the Kubernetes cluster generate IP packets and thus, they are external to the DESIRE6G domain. The outgoing traffic of these pods is first handled by the UE2SM instance running on the edge server, extending packets with DESIRE6G headers.
2. The NFR also running on the same node then forwards the packets to the Firewall NF.
3. Then NFR gets back the packet, determines the next NF to be visited and forwards the packet to the Tofino switch.
4. The Tofino switch recognizes the DESIRE6G header and applies NFR to execute the forwarding logic. As a result, the DESIRE6G header is removed, the packet is encapsulated into a VXLAN tunnel and sent to the robot through the RAN. Note that the artificial bottleneck link is not crossed in the downlink direction.

FIGURE 82. DEMO 2: MAPPING OF DATA PLANE COMPONENTS

5.5.2 Workflow 1: Service Deployment

The workflow (illustrated in Figure 83) starts when the tenant submits a service-deployment request to the SMO, specifying high-level requirements (Step 1). The Intent-Based Networking (IBN) component translates this request into a service graph (Step 2), stores the resulting graph in the service catalog (Step 3), and forwards the intent to the Service Orchestrator (SO) (Step 4).

Upon receiving the request, the SO retrieves the service graph and queries the Optimization Engine (OE) with a decomposition request, to determine how the service graph should be deployed across the DESIRE6G sites (Step 5). The OE collects aggregated infrastructure resource availability information from the Topology module and uses the service graph specifications and SLO constraints to determine which partitioning strategy has the highest probability to achieve the specified SLO constraints and executes the service-partitioning logic (Steps 6 and 7), as described in Deliverable D3.2, Section 3.2. In this scenario, there is only a single DESIRE6G site available. As expected, the OE annotates the graph with the corresponding site identifier and returns the updated graph to the SO (Step 8), as there is no need for service graph partitioning in this instance, showcasing an edge case scenario. The code below shows the final NSD YAML service graph deployed by the IML. The structure of the YAML service graph is analysed in Section 4.4.2.1.

```
lnsd:
  ns-instance-id: "22113344"
  ns:
    name: "Digital Twin demo2"
    id: "bbbbcccc"
    vendor: "D6G"
    descriptor-version: "1.0"
    site-id: "site1"
    location-id: 50
    default-service-id: "20"

    site-connections: []
    infra-nfs: []

    application-functions:

      # On edge AF
      - instance-id: "app"
        id: "gol-navigation"
        name: "gol navigation"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.11"]
        is-scalable: true
        instances: 2
        static-instance-ips: ["10.10.10.11", "10.11.7.6"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"

      - instance-id: "ros"
        id: "ros-master"
        name: "ros-master"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.10"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"

      - instance-id: "twin"
        id: "digital-twin"
        name: "digital twin"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.13"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"

      - instance-id: "receiver"
        id: "video-receiver"
        name: "video receiver"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.14"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"

      - instance-id: "mediamtx"
        id: "mediamtx"
        name: "mediamtx"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.15"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"

      - instance-id: "vizanti"
        id: "vizanti"
        name: "vizanti"
        version: "1.0"
        domain: "external"
        static-ips: ["172.20.50.16"]
        shared-bridge: "ros-br-0"
```

```
- instance-id: "mas-a"
  id: "mas-a"
  name: "mas-a"
  version: "1.0"
  domain: "external"
  static-ips: ["172.20.50.93"]

# On robot UE
- instance-id: "gol-base"
  id: "gol-base"
  name: "Go 1 Base"
  version: "1.0"
  domain: "external"
  is-ue: true
  static-ips: ["172.20.50.7"]
  external-routing: true

- instance-id: "lidar"
  id: "lidar"
  name: "lidar"
  version: "1.0"
  domain: "external"
  is-ue: true
  static-ips: ["172.20.50.8"]
  external-routing: true

- instance-id: "streamer"
  id: "video-streamer"
  name: "Video Streamer"
  version: "1.0"
  domain: "external"
  is-ue: true
  static-ips: ["172.20.50.9"]
  external-routing: true

# Pseudo node
- instance-id: "ran"
  name: "RAN"
  version: "1.0"
  domain: "external"
  is-ue: true
  static-ips: ["172.20.50.8"]
  extra-ueids: [["172.20.50.9", "172.20.50.7"]]

network-functions:
- instance-id: "firewall"
  id: "firewall-bmv2"
  name: "Firewall"
  version: "1.0"

forwarding_graphs:
- graph-name: "upstream2"
  direction: "upstream"
  links:
  - id: "upstream-3"
    connection-points:
    - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
    - if-id-ref: "firewall:0"
  - id: "upstream-4"
    connection-points:
    - if-id-ref: "firewall:0"
    - if-id-ref: "app:0"
- graph-name: "downstream2"
  direction: "downstream"
  links:
  - id: "downstream-3"
```

```

connection-points:
  - if-id-ref: "app:0"
  - if-id-ref: "firewall:0"
- id: "downstream-4"
  connection-points:
    - if-id-ref: "firewall:0"
    - if-id-ref: "ran:0"
    
```

Next, the SO sends the service description to the Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO), which generates the Multi-Agent System (MAS) pipeline descriptor, including the application functions and resource metrics to be monitored in the Kubernetes cluster through the pervasive Kafka-based monitoring framework (Steps 9–11).

Finally, the SO sends the resulting sub-graph to the IML, which deploys the MAS components, application modules, and required network functions across the local infrastructure, thereby instantiating the full bidirectional service chain (Steps 12–14).

FIGURE 83. DEMO 2 WORKFLOW 1: SERVICE DEPLOYMENT

5.5.3 Workflow 2: IML-based Service Assurance

In this workflow (shown in Figure 84), network congestion is intentionally introduced in the programmable Tofino switch on a loopback link directly connecting two ports of the device. The capacity of this loopback link is set manually. All the uplink traffic is directed through this link. We use the traffic-generator server to emulate the load of 1000 concurrent users (Step 1). In this setup, the first emulated user represents a second robot participating in the DT service, while the remaining 999 users correspond to a background network service. Initially, the robot service is calibrated for a single robot UE with a guaranteed bandwidth of 90 Mbps. The background traffic is in a different slice where each user has a guaranteed minimum bandwidth of 1Mbps. Under these conditions, the synthetic traffic (1 additional robot + 999 background) overloads the data plane and degrades the performance of the DT system, causing increased delays and reduced throughput. The guaranteed minimum requirements cannot be satisfied for all the traffic sources in the overloaded case.

The watchdog service running on the Tofino switch monitors link-level congestion threshold values (In the Per-Packet-Value Traffic Manager (PPV-TM), packets with a value less than this number are dropped) at millisecond-level timescales to detect sustained congestion levels and SLA violation. When the value reported by the PPV-TM violates the SLA threshold defined for the DT service, the watchdog reports an SLA violation event to the IML (Step 2). Note that the measured congestion threshold value and the applied policy settings are enough to recognize SLA violation. In response, the IML automatically reconfigures the PPV-TM through its QoS API to protect the mission-critical flows of both the real and the emulated robots, according to the performance requirements defined in the service graph (Step 3). The PPV-TM update enforces per-service and per-user isolation, allocating additional guaranteed bandwidth to the low-latency slice associated with the real and the emulated robot.

Once the new policies are applied, the traffic flows corresponding to both robots are elevated above the background traffic, enabling the DT system to maintain correct operation despite the network congestion.

FIGURE 84. DEMO 2 WORKFLOW 2: IML-BASED SERVICE ASSURANCE

5.5.4 Workflow 3: Multi-domain Blockchain Federation

In this final workflow (illustrated in Figure 85), we validate the blockchain-based federation capability of the SMO. A private Ethereum blockchain network is already active, and the Federation Smart Contract (SC) is deployed on top of it. All participating domains are registered in the SC using a unique blockchain address, and interactions during federation are executed through immutable on-chain transactions issued via each domain’s DLT federation module within the SMO. At the start of this workflow, Domain 1 hosts the DT service instantiated in Workflow 1.

The workflow begins in Domain 1, where the MAS continuously monitors application-level resource usage via the pervasive Kafka-based monitoring framework, specifically reading CPU-limit metrics exposed by the Kubernetes Metrics Server API. To intentionally trigger an SLA violation, we saturate the CPU of the autonomous-navigation container (Step 1). The MAS detects the degradation and escalates an alert to the SMO layer (Step 2). The SO attempts a local remediation by redeploying the application within the local DESIRE6G site (Step 3). However, the OE determines that no sufficient resources are

available and returns an error (Step 4). At this point, Domain 1, acting as a consumer domain, uses its SMO’s DLT federation module to issue two sequential federation requests on the smart contract:

FIGURE 85. DEMO 2 WORKFLOW 3: MULTI-DOMAIN BLOCKCHAIN FEDERATION

Federation request 1: reliable layer-2 service connectivity

The consumer initiates the first request (Step 5), announcing the need for reliable, zero-packet-loss transport connectivity. Domain 2, subscribed to SC events, receives the announcement (Step 6) and responds by submitting a bid offer with its service price, following a reverse-auction mechanism (Step 7-8). The consumer accepts the offer and provides the traffic profile to be protected (Steps 9-10), including the source IPs of the robot and Edge Node 1, and the type of service (ToS) fields associated with the DT service application flows.

Domain 2 then deploys the transport service by instructing its SDN controller to configure its Tofino switches (Step 11), establishing Layer-2 connectivity with DetNet PREOF (Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions) between Domain 1 and Domain 3. For simplicity, the scenario assumes pre-existing connectivity between Domains 2 and 3.

After configuring the transport network, Domain 2 submits a blockchain transaction confirming successful service deployment (Steps 12–13), completing the first federation negotiation.

Federation request 2: ROS application migration

With the reliable transport path established, the consumer issues the second federation request for autonomous-navigation application migration (Steps 14-15). Through the same event-subscription mechanism, Domain 3 is discovered and selected as the provider (Steps 16–19). Domain 1 shares the necessary information for the federated service, including the Kubernetes deployment manifest for the ROS application and VXLAN endpoint for inter-domain data-plane connectivity. Using this information, Domain 3 establishes a VXLAN tunnel to Domain 1 and deploys the ROS application in its local Kubernetes cluster, attaching it to the overlay network using the Multus CNI plugin (Step 20). After deployment, Domain 3 submits a confirmation transaction to the smart contract (Step 21). Domain 1 receives this confirmation (Step 22), finalizes the VXLAN interconnection, and safely removes the degraded local instance (Step 23). Please note that the original application remains active and intact until the new instance is fully deployed and verified to ensure seamless migration without service interruption. As a result, the robot re-establishes ROS communication with the newly deployed application in Domain 3, and the navigation task continues without interruption. Federation is considered successful when continuous app-to-app communication is achieved between Domain 1 (consumer) and Domain 3 (provider).

5.6 Test and results

This section presents the main test executions carried out for each workflow. For each test, results are summarized in dedicated tables and complemented with plots generated from repeated executions to obtain statistically significant metrics.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D2-Wo	Workflow 0 (Steady State) Main Test	1	UC3M
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test

5TONIC	Demo 2	DT App, NFR, UE2SM	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the steady-state performance of the network and the DT application with all DESIRE6G data-plane functions already deployed and operational.		
Test requirements	The test requires the presence of a human operator to verify correct robot operation during execution. All devices must be manually configured and activated prior to testing. The RAN is operational, and the Kubernetes cluster is active, running all DT application components shown in Figure 80 as pod instances distributed across the robot Mini-PC and the edge node. The cluster also hosts a BMv2 switch deployed as a containerized component, enabling communication between the Tofino switch and the applications running on the edge node.		
External tools	N/A.		
Measurement	End-to-end network throughput and latency, and DT application throughput.		
Related Project KPIs	KPI 1,2 DT use case, KPI 7.4		
Test execution			
Initial setup/assumptions	The robot, the RAN, the Tofino switch, and the edge node are powered on and operational.		
Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploy and configure the DESIRE6G data-plane network functions (UE2SM, NFR). • Activate the UE at the robot • Generate iperf3 traffic from the robot to the edge node through the RAN and the Tofino switch to assess end-to-end communication performance. • Start the robot's autonomous navigation task with the DT application fully operational 		
Test results			
End-to-end network performance with the DESIRE6G data plane activated			

FIGURE 86. DEMO 2: END-TO-END THROUGHPUT, JITTER, AND PACKET-LOSS WITH DATA PLANE ENABLED

Figure 86 reports the uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) throughput, jitter, and packet loss, obtained from the robot UE side during a 60-second iperf3 UDP session with the edge node acting as server, with the DESIRE6G data plane active along the path. The throughput remains stable in both directions—approximately 810 Mbit/s in DL and 250 Mbit/s in UL. These values are determined by the RAN, which constitutes the limiting segment of the end-to-end communication path. No additional constraints are introduced by the Kubernetes execution environment or the programmable data plane, which supports line-rate forwarding up to 100 Gbps. Jitter remains extremely low (around 0.12 ms on average), and packet loss is 0%, demonstrating that the system fully supports the real-time requirements of DT synchronization and robotic-control requirements.

FIGURE 87. DEMO 2: END-TO-END ROUND-TRIP TIME WITH DATA PLANE ENABLED

Figure 87 presents the RTT latency characteristics of the same end-to-end communication path, obtained from an ICMP ping test and shown as a Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) over 1000 samples. The distribution indicates a minimum RTT of 6.17 ms, a median (p50) of 8.7 ms, and tail latencies of 13.5 ms (p90), 15.3 ms (p95), and 22 ms (p99). The widening of the curve between the median and higher percentiles reflects the moderate variability typical of 5G wireless access, while the overall latency profile remains sufficiently low to support real-time system operation.

DT application performance

Figure 88 reports the steady-state performance of the DT application in terms of network throughput exchanged between the robot and the edge pod instances. Pod-level traffic is monitored in real time, stored in InfluxDB, and visualized using the Grafana dashboard shown in the figure. Network activity is derived from the cumulative transmit and receive byte counters exposed by the Linux kernel for each

pod network interface via /proc/net/dev. Grafana computes TX and RX throughput as the rate of change of these counters over time, yielding real-time values in bits per second for the relevant application pods.

In the **uplink** direction (robot to edge), the go1-ros-wrapper pod transmits approximately 1.5 Mbit/s, corresponding to **odometry, joint states, and IMU messages** (blue trace). The **LiDAR** data stream (red trace) generates around 3.5 Mbit/s, while the **video stream** received by the edge-side video-receiver pod (purple trace) dominates the traffic with an average throughput of about 85 Mbit/s. This results in an **aggregated throughput close to 90 Mbit/s**. As shown in the figure, the LiDAR and robot state streams remain stable due to fixed sampling rates, bounded message sizes, and reliable TCPROS transport. In contrast, the video stream exhibits moderate throughput variations (82–86 Mbit/s), which is expected due to the use of MJPEG encoding over UDP at 1280x720 HD resolution, where each video frame is independently compressed and its size depends on the visual complexity of the captured scene.

In the **downlink** direction (edge to robot), the **control commands** delivered to the go1-ros-wrapper pod (yellow trace) require less than **500 kbit/s**, reflecting the small message size of high-level velocity commands.

FIGURE 88 DT APP PERFORMANCE

Robot autonomous navigation task

Figure 89 illustrates the main functionalities of the developed DT application that is used by the remote operator to assign and supervise an autonomous navigation task to the robot. The upper section of the interface provides an interactive map where the operator defines the navigation goal, while the blue trajectory represents the path previously travelled by the robot. The lower-left panel shows the robot's live camera feed and the lower-right panel displays the virtual replica of the robot continuously synchronized with its physical counterpart in real time, enabling simultaneous visual monitoring.

FIGURE 89 DT APP INTERFACE FOR AUTONOMOUS ROBOT NAVIGATION AND MONITORING

Test outcome comments

End-to-end communication measurements between the robot UE and the edge node with the DESIRE6G data plane enabled show stable and predictable performance. At the **network level**, **downlink and uplink throughput** remain stable at approximately **810 Mbit/s** and **250 Mbit/s**, respectively, with the RAN constituting the limiting segment of the end-to-end path, very low jitter (≈ 0.12 ms) and no packet loss. **RTT latency** is consistently low, with typical values in the **8.5–15 ms range** and bounded peaks below 25 ms, fully supporting closed-loop real-time robotic operation. At the **application level**, the **uplink aggregated traffic** is approximately **90 Mbit/s**, dominated by the video stream (~ 85 Mbit/s), followed by LiDAR (~ 3.5 Mbps) and robot state data (~ 1.5 Mbps). **Downlink traffic**, corresponding to robot control commands from the edge, remains below **500 kbit/s**. Overall, these results confirm stable steady-state operation and sufficient performance margins to reliably support real-time DT synchronization and robotic control.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D2-W1	Workflow 1 (service deployment) Main Test	2	UC3M, NUBIS, ELTE, UVA, EBY
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
UC3M	Demo 2	DT App, IBN, SO, SC, OE, MLFO, IML (LNFVO), DT App, NFR, UE2SM, MAS	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the computation time of the key DESIRE6G control-plane modules involved in the DT service deployment workflow.		
Test requirements	The SMO modules (IBN, SO, OE, MLFO, and SC) and the IML (LNFVO) are deployed and operational. The Kubernetes cluster is available and reachable for service instantiation. No DT service instance is running prior to the test execution.		
External tools	N/A		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMO processing time • IML/LNFVO processing time • Deployment time contributions due to SMO, IML and Kubernetes 		
Related Project KPIs	KPI 7.2, KPI 7.3, KPI 7.4		
Test execution			
Initial setup/assumptions	The RAN is active, and the robot UE is connected to the network. The robot Mini-PC, the Tofino switch, the edge node, and the control-plane virtual machine hosting the SMO components are all powered on and operational.		
Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploy and start all the SMO and IML subsystems to run in steady state 		

- Verify that no DT services are instantiated and that no DT traffic is flowing
- Trigger the workflow by sending a service deployment request from the tenant to the SMO, specifying high-level requirements (application and network functions, service links, and E2E latency constraints)
- Verify that the IBN correctly translates the intent into a service graph and stores it in the SC
- Verify that the SO retrieves the service graph from the SC and requests service decomposition from the OE
- Verify that the OE computes the service decomposition for the available site and returns the annotated service graph to the SO
- Verify that the SO forwards the service description to the MLFO and that the MAS pipeline descriptor is generated
- Verify that the SO sends the resulting sub-graph to the IML/LNFVO
- Verify that the IML/LNFVO receives and parses the sub-graph, instantiates the application functions, network functions, and MAS components, and configures the NFs control plane
- Verify that the IML/LNFVO reports the deployment outcome to the SO and that the SO receives the ack
- Verify that e2e DT application traffic is flowing is established and flowing correctly
- Measure and record the computation time contributions of the SMO and IML modules

Test results

The experimental evaluation breaks down the execution time between SMO and non-SMO components. Figure 90 presents measurements collected at the SMO level, distinguishing the main SMO processing stages and the corresponding SO interaction with the IML in Domain1. Each step is depicted with a distinct color and annotated with the relevant DESIRE6G modules. The results indicate that all SMO-related functions—including IBN, SO, SC, Topology, OE, and MLFO—consistently execute within the millisecond scale. SMO processing remains below a few tens of milliseconds, demonstrating that management and control operations contribute negligible latency to the overall workflow. Among these stages, the SLA-to-Intent translation phase is the first and one of the most time-consuming steps, accounting for around 70 ms, reflecting the overhead of interpreting high-level tenant requirements and

generating structured service representations. The service decomposition phase contributes approximately 30 ms and corresponds to the interaction between the SO, OE, and Topology modules to derive the deployment structure and select the target site. The MAS pipeline computation phase takes around 13 ms and captures the interaction between the SO and the MLFO. During this phase, the MAS pipeline descriptor is constructed using the service details, including the service instance identifier and the endpoint and exposed topics of the pervasive Kafka-based monitoring module associated with application pod resource usage. The dominant contribution in the timeline is the IML phase, which takes about 121 ms and includes validation of service sub-graphs and generation of Kubernetes manifests for subsequent instantiation. Overall, from the **SMO perspective**, the **complete control-plane operation (excluding Kubernetes execution)** completes in approximately **234 ms**.

FIGURE 90. DT SERVICE DEPLOYMENT: SMO AND NON-SMO PROCESSING TIMES

FIGURE 91. DT SERVICE DEPLOYMENT: IML TIME CONTRIBUTIONS INCLUDING KUBERNETES

From the IML perspective, Figure 91 illustrates the time contributions during the deployment process within Domain1 via the LNFVO API. After receiving the NSD, the IML completes its internal processing in about 1.40 ms, followed by a 119.84 ms interval dedicated to generating pod configuration specifications through Kubernetes API calls. The subsequent pod creation occurs in parallel, taking several seconds to instantiate eleven distinct pods: the lidar-app, go1-ros-wrapper, and camera-app on the robot’s Mini-PC, as well as the digital-twin-app, video-receiver-app, auto-navigation-app, firewall-nf, MAS, af-selector, and NFR on Edge Node 1. Once deployment is finalized, the IML computes and delivers the control-plane rules to the NFR and af-selector components in less than 6 s, bringing the **total duration of the IML-driven deployment** process to approximately 22 s.

Test outcome comments

The results confirm that the SMO/IML architecture meets the targeted KPIs for automation, decision making, and resilience. Service creation and deployment are carried out in a fully autonomous way, without any manual intervention, thus directly validating KPI7.2. The processing times of the main SMO components (IBN, SO, SC, Topology, OE, and MLFO) consistently remain within the millisecond range. Specifically, SLA-to-Intent translation takes approximately 70 ms, while service decomposition requires about 30 ms, in line with KPI7.3. In addition, the generation of the MAS pipeline descriptor takes around 13 ms, and the IML/LNFVO stage spends roughly 121 ms to process service sub-graphs and produce the Kubernetes manifests needed for service instantiation. Overall, the SMO control-plane latency is

negligible compared to execution-layer delays, allowing the system to react quickly to changes in traffic conditions and service requirements. Concerning KPI7.4, the results show that FaaS placement and redundancy decisions are computed within sub-second timescales when the Kubernetes deployment phase is excluded.

Finally, the IML/LNFVO component shows low internal computation and API invocation times, on the order of a few tens of milliseconds. In contrast, the dissemination of control-plane commands to the software-based NFV backend takes around 5 s. As a result, the overall deployment time is mainly dominated by Kubernetes API interactions and the actual pod instantiation process, which typically lasts several seconds depending on the container images used.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D2-W2	Workflow 2 (IML-driven service assurance) Main Test	3	UC3M, ELTE
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
UC3M	Demo 2	DT App, IML (LNFVO), PPV-TM	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the DT service assurance loop under network congestion by measuring the IML reaction time to detect SLA violations and reconfigure the PPV-TM to restore service performance.		
Test requirements	The DT service is pre-deployed and operational (Workflow W1 completed). The IML (LNFVO) is deployed and running. The PPV-TM module and the throughput SLA watchdog service are both active on the Tofino switch. A constrained bottleneck link is configured on the Tofino with a capacity of 600 Mbps.		
External tools	Traffic generator (iperf)		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IML reaction time (from congestion generation to service recovery). 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end (robot-edge) RTT latency and DT application throughput under congestion.
Related Project KPIs	KPI7.1, KPI7.2
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	The RAN is active, and the robot UE is connected to the network. The robot Mini-PC, the Tofino switch, and the edge node are powered on and fully operational, with the DT service already deployed and running (Workflow 1 completed).
Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate background traffic without the DESIRE6G service-assurance loop enabled by emulating 1000 concurrent users from the traffic-generator server toward the edge node, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ one emulated robot flow belonging to the DT service, and ○ 999 background flows associated with a best-effort service with guaranteed minimum bandwidth. ○ The traffic management policies assume a single robot UE in the system. • Observe and evaluate the resulting degradation of DT service performance under the original resource sharing policy. • Repeat the experiment with the DESIRE6G service-assurance loop enabled, activating the PPV-TM with the throughput SLA watchdog function on the Tofino switch. • Measure the IML reaction time required to automatically restore service performance. • Observe and verify that DT service performance remains stable despite the presence of background traffic.
Test results	
DT application degradation under background traffic without DESIRE6G service-assurance	
<p>Figure 92 illustrates DT application performance when background traffic from 1000 concurrent users is injected and the DESIRE6G service-assurance loop is disabled. The figure shows real-time metrics collected at the robot and edge, including RTT latency (top-left), per-flow throughput of the emulated</p>	

users (bottom-left), and DT application traffic exchanged between robot and edge together with the received video frame rate (right). All users operate under a default best-effort policy, with a minimum guaranteed bandwidth of 1 Mbit/s per flow and no service or user prioritization.

Under these conditions, congestion at the Tofino bottleneck leads to a severe degradation of DT application performance. RTT latency between the robot and the edge node rapidly increases to approximately 150 ms, causing loss of synchronization between the physical robot and its virtual replica. At the same time, all data streams experience significant packet loss or complete interruption, leaving the robot unable to detect obstacles and the remote operator without real-time visual feedback, preventing safe autonomous navigation.

FIGURE 92 DT APP PERFORMANCE UNDER NETWORK CONGESTION WITHOUT DESIRE6G SERVICE-ASSURANCE LOOP ENABLED

Service recovery with DESIRE6G assurance and IML reaction time

Figure 93 shows the DT application behaviour when the same background traffic load is applied with the DESIRE6G service-assurance loop enabled. After congestion is detected by the throughput SLA watchdog on the Tofino switch, the IML automatically reconfigures the PPV-TM, enforcing guaranteed bandwidth policies of 90 Mbit/s for the physical robot (as required for mission-critical operation identified in Workflow WO) and the emulated DT robot, while the remaining non-mission critical background users get smaller share from the available resources under the new best-effort policy.

As shown in the figure, DT service performance is quickly restored after policy enforcement. RTT latency remains below 25 ms, with only a brief peak of 80 ms when background traffic is first generated. Video, LiDAR, and robot-state data streams remain stable despite the heavy background load. In addition, the figure clearly shows that the emulated DT robot user (highlighted in blue) is correctly prioritized, consistently receiving its 40 Mbit/s throughput demand.

FIGURE 93 DT APP PERFORMANCE UNDER NETWORK CONGESTION WITH D6G SERVICE-ASSURANCE LOOP ENABLED

The **IML reaction time**, measured from the start of background traffic to successful PPV-TM reconfiguration, averages approximately **900 ms** across 20 runs. Figure 94 presents a representative execution timeline based on timestamped logs from the traffic generator, the SLA watchdog, IML, and PPV-TM modules, showing the sequence of congestion detection, IML notification, and QoS policy enforcement.

FIGURE 94 IML-BASED DT SERVICE ASSURANCE EVENT TIMELINE, FROM CONGESTION DETECTION TO TRAFFIC P (MODULE LOGS)

Test outcome comments

Under background traffic from 1000 concurrent users and without DESIRE6G service assurance, DT application performance degrades significantly, with RTT latency increasing to around 80 ms and complete loss of video and LiDAR streams. When the DESIRE6G assurance loop is enabled, the IML automatically detects policy violation caused by link congestion and recovers the service in under 1 second (~900 ms on average) by reconfiguring the PPV-TM in the Tofino switch via QoS fine-grained API, protecting mission-critical flows of the physical robot and an emulated DT robot against the remaining 999 background users. As a result, real-time performance is restored in the DT application, with RTT maintained below 25 ms and uninterrupted data streams despite heavy congestion.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
D2-W3	Workflow 3 (Multi-domain DLT federation) Main Test	4	UC3M, NUBIS, ELTE, UVA, TID, UPM

Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
UC3M	Demo 2	DT App, DLT Federation, SO, SC, OE, MAS, MLFO, Kafka Monitoring, DL, LNVFO, SDNc, PREOF	Final
Description of the test			
Main function	Evaluate the DLT-based federation capabilities of the SMO, in terms of latency, required to complete a fully automated federation negotiation and execution across three independent administrative domains.		
Test requirements	All three domains are operational and reachable, each running an orchestration layer with the DESIRE6G DLT Federation module. Domain 1 hosts the DT service (Workflow 1 completed) together with MAS, Kafka-based monitoring, and IML. Domain 2 operates a programmable Tofino-based transport network managed by an SDN controller. Domain 3 provides a reachable single-node Kubernetes cluster for application migration. A private Ethereum blockchain is active, with one blockchain node per domain, the Federation Smart Contract deployed, and all domains registered using unique blockchain addresses.		
External tools	stress-injector [28] (Python library) used to artificially load CPU resources of the autonomous-navigation container in order to trigger application-level resource congestion.		
Measurement	Completion time of the two sequential federation requests (Workflow 3, Section 5.5), including the event timeline of interactions between the three domains and the blockchain smart contract during the federation process.		
Related Project KPIs	KPI7.2, KPI7.3, KPI7.4		
Test execution			

<p>Initial setup/assumptions</p>	<p>The Federation Smart Contract is deployed and active on the blockchain network, and all participating domains are registered using unique blockchain addresses. Domain 1 hosts the DT service and continuously monitors application-level resource usage through the MAS and Kafka-based telemetry framework. The programmable transport network in Domain 2, implemented with Tofino switches and managed by an SDN controller, is operational with no forwarding rules preinstalled. In Domain 3, the edge node and its Kubernetes cluster are powered on and ready to host federated application deployments. Pre-established data-plane connectivity exists between Domain 2 and Domain 3.</p>
<p>Steps</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trigger CPU resource saturation on the autonomous-navigation application in Domain 1. • Detect the resulting SLA violation through MAS using Kafka-based telemetry. • Attempt local remediation via the SMO and receive rejection from OE due to insufficient available resources. • Automatically trigger the multi-domain DLT-based federation workflow (Workflow W3). <p>Measure and record all relevant events during the sequential federation interactions across the three domains, covering the complete negotiation and execution lifecycle.</p>
<p>Test results</p>	
<p>Figure 95 shows the network status of the private Ethereum blockchain used for federation, highlighting that one blockchain node is operated by the SMO of each participating domain.</p>	

FIGURE 95 PRIVATE ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN FOR MULTI-DOMAIN FEDERATION

Figure 96 presents the coordinated logs of the MAS, MLFO, and OE modules during the federation decision and reaction phase. When CPU saturation is intentionally introduced in the autonomous-navigation container, the MAS detects the resource congestion by comparing allocated and consumed CPU against a 90% threshold. The alert is forwarded to the MLFO and SO, which first attempt local remediation. The OE then evaluates site availability using live topology information and reports insufficient local resources, prompting the SO to trigger two sequential federation requests to external domains to migrate the affected application with the required networking and compute resources.

FIGURE 96 FEDERATION DECISION AND REACTION LOGS ACROSS MAS AND SMO INSTANCES (DOMAIN#1)

Figure 97 shows the on-chain record of inter-domain federation actions, where all interactions are stored as immutable, time-stamped transactions, providing a verifiable trace of the federation process.

FIGURE 97 FEDERATION INTERACTIONS RECORDED AS IMMUTABLE BLOCKCHAIN TRANSACTIONS

Figure 98 presents the cumulative time required to complete the federation process across all involved domains, averaged over 20 executions. The stacked bars show blockchain-based federation procedures in blue, and in red, the procedures related to deploying the new application instance in the external domain, including data-plane configuration.

The results indicate that the **average federation completion time** – or the time it takes from triggering federation in Domain#1 to restoring end-to-end data-plane connectivity with the migrated application in Domain#3 – is **~31.33 s**. The **dominant contribution (~30.9 s) corresponds to blockchain-related federation procedures**. This is mainly due to the sequential execution of smart contract transactions, including service announcement, bid submission, provider selection, and deployment confirmation. Each transaction undergoes multiple processing stages: it is first locally verified and signed, then

broadcast to peer nodes, included in a proposed block, validated by all nodes through the consensus protocol, and finally committed to the shared ledger as part of a finalized block. This multi-step process introduces the latency observed in the results, **reflecting the cost of achieving a fully automated and verifiable federation agreement**. By contrast, state-of-the-art solutions depend on pre-established agreements, which makes them unsuitable for unexpected and dynamic conditions such as the infrastructure failure considered in our experiments, and they also suffer from significant limitations including manual operations, long setup delays, high overhead costs, and reliance on trusted third parties (see D3.1 [29] for further details).

Importantly, the time overhead introduced by both the blockchain-based federation interactions and the associated deployment procedures (shown in red in Figure) is entirely confined to control-plane operations and does not affect service performance or continuity. Throughout the federation process, the original application instance in the consumer domain remains fully operational while the new instance is deployed and prepared in the provider domain. After deployment is confirmed, the IML in the consumer domain, under instruction from the SMO, performs a short reconfiguration phase lasting approximately 0.43 s. During this phase, the VXLAN interconnection is extended on the robot UE and the edge node, and the forwarding graph is updated to redirect traffic toward the federated instance, enabling a make-before-break transition with no observable service disruption.

Regarding off-chain deployment procedures in the provider domains, Domain#2 incurs the highest configuration time (~5.64 s) due to the setup of the DetNet-PREOF transport service through the SDN controller. This operation requires programming ports and forwarding tables on three Tofino switches using the barefoot runtime API. In contrast, Domain#3 requires ~1.82 s to establish the VXLAN tunnel with Domain#1 and deploy the application in its Kubernetes cluster, involving fewer components and simpler configuration steps.

FIGURE 98 ACCUMULATED FEDERATION TIME ACROSS DOMAINS

FIGURE 99 TIMING VARIABILITY OF FEDERATION EVENTS ACROSS DOMAINS

Figure 99 shows the temporal variance of federation events, obtained by collecting timestamped logs of blockchain transaction submissions and corresponding event notifications at the orchestration layer of each domain. Narrow ticks denote the mean occurrence time of each event, while the coloured

regions indicate their variance. Each event is numbered and labelled in the legend. The results show that the first federation request, associated with DetNet transport connectivity, is completed in ~16 s, while the second request, related to application migration, completes in ~14 s, enabling successful end-to-end service restoration. The maximum observed variance across all federation events is ~2 s, confirming stable and predictable execution of blockchain federation transactions across multiple runs and administrative domains.

Test outcome comments

The average time to complete the federation workflow—comprising two sequential federation requests—is 31.34 s (approximately **15 s per request**). This duration is dominated by blockchain-based federation operations (~30.9 s), which result from the sequential execution of smart-contract transactions for service announcement, bid submission, provider selection, and deployment confirmation. This overhead reflects the cost of achieving a fully automated, verifiable, and zero-trust federation process, in contrast to state-of-the-art federation approaches that typically rely on pre-established, manually negotiated bilateral agreements and are therefore limited to static environments. Importantly, these blockchain-based operations are confined to the control plane and do not impact service operational performance or continuity.

6 Proof of Concepts (PoCs)

In addition to the integrated demonstrations presented in the previous sections, the work carried out in WP5 includes a set of ten Proofs of Concept (PoCs) designed to validate specific architectural features, mechanisms, and enablers that could not be fully integrated into the large-scale demos due to scope, platform, or timing constraints. These PoCs serve as focused experimental validations, each addressing one or more key technical objectives of the DESIRE6G framework.

The PoCs collectively ensure comprehensive coverage of the DESIRE6G architecture across all its layers, from the programmable data plane up to intent-based orchestration. Each PoC contributes a distinct validation target, providing quantitative performance indicators (KPIs) and qualitative insights that directly support the architectural and functional requirements of the project.

Each PoC is explicitly mapped to one or more DESIRE6G architectural pillars, ensuring its coherence with the overall system vision. The results from these PoCs feed back into the design, integration, and optimization loops of the DESIRE6G demonstrators, thereby reinforcing the project's validation methodology.

PoC main objectives, components and KPIs are summarized in Table 15, to provide a clear understanding of their role within DESIRE6G.

TABLE 15 POC SUMMARY

PoC	Title	Goal	DESIRE6G components	Key KPIs
1	Offloading of UPF Functions in BF-3 Smart NIC	Offload UPF packet processing (GTP-U, QoS, SFT) to BF-3 DPU to support large-scale 6G cores with lower CPU load and latency.	Programmable Data Plane (PDP); Physical Infrastructure	Max supported UEs/flows ($\geq 500k$ UEs, $\sim 1.2M$ flows); flow-install latency (median/95p in μs); sustained Mpps / line rate; CPU usage reduction vs SW-only UPF.
2	Intelligent Image Monitoring	Show IML can insert/remove a P4/eBPF QoSControl NF at runtime and quantify impact on an industrial video + robot service.	PDP; Infrastructure Management Layer (IML)	Reconfiguration time; change in throughput, jitter, loss, latency; correctness of stream selection; absence of service interruption.
3	Software Performance Monitoring	Validate binary-embedded monitoring that needs no external tools while keeping overhead low and measurements accurate.	Pervasive Monitoring / Observability; IML support	Accuracy of estimated performance (e.g. $\geq 98-99\%$ vs ground truth); CPU overhead (%); convergence time to stable metrics.

4	SLA-to-Intent Translator	Translate free-text SLAs into machine-readable RDF intents and slice templates consumable by SMO/IBN	Intent-based Orchestration (SMO); IBN	Slice-type classification accuracy; SLO field completeness; retrieval relevance (similarity score); user acceptance rate; intent error rate.
5	CU-UP Offloading	Demonstrate dynamic CU-UP offload to switch/SmartNIC, decreasing latency and host CPU/energy while preserving 5G architecture.	RAN PDP; Optimization & Network Control Layer	Flow allocation time (ms); per-device CU-UP latency (ns/ μ s); CPU power/energy savings (%); share of traffic successfully offloaded.
6	Inter-slice Radio Resource Scheduling	Enable slice-aware TTI-level PRB scheduling via EdgeRIC while keeping 3GPP-compliant intra-slice logic.	RAN & Optimization Layer; RT-RIC integration	Slice SLA satisfaction; PRB utilization/efficiency; inter-slice fairness/isolation; recovery time after load/CQI changes; loop stability.
7	5/6G in a backpack - UPF scaling	Validate both extreme downscaling (backpack 5G) and cloud-native scaling of DESIRE6G P4-based UPF.	Core Network PDP; IML; Physical Infrastructure	Power budget (downscale/scale-up); end-to-end latency and throughput in backpack setup; UPF Mpps vs cores; max services/UEs; CP request rate (UE attach/remove).
8	Hardware-agnostic AI inference offloading for edge robotics	Use vAccel + SOL to offload robot depth-estimation inference to heterogeneous edge HW and meet real-time demands.	AI/Edge Computing; IML, SOL	Inference throughput (FPS) per scenario; improvement factor vs baseline; ability to meet ≥ 5 FPS requirement; throughput stability over time.
9	MAS deployment, attestation and secure communication	Implement secure MAS deployment, DLT-based mutual attestation and key distribution using MLFO + SECaaS.	MAS, SECaaS	Total secure deployment time; per-step times (SC upload, credentials, attestation, key ops); CPU overhead (%); runtime performance penalty (%).
10	SMO scalability	Assess scalability and latency of microservice-based SMO pipeline under many concurrent service requests, focusing on OE scaling	SMO / Intent-based Orchestration	End-to-end processing latency; throughput (req/s); per-component execution time; scaling efficiency with OE replicas; CPU/RAM utilization under load.

6.1 PoC 1 - Offloading of UPF Functions in BF-3 Smart NIC

6.1.1 Goal and KPIs

This PoC explores accelerating User Plane Functions (UPFs) using NVIDIA BlueField-3 DPUs to address 6G requirements for high throughput and low latency. Traditional software-based UPFs face bottlenecks in packet processing and GTP tunnel handling. By leveraging DOCA Flow APIs, this PoC offloads tasks like GTP encapsulation and QoS enforcement to hardware, reducing CPU load and latency. A key innovation is the integration of Stateful Flow Table (SFT) offload, enabling support for over 500K UEs and millions of flows—far beyond Tofino-based solutions. The result is a scalable, high-performance, and flexible UPF architecture for next-generation mobile networks.

The PoC was setup, tested and executed in the ARNO testbed. The components and modules integrated in the PoC are reported in Table 16. The target KPIs are KPI4.5 (“Offloaded in-network computations result in less than 100us response times”) and KPI5.2 (“In-network feature extraction in less than 200us, compared to current >10s time required by external SW features extraction. Off-load to DPUs”).

TABLE 16: COMPONENTS AND MODULES INTEGRATED IN POC 1

System component	Module name	Module ID	Responsible	Project Repository pointer	Zenodo pointer
Network Functions	Offloading to BF-2 and BF-3	4.503	CNIT, NVIDIA	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Acceleration/security-functions-bf2	To be uploaded after Globecom25 acceptance

6.1.2 Implementation

To evaluate the proposed 6GUPF architecture, a realistic testbed on a Dell R760 server with an NVIDIA BF-3 DPU has been implemented, integrating both control- and data-plane functions representative of 6G core deployments. Figure 100 illustrates this setup, which connects a base station emulator to a data centre traffic sink: the setup is aimed to entirely implement 6GUPF architecture inside the BlueField-3 DPU, with no involvement of the host CPU.

FIGURE 100 6G UPF ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN. THIS SETUP DOES NOT INVOLVE CPU AT ALL, ALLOWING FULL DEPLOYMENT ON BF3.

Traffic is generated from the Base Station, which represents the 5G RAN, and is forwarded via the N3 interface as GTP-U encapsulated packets. These packets are injected using an emulated VIAVI/TRex traffic generator, which emulates high-throughput and latency-sensitive mobile traffic over L2 links. At the core of the testbed lies the server equipped with a BF-3 DPU, responsible for the hardware offloading of UPF packet processing workloads. Inside the BF-3 DPU, the DOCA Flow API manages programmable pipelines for flow parsing, GTP-U header encapsulation/decapsulation, and traffic classification. A key component of the system is the SFT for flow tracking, which maintains per-flow metadata to enable intelligent state-aware forwarding at line rate.

Following classification and processing, the decapsulated packets are forwarded over the N6 interface as standard IP traffic to the Data Center, acting as the traffic sink. Traffic sink validation and replay are facilitated via another port of the DPU, which connects to the VIAVI/TRex traffic generators. Traffic is generated with a Gaussian mixture of 70% elephant flows (long-lived) and 30% burst mice flows, calibrated across MTUs from 128B to 1500B. The traffic generator produces a mix of GTP-U and IP packets to simulate real-world 6G network scenarios. This architecture encapsulates a production-realistic deployment scenario where the UPF is embedded directly within the data path of the base station. Packet processing is conducted based on QoS policies, which are dynamically assigned to packets according to their classification and network conditions. High Priority is assigned to packets

requiring minimal delay for network applications. Medium Priority is assigned to packets that require high throughput but are not latency-sensitive. Low Priority is assigned to packets that are less sensitive to latency and throughput.

The DOCA Flow API manages the ingress pipeline with five stages namely ingress classification, QoS assignment, GTP processing, L2 forwarding, and final forwarding. After ingress classification, the DOCA flow checks for QoS. The encapsulation process involves defining programmable tables for TEID-based matching and forwarding. The complete DOCA Flow configuration scripts, including TEID-based match-action pipelines and rule installation routines. This implementation demonstrates that offloading GTP-U processing into the DPU pipeline significantly reduces CPU overhead, lowers packet-processing latency, and enables wire-speed throughput while preserving programmability through a software-managed control plane. This implementation forms the foundation for the performance evaluation that we present in result section.

6.1.3 Test and results

To quantify the performance of flow creation and hardware offloading,

Table 17 summarizes the PoC measurements. The DPU achieves median hardware flow-installation latency of 7.3us, with a 95th percentile of 17 us, demonstrating that DOCA Flow can install flows at microsecond scale even under sustained traffic load. Once installed, subsequent packets hit the DPU's hardware fast path, confirmed via OVS/TC counters and NIC offload statistics. The steady-state flow-arrival rate is approximately 1.2 million flows per second. The observed gaps for max latency correspond to software-based external traffic generator pauses and are not indicative of hardware limitations.

TABLE 17 6G UPF RESULTS

Metric	Observer Value	Notes
Median flow-install latency	2.7 microseconds	From flow_create_latency.csv
95 th percentile latency	16.2 microseconds	Rare slow-path events
Maximum latency	87 microseconds	Upper tail due to SW stalls
Hardware offload activation	Yes	First packet SW → HW fast-path
TEID capacity tested	1.2 million	All flows installed
Ingress RX rate (p0)	104 Mpps	Line-rate at 100/200 GbE
VNF (SF3) processing limit	70 Mpps	ARM/DPDK bottleneck

Table 18 compares existing UPF architectures with our proposed 6GUPF. State-of-the-art CPU- and P4-based UPFs are limited by TCAM/SRAM capacity, typically supporting 100K–400K active flows. Because CPU-based UPFs suffer from TCAM/SRAM limitations because packet classification and flow state must be emulated in cache limited software structures. In contrast, the 6GUPF leverages DRAM-backed state and hardware GTP-U pipelines, enabling approximately 1.2 million active flows, making it one of the highest-capacity UPF architectures reported in the literature.

TABLE 18 6G UPF AGAINST EXISTING ARCHITECTURES

UPF	UEs	SRAM	TCAM	Flows
SD-Fabric	35.8K	34.2%	17.4%	~100K
SD-Fabric-UPF	55.3K	43.3%	4.2%	~150K
HiP4-UPF	159.7K	85.4%	9.7%	~400K
6GUPF (This PoC)	>=500K	45% (DRAM)	N/A	~1200K

It has been demonstrated that BlueField-3 100Gbit/s SmartNIC can sustain 104 Mpps ingress and install up to 1.2 million GTP-U TEID flows with microsecond-scale latency (2.7 μ s median). While the DPU hardware pipeline can forward packets in sub-5 μ s, the dominant limitation was the Scalable Function (SF) VNF path, which saturated at ~70 Mpps due to ARM-core polling and scalable function slow-path overhead. The TEID arrival delay median 3.74 ms, was constrained by the Scapy/Trex traffic generator rather than the DPU pipeline. The arrival of a new TEID means that to the first packet of an unseen GTP-U tunnel, which triggers a one-time slow-path processing on the BlueField-3 CPU to install a hardware flow rule, after which all subsequent packets are handled entirely in the hardware fast path.

The results confirm that the DPU can handle large-scale tunnel state with consistent microsecond flow install latencies, and that throughput bottlenecks originate from the software VNF path rather than the DOCA hardware fast path.

6.2 PoC 2 - Intelligent Image Monitoring

6.2.1 Goal and KPIs

This PoC demonstrates how IML (LNFVO) can reconfigure the data plane pipeline in runtime and shows how the deployment of a custom network function affects the end-to-end performance (throughput,

jitter, loss and latency) and what the cost of the data plane pipeline reconfiguration (time needed) is. The workflow of the PoC and the initial evaluation results have been presented in D5.2.

The system consists of several components:

- 1) a video camera stream emulator server that sends 4 IP camera streams to the Cloud controller.
- 2) a robot emulator server that generates status messages of the emulated robot at a predefined frequency (125Hz). The emulated robot follows a predefined trajectory in an emulated industrial area covered by the 4 IP cameras, as shown in Figure 24.
- 3) a p4-programmable GbE switch based on PCEngines APU hardware with P4-eBPF backend using NIKSS as control plane software. This node executes the robot-state-based camera stream filtering method implemented as a P4 program. The node also offers a simple REST-based stream shaping network exposure API through which robot operators can define rules that describe the importance of camera streams at each robot states (i.e., the position in the industrial area can determine which streams are needed at good quality).
- 4) an industrial controller server that captures the stream and the robot states and evaluates if the required stream quality was provided by the system. This node also loads the monitoring data to influxDB can be visualized on a Grafana dashboard.

The emulated wireless link is between the P4-switch and the cloud-based industrial controller.

6.2.2 Implementation

In the setup, we deploy a simple network service that interconnects two DESIRE6G sites as depicted in Figure 101:

- 1) an industrial environment (D6G microsite) with a P4 programmable gateway switch (PcEngines APU with P4-eBPF/XDP backend), multiple emulated IP cameras and an emulated robot moving in a specific area;
- 2) a cloud site (D6G site) where the industrial controller is deployed on a K8S cluster. The two sites are connected with an emulated constrained/critical link (e.g., a radio link). The capacity of the critical link is varied in the different evaluation scenarios.

In the PoC, we start with a simple service graph that interconnects the emulated devices of industrial site with the industrial controller application function (AF). The initial service does not contain the

QoSControlNF as shown in the figure. The two sites are managed by two IML instances. The PoC show how the service graph can be extended with a new P4-based NF (QoSControl NF) in runtime without service interruption. To this end, we have implemented the software stack for the PcEngines APU hardware that enables the dynamic addition and removal of P4 programs to the data path.

FIGURE 101: UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM DATA PLANE PROCESSING AND THE PHYSICAL SETUP

The developed software stack (see Figure 102) integrates various tools in this PoC: we use the P4RROT code generator to create the P4 code (manually created P4 codes can also be deployed), the P4 compiler (P4C) for eBPF/XDP backend is used to generate the eBPF code (extended with special D6G-Dispatcher metadata to transmit state information between NFs and the dispatcher), libbpf-based eBPF compiler to generate the binary of the NF and the D6G-Dispatcher eBPF/XDP program that manages network function execution and can dynamically load multiple (up to 4) custom eBPF/P4 programs as processing stages. The dispatcher uses the DESIRE6G Gateway (D6GGW) infraNF for executing the local NF forwarding graph and it is bound to different network interfaces (Port 0 and 1 in the figure).

FIGURE 102: DESIRE6G INTEGRATION ON AN EBPF/XDP TARGET

Figure 103 depicts the data path when a custom NF is deployed on the node: (1) The D6G-Dispatcher first receives the packet on Port 0, and then (2) forwards it to the D6GGW that applies Ue2SM to extend the packet with DESIRE6G header if needed and apply the NFR function to forward the packet to the next NF in the execution graph. Instead of the setting the egress port and Ethernet MAC addresses, NFR modifies the D6G-Dispatcher metadata to notify the dispatcher about the forwarding decision. Such decision could be a) egressing the packet on a physical port (i.e., after returning to the dispatcher (3), the packet is sent out on one of the ports) or b) forwarding it to a stage hosting a NF data plane program. After applying NFR, the packet returns to the D6G-Dispatcher (3) that processes the metadata fields and forward it to the first stage (4) where the next NF is running. When the NF is completed, the packet is handed over to the dispatcher (5) again that marks the completion of the NF in a metadata field and directs the traffic to D6GGW (6) for further forwarding decision. After that the packet is sent back to the dispatcher (7) and if no more local NF to be executed, the packet is egressed on one of the ports.

FIGURE 103: DATA PLANE PATH IN AN EBPF/XDP-BASED DESIRE6G NODE

6.2.3 Test and results

Interrupt-free service reconfiguration with D6G-Dispatcher

In the first test scenario, we focus on the runtime reconfiguration of the service, inserting the QoSControl NF into forwarding graph. The QoSControl NF is deployed before the critical link on a PcEngines APU device running the D6G-Dispatcher's software stack.

We first start with the initial setup, where camera streams are not controlled. The number of IP camera streams are gradually increased (up to 135 streams) to show their effect on load, latency and jitter. In this experiment the bottleneck capacity is 500Mbps which is below the offered load. After reaching 400Mbps, IML gets an extended service subgraph containing the QoSControl NF. We assume that the eBPF binary to be loaded is available (e.g., in the image repository). IML loads the NF binary by using the D6G-Dispatcher and then configures the D6GGW with the new NF forwarding rules, but it does not stop the service. All the process is done in operation and in the presence of active traffic flowing through the device.

The measurements show that the deployment of the new NF and the data path reconfiguration do not result in any performance deviations in terms of loss (no loss), delay (<8usec) and jitter (1-2usec). After the activation of the QoSControl NF, the irrelevant video sources are dropped by the NF, significantly reducing the load on the critical inter-site link.

FIGURE 104: EFFECT OF SERVICE RECONFIGURATION ON THROUGHPUT

FIGURE 105: EFFECT OF SERVICE RECONFIGURATION ON DELAY (INGRESS TO EGRESS)

FIGURE 106: EFFECT OF SERVICE RECONFIGURATION ON JITTER (BASED ON INGRESS TO EGRESS DELAY)

Figure 104, Figure 105 and Figure 106 illustrate the scenario. As the number of IP camera streams increases, the throughput demand is linearly increasing as expected. After reaching 400Mbps, we send the updated local NSD to the DESIRE6G microsite. The dashed vertical line represents the point when the QoSControl NF deployment is completed. One can also observe that there is the deployment

process does not affect the throughput performance. After this point, the QoSControl NF starts filtering out non-important packets and the throughput demand drops significantly. We can also see that the service reconfiguration has no visible effect on the experienced delay and jitter. The applied data plane reconfiguration does not block the packet streams. Note that the delay was measured inside the D6G-Dispatcher as the time difference between the packet arrival and egressing on physical ports. A slightly higher delays can only be observed at the beginning of the scenario when the traffic arrives to a “cold” device at the first time.

Scalability and application level KPI measurements

In this scenario, the number of camera streams are set to 100. The QoSControl NF has already been deployed. The critical link is limited to 80 Mbps. The video streams generate more than 100 Mbps load. The cameras are placed along a straight line as depicted in Figure 107.

FIGURE 107: EVALUATION SCENARIO

The robot moves across different zones marked with the different boxes. Each zone is covered by two IP cameras. Thus, at any time two streams need to be delivered with high quality to the industrial controller for decision making, the quality of other streams can be reduced. The rules in the QoSControl NF are configured so that in each area two camera streams are forwarded lossless while for other streams I-frames (key frames of the video) are only forwarded. Figure 108 and Figure 109 show that all the camera streams are kept alive, at the application level we do not experience unintended packet losses (losses that belong to important camera streams needed for decision making in the industrial controller) and the load on the critical link went below the bottleneck capacity (the total load was ~60Mbps). We use the connection aliveness and the unintended loss as application level KPIs in this emulated environment.

FIGURE 108: PER-FLOW THROUGHPUT OF IP CAMERA STREAMS WHEN QOSCONTROL NF IS APPLIED

FIGURE 109: IMPORTANT CAMERA STREAMS DO NOT EXPERIENCE UNINTENDED PACKET DROPS; OTHER STREAMS HAS 10-30% LOSS

6.3 PoC 3 - Software Performance Monitoring

6.3.1 Goal and KPIs

The objective is to explore how self-contained performance monitoring can deliver accurate metrics to assess the execution speed of a software workload in a given environment, without requiring privileged system calls to the operating system or relying on monitoring tools installed on the host. To remove monitoring dependencies, our method consists of inserting timestamps directly inside the workload executable—leveraging `e9patch`—thereby making the software capable of measuring itself.

Our study covers both short-lived workloads (e.g., `Prime()`) and, persistent workloads (e.g., network functions). The latter do not provide a termination point since they never end, which prevents direct measurement of total execution time. Persistent workloads therefore expose a monitoring gap typically filled by specialized performance-monitoring tools (e.g., DPDK for network functions).

Three KPIs guided our work and were used to quantify the relevance of our findings:

Accuracy: the ability to generate trustworthy and precise measurements of overall software performance using metrics collected through integrated monitoring features.

Penalty: the direct CPU cost induced by the monitoring snippets themselves.

Convergence: the time required to obtain reliable and usable reference measurements and to derive a stable performance ratio based on the time series.

About DESIRE6G KPIs, target KPIs KPI6.1 (“Completeness of the security functions including self-authentication, software confidentiality and run-time verification, remote execution monitoring and control leveraging DLT overlay”) and KPI6.4 (“20% maximum average runtime overhead incurred by the composite security compared to non-protected versions of representative sample of each targeted software type as defined in KPI6.3 above”).

Notably, convergence has not been measured and should be considered ancillary or secondary to the first two KPIs. Moreover, these KPIs are not independent or orthogonal—in fact, they are tightly linked. For example, accurate measurement requires sufficient integration time, which impacts convergence. Higher accuracy is obtained through more measurements, which inevitably increases penalty

6.3.2 Implementation

To cover both fixed-lifetime and persistent software, two workbenches were implemented within TSS's infrastructure. Because it is more specific, we designed a dedicated workbench for the L2Fwd network function, driven by the TRex traffic generator, monitored with DPDK, and stressed using worker processes from stress-ng.

FIGURE 110. L2FWD WORKBENCH

6.3.3 Test and results

The following tests and research areas were conducted:

Accuracy of measuring call frequency and execution time at the code-block level. Control-flow graph undecidability and dynamic behaviour introduce biases and errors, because code blocks may be entered or exited midway—not necessarily at their entry or exit points. Timestamping both ends fails in such mid-flow situations.

Performance penalty induced by control-flow-based timestamp insertion. These results led us to significantly restrict timestamp placement and to use modulo-based block sampling when needed, as a monitoring method must not distort the very performance ratio it measures.

Instrumenting the workload's main processing routines, since they capture how often these routines are executed and how long they take—allowing identification of suitable blocks for patching.

Using ultra-long, semantically empty no-op software to capture the CPU-ratio rate effectively, leveraging both call frequency and execution time.

Exploring the relationship between convergence and accuracy when using only a small sample of reference-block metrics in finite-lifetime programs. The measurements made for these different tests and research areas are consequent. A fraction of them, representative to applicable outcomes, is presented below.

6.3.3.1 Accuracy KPI

Workload: l2fwd (infinite-lifetime)

Method: Estimation of packets sent using call frequency. Verify the correlation between the assessed volume and real volume delivered by Trex traffic generator.

This test estimates the number of packets sent by l2fwd using a linear regression model based on the reference block's call frequency, with varying TRex input rates. Accuracy strongly depends on the instruction selected for patching; in this experiment we patched instruction `0x1e66c7`, the first instruction of the packet-processing loop, which provided a reliable proxy for packets sent.

shows the accuracy in the last column (i.e., as a percentage of the real value) of the assessed volume of packets sent (i.e., second column) derived from the call frequency (i.e., first column), compared to what is actually delivered by Trex (i.e., third column).

TABLE 19 SELF CONTAINED MONITORING ACCURACY KPI TABLE

Call Frequency of Ref. Block	Estimated Packets Sent (Based on CF)	Real Packets Sent	% accuracy
916.2827	157658.658	158872	99.24
1045.967	317946.212	319759	99.43
1188.637	502628.440	476540	94.53
1266.602	60724.334	633169	95.91
1398.430	790078.922	790309	99.97
1499.597	935450.279	945336	98.95
1632.435	1133005.943	1114428	98.33
1724.067	1273697.744	1271648	99.84
1814.399	1415922.463	1423574	99.46

The linear regression model demonstrates strong predictive performance across a wide range of TRex input rates. For most data points, the estimated packet counts closely match the real values, achieving accuracy consistently above 98%, with several measurements exceeding 99%. A few mid-range

deviations (~95%) are observed but remain within acceptable bounds considering measurement noise and runtime variability. Overall, the model reliably captures the relationship between block call frequency and packet throughput, validating its usefulness for real-time estimation of l2fwd performance.

6.3.3.2 Penalty KPI

Workload: Prime calculator (finite-lifetime), computing the first 100,000 prime numbers
Method: Assess performance through call frequency of a trampoline set on core routine code. Check the impact of that probing on global performance by measuring the total program execution time. To better assess the accuracy of our method, we add No-Op instructions in the trampoline to augment its impact and verify it. Last, a sampling of the probe activation reduces in due proportion the general impact.

The prime calculator was patched at block `0x1226`, corresponding to the `is_prime` verification loop. Since this loop executes many times, the induced overhead caused by the trampoline shall be low to Table 19 reduce the penalty impact. To illustrate the induced impact, we had injected short trampolines of varying length including 1 to 10 No-Op instructions. By combining an optimized payload (1-10 No-Op instructions in the reference block) with sampling, we obtained an effectively zero performance penalty. The baseline execution time was 0.455128 s.

TABLE 20: SELF-CONTAINED MONITORING PENALTY KPI TABLE

Patched Executable	Time (s)	% penalty
Prime Calculator 10 NOPs Block 0x1226	0.461611	+1.4%
Prime Calculator 1 NOPs Block 0x1226	0.460411	+1.2%
Prime Calculator 10 NOPs Block 0x1226 Modulo 100	0.449311	0%
Prime Calculator 10 NOPs Block 0x1226 Modulo 10	0.449696	0%

Configurations using small or moderate block patching (e.g., 1 or 10 No-OPs at block `0x1226`) show minimal overhead, with penalties of only +1.2% to +1.4%.

More importantly, when sampling with modulo-based block triggers (e.g., modulo 10 or 100), the measured penalty drops to 0%, with no observable slowdown relative to the unmodified executable. These results confirm that the proposed instrumentation approach is highly efficient.

6.4 PoC 4 - SLA-to-Intent Translator

6.4.1 Goal and KPIs

This PoC showcases an SLA-to-Intent translation framework for CSPs that converts free-text customer requirements into actionable 6G Intent-Based Networking intents. A user-friendly UI captures and refines Service Level Objectives (SLOs), while the system extracts keywords, retrieves matching slice templates using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and vector embeddings, and generates intents via one-shot learning. If no predefined slice fits, customers can define new services and SLOs through an enterprise interface. The framework validates the request, identifies the correct slice type (e.g., URLLC), merges requirements with slice KPIs, and finally translates the service definition and SLOs into machine-readable Resource Description Framework (RDF) intents for IBN/SMO consumption.

KPIs to measure (simple examples that match system abilities)

- Classification accuracy: How often the system's top-picked slice (by vector similarity) is the correct one.
- SLO and service details coverage: How many generated SLOs include the needed fields (for example: availability, latency, capacity, reliability, security level, location limits, and business-hour rules).
- Retrieval relevance: The average similarity score (or cosine distance) of the slice templates the system returns, higher means more relevant.
- User confirmation rate: The share of proposed SLOs that users accept without changing.
- Error rate: The share of requests that fail (intent not created or created incorrectly) or produce badly formed SLOs.

6.4.2 Implementation

The architecture components are shown in Figure 111.

FIGURE 111:SLA-TO-INTENT TRANSLATION FRAMEWORK

- Front-end UI:** The UI supports free-text SLA input and provides an SLO Review tab for checking the extracted keywords and matched slice KPIs, as illustrated in Figure 112. The SLA Configuration tab allows users to edit and confirm the service details. An Intent tab shows the RDF intent and lets the user submit it to the IBN system. The Agreement tab presents the SLA appendix, allowing the customer to confirm what was requested and what the CSP understood. This is the final approval step before starting the service request initiation.

FIGURE 112. USER INTERFACE FOR CUSTOMER-DRIVEN SERVICE REQUEST DEFINITION

- **SLA analysis & mapping:** Performs text preprocessing (tokenization and basic NLP), creates a vector embedding of the user request, and uses a RAG step to combine retrieved slice templates and metadata with an LLM (or rule-based logic) to generate candidate SLOs. Manages embeddings and retrieves the best-matching predefined slice templates stored in YAML/JSON.
- **Vector DB (ChromaDB):** An open-source vector database for efficiently storing, managing, and retrieving high-dimensional embeddings.
- **Intent Generator:** After SLO confirmation, creates an RDF-based intent representation and sends it to downstream intent orchestration.

Data: slice definition and related common services (HD Video, AR/VR) for common slice types (e.g., URLLC, eMBB, mMTC), rdf base intent template, SLO metrics for each current slices.

The user-facing UI and APIs were implemented as a lightweight web application and REST endpoints. The frontend uses standard web technologies (HTML, CSS and JavaScript) and a Java component was used for testing/integration on the client side. Backend services are implemented in Python 3.11.6 using Flask to expose RESTful APIs that accept free-text SLA requirements, forward them to the processing pipeline, and return generated SLOs/intents. Embeddings and vector storage are handled with ChromaDB, and the SLA analysis and mapping pipeline tokenizes incoming text, creates embeddings, and retrieves predefined SLA slice characteristics from a YAML source. For understanding user service description, intent generation we leverage the gpt-4o-mini LLM.

6.4.3 Test and results

We tested with a set of free-text SLA requests from different use cases (HD video, low-latency control, massive IoT). Each request had an expected slice type and required KPIs. We measured processing time, collected the generated SLO and intent, and checked if required fields were present and correctly formatted.

To illustrate the process, consider the customer input provided in Listing 1 – Customer Input. This text describes a need for a connectivity service enabling remote control of autonomous capable taxis in Istanbul, with HD video streaming and ultra-low latency requirements. When this input was analyzed using similarity and semantic matching, it achieved a similarity score of 0.85, indicating a strong match with the URLLC (Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication) service class. This score reflects that the

customer's operational requirement, real-time vehicle control with high reliability, aligns closely with URLLC characteristics.

I want to create a connectivity service for Tele-operated Taxi Service in Istanbul. The Drivers at control room (X) can directly control autonomous-capable vehicle. This would require Highly available and ultra-low latent network which can stream HD video from cameras on car to the control room screen.

Listing 1 – Customer Input

This intent has been structured in accordance with the TM Forum Intent Common Model, incorporating Delivery Expectations, Property Expectations, and Reporting Expectations as illustrated Listing 2 – RDF Intent Form of Customer Request. In this example, the Delivery Expectation captures the need for a URLLC resource to support real-time remote vehicle control, while the Property Expectations translate the customer's SLOs such as ultra-low latency for steering responsiveness, high throughput for HD video streaming, and strict availability and packet-loss criteria into measurable conditions. The model also includes a Reporting Expectation that monitors the Tele-operated Taxi Service intent and ensures that any acceptance, rejection, or KPI threshold breach is reported back to the customer, providing full transparency throughout the intent lifecycle.

```
@prefix ex: http://example.org/ .
@prefix icm: http://models.tmforum.org/TIO/v3/IntentCommonModel/ .
@prefix imo: http://models.tmforum.org/TIO/v3/IntentOntology/ .
@prefix log: http://models.tmforum.org/TIO/v3/LogicalOperators/ .
@prefix quan: http://models.tmforum.org/TIO/v3/QuantityOntology/ .
@prefix dct: http://purl.org/dc/terms/ .
@prefix rdf: http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns# .
@prefix rdfs: http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema# .
@prefix xsd: http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema# .
```

```
ex:Tele_operated_Taxi_Service
```

```
  a icm:Intent ;
  rdfs:comment "Tele-operated Taxi Service intent" ;
  imo:intentOwner ex:SLA_to_Intent ;
  icm:layer "SMO" ;
  log:allOf ( ex:E0 ex:E1 ex:E2 )
```

```
ex:LocationInfo
```

```
  a icm:Information ;
  rdfs:label "Geographical location of the slice service" ;
  icm:information "Istanbul"
```

```
ex:T1
```

```
  a icm:Target ;
  icm:chooseFrom ( [ set:resourcesOfType ( ex:URLLC ) ] )
```

```
ex:E0
```

```
  a icm:DeliveryExpectation ;
  icm:target ex:T1 ;
  icm:DeliveryDescription ex:Slice ;
  icm:OrderID "1"
```

```
ex:T2
```

```
  a icm:Target ;
  icm:chooseFrom ( [ set:resourcesOfType ( ex:URLLC ) ] )
```

```
ex:E1
```

```
  a icm:PropertyExpectation ;
  icm:target ex:T2 ;
  log:allOf ( ex:C1 ex:C2 ex:C3 ex:C4 )
```

```
ex:C1
```

```
a icm:Condition ;
rdfs:label "Availability" ;
quan:atLeast [ ex:availability
  [ rdf:value "99.99"^^xsd:decimal ;
    icm:unit80000 "percentage" ]
  ]
.

ex:C2
a icm:Condition ;
rdfs:label "Throughput" ;
quan:atLeast [ ex:throughput
  [ rdf:value "20"^^xsd:decimal ;
    icm:unit80000 "Mbps" ]
  ]
.

ex:C3
a icm:Condition ;
rdfs:label "Latency" ;
quan:atMost [ ex:latency
  [ rdf:value "1"^^xsd:decimal ;
    icm:unit80000 "ms" ]
  ]
.

ex:C4
a icm:Condition ;
rdfs:label "Packet_Loss" ;
quan:atMost [ ex:packet_loss
  [ rdf:value "0.0001"^^xsd:decimal ;
    icm:unit80000 "percentage" ]
  ]
.

ex:T3
a icm:Target ;
rdfs:member ex:Tele_operated_Taxi_Service
.

ex:E2
a icm:ObservationReportingExpectation , iv:ValidityReportingExpectation ;
icm:target ex:T3 ;
icm:reportDestination [ a rdfs:Container ;
  rdfs:member ex:SLA_to_Intent ] ;
icm:reportTriggers [ a rdfs:Container ;
  rdfs:member imo:IntentRejected ;
```

```
rdfs:member imo:IntentAccepted ;  
rdfs:member imo:ThresholdBreach ]
```

Listing 2 – RDF Intent Form of Customer Request

The solution achieved an average template match similarity score of 0.7. Overall SLO completeness was 90%, with most outputs including key KPIs such as availability, latency, and throughput. User acceptance was 80%, while 20% of results required more specification. During intent creation, approximately 70% of intents were generated with accurate content, while the remaining required minor corrections.

The observations show that requests containing clear keywords such as “low latency” or “HD video” resulted in highly accurate template matches, while vague inputs often produced generic SLOs until clarification were added in the UI. We added UI SLA configuration tab lets users clarify each metric easily for low similarity scores to gather missing details and improve accuracy. Some intent templates also had inconsistent field names, and standardizing this improved overall reliability.

The recommendations include expanding and standardizing the template library with clear markings for required and optional KPIs, as well as improving RDF mapping rules to reduce creation errors. Incorporating user edit history can further refine templates over time.

6.5 PoC 5 - CU-UP Offloading

CU-UP Offloading explores the practical feasibility of dynamically offloading CU-UP functions from a host server to heterogeneous programmable data-plane targets – specifically a Tofino switch and a BlueField-2 SmartNIC – within a real O-RAN-compliant testbed. This PoC demonstrates how CU-UP processing can be transparently executed on these hardware accelerators, and how flows can be detected, classified, and steered in real time through a centralized controller and lightweight agents running on each device. The implementation validates the FlexUP idea (see D4.3 section 8 [15]) : that CU-UP functions such as GTP-U processing, Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP) handling, and Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) operations can be executed in the data plane without disrupting the existing 5G architecture, while still respecting each device’s functional and capacity constraints.

The PoC therefore evaluates the practical performance of this offloading approach, how quickly the system can identify a new flow and enforce the decision obtained by solving the corresponding flow-

allocation problem at the FlexUP controller (see D4.3 section 8.2 [15]), how latency is reduced when packets are processed in hardware vs. software, and how host CPU power consumption changes once traffic is shifted to the switch or SmartNIC. The results obtained on the testbed confirm that meaningful benefits can be achieved with the current hardware, motivating the definition of specific goals and KPIs for assessing offloading efficiency, reaction time, and energy savings in an operational environment.

6.5.1 Goal and KPIs

Demonstrate a transparent, topology-independent mechanism that (i) offloads CU-UP functionality to heterogeneous programmable data-plane targets (programmable switch, SmartNIC), (ii) dynamically assigns flows to those targets based on flow needs and device state, and (iii) reduces host CPU load and energy consumption while preserving or improving per-flow latency in a real testbed.

Primary KPIs (measured in the PoC):

- **Allocation time:** We measure the response time from the flow's first packet's arrival, while it is still handled by the legacy CU-UP, until the FlexUP agent completes its placement decision and the corresponding data-plane rules are installed and active. This metric captures how quickly FlexUP can react to new URLLC traffic flows (measured min/max: 21.00 ms / 29.30 ms in the PoC).
- **Per-device CU-UP processing latency:** median/percentiles per device (switch, SmartNIC, CPU). In the PoC the switch data plane latency was measured at ~310 ns vs CPU ~73,000 ns (switch ≈ 99.49% faster).
- **Host CPU power consumption / utilization:** Watts and CPU utilization as a function of offered packet rate (pps) and traffic mix (URLLC/eMBB/mixed). The PoC reports host CPU power consumption curves.
- **Energy savings:** percentage reduction in host CPU power consumption after offloading, relative to the baseline software CU-UP.

6.5.2 Implementation

The PoC implements three logical components: (i) FlexUP agents running on each target (Tofino switch and BlueField-2 SmartNIC) to identify flows and apply/install data-plane processing rules, (ii) a

centralized FlexUP controller (Python, CBC solver and greedy heuristics) that receives flow notifications, runs the decision model and installs rules, and (iii) the legacy CU-UP (software) on the host that acts as the fallback/slow path. The data plane pipeline and agent behaviour are implemented on each device as described below.

FIGURE 113: CU-UP OFFLOADING: FLEXUP IMPLEMENTATION

Switch (Tofino) implementation:

- **P4/TNA pipeline running on a Tofino target.** The switch implements the fast CU-UP data plane features that are feasible in P4: GTP-U encapsulation/decapsulation, SDAP QoS mapping, PDCP sequencing and reordering, deduplication, and rule-based forwarding to selected targets. Encryption/compression are not available on the switch hardware and therefore remain outside the switch offloading scope.
- **Flow identification uses packet headers** (UDP destination port 2152 for GTP-U) and ingress interface; match-action tables and on-switch registers maintain per-flow state and agent lookups. When no rule exists, the packet is forwarded to the traditional CU-UP deployment (CPU) and the controller is notified. See the P4 pipeline diagram in the PoC. See Figure 113.a.

SmartNIC (BlueField-2) implementation:

- **BlueField-2 pipeline built with DPDK + DOCA Flow** for hardware-assisted path plus embedded ARM cores for software processing. The SmartNIC handles SDAP, GTP-U, PDCP sequencing in hardware; more complex tasks (e.g., PDCP reordering, compression, cryptography in this PoC) run on the embedded cores because that BlueField variant lacked crypto HW acceleration. The SmartNIC runs the FlexUP agent to accept/execute controller instructions and to forward to CPU when needed. See Figure 113.b.

Controller & decision logic:

- **Centralized Python controller** implements the allocation decision as an ILP (for small instances with CBC/Gurobi) and a lightweight greedy online heuristic for real-time decisions. The heuristic identifies candidate targets that satisfy functionality/capacity and picks the node minimizing marginal energy or latency cost (depending on the objective). The controller communicates with agents via a lightweight control API to push table entries and to receive periodic status (capacity, energy estimations, flow metadata such as QFI, sequence number, TEID).

Implementation-Level Design Choices:

- Flow detection and the notification message include compact metadata (QFI, sequence number, GTP-U TEID) to let the controller run allocation without payload inspection. The agents use match-action rules + registers to keep per-flow state and to forward packets to the chosen target without involving CPU on the fast path.
- Limitations of each target are encoded in the controller, enabling transparent decisions that respect capability constraints.

6.5.3 Test and results

The PoC was deployed at the testbed described on Section 2.2.5 with two servers, a BlueField-2 SmartNIC and an EdgeCore/Tofino switch; host CU-UP based on simplified srsRAN. While traffic is synthetically generated using TRex [30], packet headers, rates, and timing characteristics emulate DU-originated CU-UP traffic, enabling controlled and repeatable evaluation of offloading behaviour.

Figure 114 presents the allocation time and processing latency for different flows for the three devices. Allocation time includes flow detection, decision-making, and configuration steps and implies the

controller’s reaction time to steer flows away from the CPU. As indicated in the results, in the worst-case scenario, FlexUP completed the decision process in 29.30 ms. Additionally, we compare the CU-UP processing latency across the devices, where the switch, as expected, is up to 99.49% faster than the CPU (310ns vs. 73,000ns), further reinforcing the benefits of intelligent offloading to programmable data plane devices. This confirms that once flows are offloaded in the switch data plane, per-packet latency is orders of magnitude lower.

FIGURE 114: FLOW ALLOCATION TIME

Figure 114 presents the CPU power consumption versus packet rate for URLLC, eMBB, and a 50:50 mixed traffic profiles. The reported CPU power consumption refers exclusively to the host server CPU running the legacy CU-UP. Power consumption increases with the packet rate across all profiles. URLLC consistently consumes the least power as traffic is offloaded to the hardware accelerators, while eMBB exhibits the highest, reflecting greater CPU processing demands.

FIGURE 115: HOST CPU POWER CONSUMPTION

Practical interpretation & applicability. Long-lived or moderate-duration flows (typical eMBB slices or persistent URLLC sessions) benefit greatly because the per-packet processing savings on the switch/SmartNIC amortize controller decision time and enable large CPU energy and latency reductions. The switch is ideal where the required CU-UP features are supported (GTP-U encapsulation/decapsulation, SDAP, PDCP sequencing/reordering), delivering sub-microsecond data plane latency.

Current limitations. The measured 21–29 ms allocation latency implies the controller is not yet viable for steering very short-lived flows. Possible mitigations include (i) pre-provisioning rules for known/QoS-marked flows, (ii) accelerating the control channel or parallelizing the decision pipeline, and (iii) or moving greedy placement logic closer to the agent through a hierarchical decision model.

Furthermore, Tofino lacks encryption and compression support, while the BlueField SmartNIC employed in the PoC does not provide HW crypto acceleration, so cryptographic PDCP functions ran in software. These limitations restrict which flows can be fully offloaded to data-plane targets. The controller enforces functionality constraints to avoid offloading flows that require unsupported features. Looking ahead, as end-to-end encryption becomes prevalent in networks (e.g., QUIC/TLS), it is worth exploring selective or optimized PDCP security processing, while remaining compliant with 3GPP security requirements, to reduce redundant cryptographic overhead for traffic whose payload confidentiality is already ensured end-to-end.

Takeaways. This PoC demonstrates the potential of offloading CU-UP functionality to programmable switches and SmartNICs, to achieve low-latency, energy-efficient flow handling. At the same time, it highlights important practical constraints. The following takeaways summarize the main insights relevant for future system design and deployment.

- **Hybrid placement is essential:** Programmable switches should be preferred for latency-critical flows that do not require cryptographic or compression function. SmartNICs remain the appropriate choice for flows that depend on CU-UP functions such as encryption, compression, while still benefiting from data-plane acceleration (energy savings, low processing latency).
- **Controller reaction time must be reduced:** The measured 21–29 ms allocation latency limits the controller’s ability to steer very short-lived flows. Practical mitigations include (a) prepopulating rules for expected flows or QoS-marked traffic, (b) implement a local (agent) lightweight placement policy for fast decision making and only escalate to central controller for longer-term optimizations.
- **Hardware selection matters:** The PoC revealed constraints arising from missing hardware features: Tofino lacks encryption and compression primitives, while the SmartNIC used lacked on-board crypto acceleration. Selecting hardware with the necessary accelerators is critical when the goal is to offload full CU-UP functionality to the data plane.

6.6 PoC 6 - Inter-slice Radio Resource Scheduling

6.6.1 Goal and KPIs

The objective of PoC 6 is to enable adaptive inter-slice radio resource scheduling on a 5G gNB (Next Generation NodeB) implemented with srsRAN [31] Release 25.04. The inter-slice scheduling framework introduced in D4.3 section 6 [15], formulates the SLA-aware radio resource allocation problem as an OCO (Online Convex Optimization) problem, enabling real-time adaptation to unknown and time-varying traffic demands. The approach operates at TTI (Transmission Time Interval) granularity, dynamically adjusting slice-level PRB (Physical Resource Block) allocations to satisfy SLA constraints under time-varying channel conditions. The focus of the PoC is to validate the proposed inter-slice scheduling approach while preserving the gNB’s intra-slice scheduling logic. To support this, the PoC incorporates the EdgeRIC [32] architecture and extends its RT-E2 [33] (Real-Time E2 interface) telemetry and control interfaces so that they can support slice-level observability and external slice-aware

resource decisions. The EdgeRIC platform provides a baseline RT-E2 interface that exports per-UE (User Equipment) metrics and imports per-UE control actions at every TTI. PoC 6 extends this interface to support inter-slice scheduling by leveraging the existing mapping of UEs to RRM (Radio Resource Management) policies, each identified by an S-NSSAI (Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information). This mapping enables per-UE telemetry to be aggregated per slice and converted into slice-level KPIs. Similarly, the existing per-UE control messages (weights and MCS - Modulation and Coding Scheme - selections) can be used to shape inter-slice PRB distribution without modifying the selected intra-slice scheduler. With this design, the **inter-slice scheduler is implemented as an EdgeRIC μ App**, while the DU continues to enforce all lower-layer mechanisms, such as HARQ (Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request), MCS selection, and resource mapping.

The telemetry emitted each TTI (per UE) includes:

- Current DL TTI index
- CQI (Channel Quality Indicator)
- UL SNR (Uplink Signal-to-Noise Ratio)
- DL and UL buffer occupancy
- TX/RX byte counters (transmitted/received)
- Scheduled DL TBS (Transport Block Size)

These metrics are aggregated per slice to derive slice-level load, throughput, RB usage, and SLA indicators. The control inputs applied each TTI (again per UE):

- A vector of scheduling weights that influence the size of UE-specific PRBs
- Optional MCS that replace the native rate-selection logic

Through these mechanisms, the external controller indirectly shapes the PRB distribution across slices. The primary KPI is slice **SLA satisfaction in terms of throughput**. For each slice and each TTI, the achieved throughput is compared against the effective target rate, defined as the minimum of the instantaneous traffic demand and the configured SLA cap. This KPI captures how accurately each slice tracks its SLA under time-varying load and channel (CQI) conditions.

A second KPI is **PRB utilization and efficiency**. Per slice at TTI granularity, we evaluate the minimum PRB allocation and the aggregate PRB usage relative to the total cell PRB budget. This KPI reflects how efficiently the controller allocates radio resources to meet SLA targets while respecting physical capacity limits and avoiding persistent under-utilization or over-allocation.

A third KPI is **inter-slice fairness and isolation**, derived from the long-term distribution of throughput and PRB allocations across slices, with particular attention for no persistent starvation under high load. The KPI verifies that no slice hogs shared resources and that allocations remain bounded by the PRB budget, preserving slice isolation.

6.6.2 Implementation

The implementation of this PoC builds on the slicing and scheduling abstractions of srsRAN [31], extended with real-time telemetry and control capabilities provided by the EdgeRIC [32] architecture. These extensions enable an external controller to influence both per-UE and inter-slice scheduling behaviour at TTI (Transmission Time Interval) granularity, while preserving all standard 3GPP NR (New Radio) MAC and PHY procedures [34]. The complete system is deployed and evaluated within the Keysight O-RAN Architect platform [10] as part of the JUSNS 6G-Sandbox program.

FIGURE 116 INTEGRATION AND TESTING OF RT-RIC WITH KEYSIGHT O-RAN ARCHITECT (KORA)

In srsRAN, network slices are defined through RRM (Radio Resource Management) policy members, each associated with a PLMN (Public Land Mobile Network), indicating the operator domain, and an S-NSSAI (Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information), identifying the specific network slice. At startup, the gNB forms:

- (i) a dedicated control-plane slice for all SRBs (Signalling Radio Bearers),
- (ii) a default data-plane slice for DRBs (Data Radio Bearers) without a matching policy, and
- (iii) additional slices for each configured RRM policy member.

Each slice is characterized by a minimum PRB allocation, a maximum PRB allocation, and a priority level. These parameters determine the slice's share of cell bandwidth and align with the slice-aware RRM behaviour defined in NR specifications [35].

During each TTI the inter-slice scheduler evaluates which slices are eligible for DL and UL transmission using standard 3GPP timing (including k_0/k_2 offsets [36]), current PRB usage relative to configured limits, priority ordering, and fairness constraints ensuring no slice is persistently starved. Based on these factors, the scheduler assigns each eligible slice a PRB envelope for that TTI. This procedure reflects the 3GPP NR MAC scheduling framework, where slice policies influence high-level resource distribution, but intra-slice decisions remain opaque to the slice abstraction [37].

After inter-slice allocation, the intra-slice scheduler distributes the slice's PRB envelope among its UEs. This component follows standard NR MAC procedures. HARQ (Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request) retransmissions are served first, followed by new transmissions based on the slice's scheduling strategy (e.g., proportional fair). The scheduler then determines MCS (Modulation and Coding Scheme), transport block size, resource-grid placement, and PDCCH (Physical Downlink Control Channel) /PUSCH (Physical Uplink Shared Channel) mapping, while meeting BWP, control-channel, and physical-layer constraints [38]. This intra-slice logic remains unmodified in PoC 6.

To enable external inter-slice control, srsRAN is augmented with the RT-E2 (Real-Time E2 interface) defined by EdgeRIC [32]. At the end of each TTI, the gNB exports a structured telemetry record containing per-UE CQI (Channel Quality Indicator), UL SNR (Uplink Signal-to-Noise Ratio), DL/UL buffer occupancy, transmitted and received byte counters, and the scheduled DL TBS (Transport Block Size). As each UE is linked to a slice via its S-NSSAI, these per-UE metrics can be aggregated into slice-level KPIs such as throughput, PRB usage, and SLA indicators. Before each TTI, the gNB also imports RT-E2 control messages containing UE-specific scheduling-weight vectors and optional MCS overrides. These messages influence the intra-slice scheduler's prioritisation and rate selection, in accordance with standard NR MAC control mechanisms [39].

This PoC extends this RT-E2 interface to allow direct manipulation of the inter-slice scheduler's resource-allocation parameters. Through this extension, an external controller may dynamically adjust each slice's effective minimum PRB, effective maximum PRB, or priority weighting prior to inter-slice scheduling. By doing so, the controller can modulate how aggressively each slice competes for bandwidth during a TTI.

The resulting slice-level resource envelopes are then honoured by the intra-slice scheduler, maintaining complete alignment with standard NR MAC operation while enabling closed-loop slice-aware control.

Validation of this PoC is conducted within the Keysight O-RAN Architect environment [40, 41], as illustrated in Figure 116. Within this platform, Keysight RuSIM emulates both the RU (Radio Unit) and UE PHY/MAC behaviour. RuSIM is orchestrated by Keysight AirMosaic, which generates multiple emulated UEs with configurable mobility patterns, traffic models, and channel-quality trajectories. In parallel, Keysight CuSIM and Keysight CoreSIM emulate the gNB's CU (Central Unit) and the 5G Core Network, respectively, enabling correct UE registration, NAS signalling, PDU session establishment, and slice selection based on S-NSSAI. Operating inside this environment, the extended srsRAN gNB acts as the DU (Distributed Unit) scheduler under test.

6.6.3 Test and results

Experimental Setup. The experiment uses 50 UEs grouped into 5 slices of 10 UEs each, all contending for the same cell bandwidth and configured with identical SLA (throughput of 100 Mbps). UEs experience heterogeneous, time-varying channel conditions configured using AirMosaic. The results presented are obtained by processing per-TTI telemetry from the O-DU collected by the external μ App. Measurements are aligned by TTI index and aggregated from per-UE to per-slice series for throughput, PRB allocations, and CQI statistics.

Traffic Model. UEs establish their traffic sessions sequentially, with a configurable inter-UE session start delay of 1 ms, in addition to the inherent gNB registration and session-setup delays. This delay determines when each UE begins receiving downlink (DL) traffic, leading to a gradual increase in the aggregate offered load. Consequently, the total traffic demand ramps up over time and reaches the configured group rate only after all UEs in the group have become active.

The generated traffic is inherently bursty at TTI granularity due to buffering and scheduling effects. Within the inter-slice scheduler's control loop, slice-level PRB allocations are updated using online gradient descent based on a CQI-driven throughput model, while the per-slice arrival rate is smoothed using an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) to set the dynamic SLA target.

Channel Conditions. Figure 117 depicts channel conditions; UEs experience different CQI distributions in terms of mean and variation, aggregated over slices. These CQI values ultimately determine the spectral efficiency available to each slice and explain why different PRB allocations are required to

achieve comparable throughput levels. *Slice-level CQI aggregation is used here solely for visualization purposes.* In the underlying control model, each slice's traffic demand is computed by summing per-UE traffic demands, while per-UE CQI measurements are retained internally to determine spectral efficiency and the resulting scheduling decisions.

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FIGURE 117 SLICE-LEVEL CQI AGGREGATION SHOWING CHANNEL-QUALITY DYNAMICS

Results. Figure 118 reports the PRB allocations per-slice (minimum) produced by the inter-slice scheduling μ App. Figure 119 shows the corresponding throughput per slice, computed from MAC scheduler counters that accumulate the scheduled transport block sizes (TBS) (or equivalently, scheduled bytes) over a sliding window. The dashed reference lines in Figure 119 indicate the effective target rate, defined as the minimum of the instantaneous demand and the configured SLA cap. As traffic demand ramps up or down due to UE activation or scheduling dynamics, the effective target adapts accordingly.

FIGURE 118 MINIMUM PRB ALLOCATION PER SLICE AT TTI-LEVEL

Across slices, PRB allocations adapt to both traffic demand and channel conditions. PRB usage initially remains close to zero because traffic is introduced gradually: UEs are activated sequentially, causing the offered load to increase over time and resulting in a ramp-up of slice-level PRB allocations. Once all UEs are active, the proposed OCO scheduling approach dynamically adjusts PRB allocations to sustain the target rate under time-varying channel conditions, increasing allocations when CQI degrades and reducing them when channel quality improves. When traffic terminates and buffers drain, demand decreases sharply and the minimum PRB allocations decay back toward zero. The plotted curves apply short sliding-window aggregation over recent TTIs, which smooths both the ramp-up and ramp-down transitions.

During periods of peak demand with unfavorable channel conditions, the sum of per-slice PRB allocations approaches the cell's total capacity of 273 PRBs, indicating operation close to full bandwidth

utilization. Despite simultaneous contention for shared resources, no slice exhibits persistent starvation, and allocations remain bounded by the available PRB budget, thereby preserving slice isolation. Throughput tracks the reference closely despite short-term fluctuations caused by bursty traffic and time-varying channel conditions.

FIGURE 119 THROUGHPUT PER SLICE; REFERENCE IS MINIMUM OF TRAFFIC DEMAND AND SLA TARGET

6.7 PoC 7 – 5/6G in a backpack – UPF scaling

6.7.1 Goal and KPI

Our current 5G networks are fine-tuned for large deployments, it is hard to easily scale the components. Especially the downscaling of the core network seems problematic, which leads to an important question: is it a problem of the technology or “only” a matter of implementation?

The PoC answers this question by using the DESIRE6G infrastructure to scale up/down the UPF network function. For a scale-down extreme we intent to show a 5G in a backpack solution, while for a scale-up exercise we aim to fulfil KPI 7.1 and show our UPF handling 100 services and 1000 users connected to one (or multiple) of those services.

6.7.2 Implementation

The 5/6G in a backpack scenario's setup can be seen on Figure 120. Two relatively low performance laptop devices were used with connection over two software radio boards (USRP B210) connected via RF cables.

The RAN software components and the core control plane were implemented by an external opensource community (OpenAirInterface). The UPF component was implemented in ERI-HU:

- UPF NF-DP (all modules) was implemented in P4 (both v1model, PSA and TNA)
- UPF NF-CP was implemented in C++ using the P4runtime library and the BFRT library for Tofino

The infrastructure components were partially implemented by ELTE and partially by ERI-HU. The latter components were used mainly for scalability testing with a simplified deployment model (using docker compose instead of Kubernetes).

For the scale-up scenario we used an AMD epyc server with 24 physical cores and 48 hyperthreads and an emulated RAN part without real radio devices. Here the UEs were represented as simple pcap traces running on an identical AMD server connected to our system under test with 2x100GbE interfaces.

The internal design of the DESIRE6G UPF can be seen in Figure 121.

FIGURE 120 5/6G IN A BACKPACK POC SETUP

FIGURE 121 UPF INTERNALS

The colour code is the following:

- Yellow: external module which with the UPF has communication interface
- Orange: the NF-CP modules where the external control interfaces are terminated and translated to internal NF-DP logic (e.g., table entries, counters). In this PoC we implemented a fully functional PFCP interface towards the 3GPP SMF (session mgmt. function). The router and firewall controller is a static entity deploying only pre-defined rules.
- Green: the NF-DP modules where actual packet processing take place. In the PoC we implemented a lightweight UPF with the following modules:
 - o GTP handler: decapsulates the UL from or encapsulates the DL traffic into GTP-U tunnels, checks TEID and UE IP address pairs and handles error cases
 - o Charging and QoS: applies per PDU session charging rules, counters and rate limiting. Since in DESIRE6G services are defined as PDU sessions, this means that we support per UE and per service granularity for charging and QoS
 - o Routing and firewall: basic, generic (non-UE-specific) routing and firewall rules
- Purple: the IML proxy layer defined in D2.2 and described in detail in D4.3
- Red: infrastructure network functions (iNFs) responsible for service mapping, NF routing and load balancing as described in D4.3. Note that in the PoC a simplified version of the “load optimizer” is used without heavy-hitter offload.

6.7.3 Test and results

As discussed above in the scalability PoC we tested two scenarios: one corresponded to extreme downscaling, while the other to cloud-native scalability.

6.7.3.1 Extreme downscaling scenario

In the extreme downscaling scenario, our main question was answered: extreme downscaling is indeed possible – naturally with some compromises in performance. The full 5G network stack (gNB, UPF, 3GPP control plane) was running on a laptop in software using real radio boards. Main results:

- Power budget: ~60W
- Used frequency: 20 MHz
- Bandwidth with iperf: ~35 Mbps
- End-to-end latency: average 7-8 msec
 - o Uplink: ~15 msec
 - o Downlink: ~2 msec
- Latency budget can be seen in the following figure (Figure 122).

FIGURE 122 RTT OVER RFSIM IN OAI

It is visible that the most of the RTT budget is used by the uplink radio link. This is not a surprise due to the signalling (grant request) required for access. The rest of the process is rather quick, so we assume that during heavier traffic – when the uplink grants are “always there” this latency can be smaller.

6.7.3.2 Cloud-native scalability scenario

The scalability scenario produced the following results:

- Power budget: ~350W
- UPF user plane performance scaling can be seen in the following table (Table 21).

TABLE 21 UPF SCALING PERFORMANCE

Number of cores	1 service, 1 UE (baseline)	1 service, 100 UEs	100 service, 1000 UEs
1 core	12 kpps	11 kpps	9.2 kpps

2 cores	X	18 kpps	16 kpps
4 cores	X	35 kpps	31 kpps
8 cores	X	64 kpps	61 kpps
16 cores	X	62 kpps	54 kpps

- Control plane performance (Table 22):

TABLE 22 UPF CONTROL PLANE PERFORMANCE

CP Operation	Performance
UE service request	~1700 / sec
UE remove service	~3200 / sec

Note that the results show good scalability, but poor per core performance. The reason is that the tests were made with the `simple_switch_grpc` software running on simple veth interfaces. One can also notice that scalability stops at around 8 cores. The reason for this is that after that the bottleneck moved from the UPF instance to the infrastructure functions, in our case the load optimizer DP, that has to be executed also on multiple cores. This is not hard as it is a stateless function, but it eats up resources from the functions in the service chain.

Note that the control plane scalability was not part of the PoC but could be easily solved as the UPF-CP entity doesn't contain permanent states from the UEs – those reside in the external controllers (in our case the SMF). The UPF CP merely translates SMF messages to the format of the underlying UPF DP modules, so it can easily run as a k8s service with multiple workers.

6.8 PoC 8 - Hardware-agnostic AI inference offloading for edge robotics

6.8.1 Goal and KPI

The main goal of this PoC is to evaluate the integration of the DESIRE6G vAccel and SOL frameworks to support the efficient and transparent execution of AI inference workloads for robotic applications across heterogeneous hardware resources. By leveraging hardware-agnostic AI acceleration, edge computing paradigms, and cloud-native frameworks, this PoC demonstrates how AI inference tasks can be

optimized and offloaded to accelerator-enabled edge infrastructure. This approach allows resource-constrained robotic platforms to satisfy the performance requirements necessary for reliable autonomous operation.

The PoC is implemented, tested, and validated within the 5TONIC testbed.

The components and modules integrated in the PoC are reported in Table 23

System component	Module name	Module ID	Responsible	Project Repository pointer	Zenodo pointer
IML	Enhanced VIM	4.102	NUBIS	https://github.com/nubificus/kata-containers/tree/main%2Bvaccel	https://zenodo.org/uploads/15776449
SMO/IML	SOL server	4.502	NEC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3mes/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Sol_Server	https://zenodo.org/records/14443011

TABLE 23. COMPONENTS AND MODULES INTEGRATED IN POC 8

6.8.2 Implementation

The PoC, illustrated in Figure 123, is implemented on top of the DT robotic system deployed in Demo 2, which serves as the main validation scenario. A computer-vision-based depth-estimation application is integrated on the robot to enhance perception by estimating the distance to surrounding obstacles during autonomous navigation.

The application processes RGB frames acquired from the robot's live webcam and produces a depth map, where each pixel represents the estimated distance to objects in the scene. This depth information can be consumed by other application functions, such as the navigation stack, to enable safe motion planning and obstacle avoidance. To ensure reliable operation the application must maintain a minimum inference throughput of 5 frames per second (FPS), which is sufficient to detect nearby obstacles and allow a mobile quadruped robot—such as the one used in the PoC validation scenario—to stop or adjust its trajectory in time while navigating at low speeds in indoor environments [42, 43].

The baseline depth-estimation model is a monocular neural network implemented using TensorFlow and Keras³. To increase the inference throughput, the model is optimized offline using the DESIRE6G

³ https://keras.io/examples/vision/depth_estimation/

SOL neural-network compiler, producing an accelerated version of the model. The optimized model is then exposed through a containerized agent with the vAccel framework running on the edge node, allowing the application to transparently offload inference execution to different hardware execution environments (CPU or GPU) to meet the performance requirement. The hardware configuration of the edge and robot nodes used in this setup is detailed in Section 2.2.8.

FIGURE 123. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP OF POC 8 FOR HARDWARE-AGNOSTIC AI INFERENCE OFFLOADING IN EDGE ROBOTICS

6.8.3 Test and results

We evaluate the performance of the PoC in terms of AI inference throughput, measured as the rate at which input RGB camera frames are processed and converted into corresponding depth-map outputs. Four experimental scenarios are considered, combining the baseline and SOL-optimized monocular depth-estimation models with different execution environments. Each scenario is executed as a continuous 60-second run to capture steady-state behaviour over time. The resulting frame rates are reported in Figure 124, with each scenario represented by a distinct colour.

Local execution on the robot using the baseline Keras model

In this configuration, inference is performed directly on the robot's Mini-PC, which provides CPU-only compute capabilities. As shown in the figure, this setup achieves a throughput of 2.55 FPS, which is significantly below the minimum functional requirement of 5 FPS.

Local execution on the robot using the SOL-optimized model

Keeping the same hardware configuration, the baseline Keras model is replaced with its SOL-optimized version. This leads to a modest performance gain, increasing throughput to 3.10 FPS. However, this still does not meet the required threshold.

Remote offloading to the edge node with vAccel (CPU execution)

In this scenario, inference is offloaded to the edge node via the vAccel agent, where execution takes place on the CPU. The stronger compute resources improve throughput to 3.52 FPS but still falls short to reach the desired performance level due to the absence of hardware acceleration.

Remote offloading to the edge node with vAccel (GPU execution)

Finally, inference is offloaded to the edge node and executed on the GPU accelerator. This configuration achieves a significant throughput improvement, reaching 8.71 FPS, which supports reliable depth perception for the robot. This results in a **3.41x increase in performance compared to the baseline configuration** (local execution of the unoptimized Keras model on the robot).

FIGURE 124. THROUGHPUT COMPARISON OF DEPTH-ESTIMATION INFERENCE USING KERAS AND SOL-OPTIMIZED MODELS WITH VACCEL EDGE OFFLOADING

6.9 PoC 9 MAS deployment, attestation and secure communication

6.9.1 Goal and KPI

The main goal of this PoC is to implement and validate the secure MAS deployment and initial mutual attestation of MAS agents. This implementation has been achieved by the integration of the MLFO and the SECAAS components which implement the main functionalities validated in this PoC. The components and modules integrated in the PoC are reported in Table 24.

TABLE 24 COMPONENTS AND MODULES INTEGRATED IN POC 9

System component	Module name	Module ID	Responsible	Project Repository pointer	Zenodo pointer
Intelligent Distributed Control, SMO	MLFO	3.007	UPC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/MLFO	Not open source
Intelligent Distributed Control	MAS Agents	3.008	UPC	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/Multi-Flow%20Agent https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/main/Multi-Agent%20System/scripts/RAN%20Agent	Not open source
Intelligent Distributed Control	SECAAS	3.009	TSS	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/desire6g/mainrepo/-/tree/tss_update_30062025/SECaaS_DLT	https://zenodo.org/records/15780450

6.9.2 Implementation

The workflow in Figure 125 shows the deployment of a MAS as part of the deployment of a network service.

FIGURE 125 SECURE MAS DEPLOYMENT AND INITIAL ATTESTATION

Step 1 - Agent deployment

After issuing the deployment to the IML, the SO forwards the final service descriptor back to the MLFO to select the proper agent executables and configuration files for the current deployment (3).

The selected binaries have been previously sent to the SECaaS wrapping service, which parses each agent executable to locate the code section within the binary and computes its cryptographic signature. This signature represents the trusted reference measurement and is securely stored in the wrapper’s internal database for later verification during the attestation phase.

The MLFO searches for the configuration files returned by the SECaaS wrapping service for the selected agents. This file provides the needed configuration for the agents to communicate with the SECaaS during the attestation procedure. The MLFO deploys and configures the agent executables (4).

Step 2 - DLT credential distribution

The MLFO compiles and uploads to the DLT the SC used for the secure key exchange distribution (5). Once the SC is running on the DLT, the MLFO creates credentials for each MAS agent and register them

on the DLT **(6)**. The MLFO distributes the credentials to the MAS agents so they can interact with the SC deployed on the DLT **(7)**.

Step 3 - Initial Remote Mutual Attestation

The MLFO triggers the remote attestation (**Onboarding mode**) on each of the MAS agents **(8)**. Upon activation, the sidecar container, configured using the file previously generated by the SECaaS wrapping service, automatically connects to the DLT network.

When the user initiates an on-demand attestation, the sidecar computes a fresh integrity measurement of its associated agent. To do so, it inspects the agent's process memory, locates the segment corresponding to the executable code, and computes a cryptographic signature over that memory region. This fresh measurement is then transmitted to the DLT network **(9)**.

The DLT, through its smart contract, elects a verifier node – specifically, the verifier that was most recently and successfully attested – to validate the measurement of the agent under verification **(10)**. The verifier retrieves the reference measurement (baseline signature) from the SECaaS database or directly from the DLT and compares it with the new measurement received from the sidecar.

If the two measurements match, the agent's integrity is confirmed; otherwise, the system detects a binary planting attack. The verification result, along with identifiers of the involved entities and a timestamp, is recorded as a blockchain transaction to ensure traceability and non-repudiation. **(11)**

Step 4 - Secure Agent Communication

The MLFO generates a random key for the MAS deployment that will be used to encrypt the communication between the MAS agents. The MLFO uploads the key to the DLT through the deployed SC **(12)**. Once the agent identity is verified and written on the DLT the agent sidecar receives the attestation confirmation and start the execution of the agent **(13)**. The agents receive a notification every time a new key is uploaded to the SC, since keys are created and uploaded by the MLFO periodically. Once the agents receive the notification, they download the new key through the SC **(14)** and encrypts the following messages using the new key.

6.9.3 Test and results

Table 25 summarizes the numerical results obtained related to the workflow execution where every metric has one or more steps associated:

TABLE 25 MAS DEPLOYMENT WORKFLOW METRICS

Metric	Description	Value
Agent deployment (3, 4)	Measured time for the agent deployment and configuration using docker compose	≈ 10 secs
DLT SC upload (5)	Measured time for the SC upload to the DLT	≈ 5 secs
DLT credential creation/distribution (6, 7)	Measured time for the DLT credential creation and distribution	≈ 10 secs
Mutual attestation trigger (8, 9)	Time starting the mutual attestation and for hashing / runtime integrity scan	0.1 - 5 ms
DLT commit and verification (10, 11)	Time for the blockchain to anchor the measurement and verify the measurement	0.5 - 1.5 s
Secure Key Upload (12)	Measured time for the key upload and DLT confirmation	≈ 5 secs
MAS Agents key retrieval (14)	Measured time for the agents to retrieve the key	≈ 100-150 ms
TOTAL Secure MAS deployment	Measured time for the execution of the whole workflow	≈ 30 secs

Note that majority of the time is spent on the Docker Compose agent deployment and the interaction with the DLT. These two factors highly depend on the hardware where the agents and the DLT is deployed as well as the Ethereum implementation used as described in 2.2.9. Better optimized DLT implementations and more computation resources should highly reduce the time spent to run the entire workflow. Moreover, the deployment of the MAS can be run in parallel with the deployment of the network service itself, greatly reducing the amount of time spent during the deployment phase. Figure 126 and Figure 127 captures show the times and the log output of the MLFO and MAS Agent.

```

18:22:57.927 Received request to create new MAS for service: svc1
18:22:57.927 Configuring agents...
18:23:07.953 Deploying contract MasContract for NS svc1
18:23:12.050 Contract MasContract deployed at address 0x29564050352FDECDFeB430837575219c4a50FED2
18:23:22.153 Selected agent addresses registered:
18:23:22.154 Agent agent1 with address : 0x53E2f970ECC4A5D269F1f3E7fd54D1C8bFCAa504 registered.
18:23:22.154 Agent agent2 with address : 0xFee9eAb121938caBF66f2C0113B0F3c0B0Aeff9b registered.
18:23:27.181 New secret key b'iYVRpBwkrNx7Q_0eSCfaDgIKrijQhCxJH5bhcbkGJ30=' set on DLT for NS: svc1

```

FIGURE 126 MLFO LOGGING

```
18:23:27.326 New secret key b'iYVRpBwkrNx7Q_0eSCfaDglKrijQhCxJH5bhcbkGJ30=' set on DLT by MLFO
```

FIGURE 127 MAS AGENT LOGGING

TABLE 26 SECAAS OVERHEAD MEASUREMENTS

Metric	Description	Value
CPU Overhead	Additional CPU load on the agent / sidecar	< 1%
Agent duration W/Wo Attestation	Performance penalty with runtime integrity verification	< 1%

Table 26 summarizes the numerical results obtained related to the overhead introduced to the MAS by the SECaaS.

6.10 PoC 10 SMO scalability

6.10.1 Goal and KPI

The main goal of this PoC is to evaluate the scalability and performance of the DESIRE6G microservice-based Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) architecture when processing service instantiation requests. The PoC focuses on the internal SMO pipeline – from initial request ingestion to the generation of the optimized Service Graph – prior to its transmission to the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML). To isolate and quantify the internal behaviour of the SMO, the IML endpoint is mocked, enabling controlled performance analysis without introducing downstream variability.

This PoC aims to validate that the SMO can efficiently process large numbers of concurrent service requests while maintaining stable end-to-end latency, predictable orchestration performance, and balanced resource utilization across its microservices. Special attention is given to the Optimization Engine (OE), which constitutes the computational hotspot of the pipeline. The PoC evaluates the responsiveness and throughput of the SMO as the OE is scaled horizontally.

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) examined in this PoC include:

- End-to-end SMO processing latency per request.
- Per-component execution time, with emphasis on the SO, Topology Module, Catalog, and OE.
- Scalability efficiency when increasing the number of OE instances.
- Throughput, defined as the number of service requests processed per second.
- Resource utilization across SMO microservices under increasing load.

These KPIs collectively demonstrate the SMO's ability to support high-demand 6G service orchestration scenarios.

6.10.2 Implementation

FIGURE 128: SMO SCALABILITY POC HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW

The PoC, illustrated in Figure 128, is implemented on top of the DESIRE6G SMO prototype deployed within a container-based testbed (docker-compose). The SMO is composed of containerized microservices that communicate through lightweight REST interfaces and a message bus (main communication between the SO and the OE). The core components involved in this PoC include:

- Service Orchestrator (SO): Receives the initial service request, performs request validation, retrieves service templates from the Service Catalog, and coordinates the processing workflow.

- Topology Module: Enriches the service description with infrastructure information, available resources, and policy constraints.
- Service Catalog: Provides the required service templates and descriptors used during orchestration.
- Optimization Engine (OE): Performs resource allocation, placement, and constraint satisfaction; it is the most computationally demanding component and is the primary scalability focus of this PoC.
- Mocked IML Interface: Acts as the termination point of the SMO pipeline, receiving the optimized Service Graph without executing further processing.

FIGURE 129: SERVICE INSTANTIATION PIPELINE (ANNOTATED TIMING HOOKS)

Each SMO module is instrumented with fine-grained timing hooks and resource metrics to capture execution behaviour under different scaling and load conditions.

The PoC evaluates the SMO as the OE is scaled horizontally using docker-compose replicas with $N = 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32$ instances. We issue 2048 service instantiation requests to the SO. The internal timing of all SMO components is recorded and aggregated across 500 execution samples to ensure statistical reliability.

6.10.3 Test and results

For the proof-of-concept, the SMO scalability is quantified by varying both the number of OE workers and the level of SO concurrency, while measuring latency, throughput, and CPU utilization across 500 samples per configuration and 2048 requests per run.

SMO sequence and timing: The sequence diagram (Figure 129) shows that the measured SMO response time is the sum of SC processing (on the order of **3–5 ms**), MQ transfer plus OE stages (ranging from about **140 ms** with many workers to over **500 ms** with a single worker), and deployment/IML interaction (roughly **40–60 ms** depending on load). These quantified timings confirm that horizontal scaling of the OE primarily reduces the MQ+OE segment, which is the dominant contributor to end-to-end SMO latency under load.

FIGURE 130: SCALABILITY VS THREADS (IN-FLIGHT REQUESTS)

Scalability vs threads (Figure 130): With 1 SO thread the average SMO latency is about **38 ms**, dominated by roughly **30 ms** of MQ+OE overhead and only a few milliseconds in SC, deployment, and internal OE processing. Increasing to 32 threads pushes the average latency to about **562 ms**, with MQ+OE overhead alone accounting for around **520–530 ms**, indicating that queuing and OE contention become the main bottlenecks under high concurrency.

FIGURE 131: LATENCY BREAKDOWN VS NUMBER OF OE WORKERS

Latency breakdown with throughput (Figure 131). : For a single OE worker, total latency per request is around **270–280 ms**, and the system sustains roughly **24 req/s**; the MQ component contributes more than **200 ms** of this delay. With 32 OE workers, the total latency per request drops to about **120–130 ms**, while throughput increases to about **120–125 req/s**, showing nearly a **5x** throughput improvement and more than **2x** latency reduction as the OE is scaled out.

FIGURE 132: CPU UTILIZATION PER COMPONENT VS IN-FLIGHT REQUESTS

CPU utilization and latency (Figure 132): At 1 SO thread the total CPU utilization across SMO components is about **20%**, and the average latency is around **40 ms**, staying within a **20-60 ms** min-max band. At 32 threads, CPU utilization reaches roughly **32-33%** (with the Service Orchestrator alone using around **15-16%**), and the average latency climbs to about **560-570 ms** with a wide spread (roughly **80-650 ms**), while throughput increases from about **24 req/s** to **56 req/s**.

FIGURE 133: LATENCY VS OE WORKERS FOR VARIABLE IN-FLIGHT REQUESTS

Latency vs OE workers (Figure 133): With **1** OE worker, the average end-to-end SMO latency is about **562 ms**, of which roughly **500 ms** is MQ+OE overhead, and less than **70 ms** is due to SC, deployment, and internal OE logic. Scaling to **32** OE workers reduces the average latency to around **217 ms**, cutting MQ+OE overhead by more than half (to roughly **140-150 ms**) and yielding an overall **2.6x** improvement in response time compared to the single-worker baseline. Throughput climbs to **138 req/s** when scaling to more than 16 Optimization Engine instances and keeping more than 16 parallel requests in-flight.

7 KPIs Conformance Analysis and Lessons Learnt

This section presents the conformance analysis of the KPIs defined for the DESIRE6G use cases described in D2.1. It summarizes the performance achieved across the Augmented Reality, Digital Twin, and Image Monitoring demonstrations, focusing on latency, bandwidth, reliability, scalability, and automation capabilities. Moreover, the section provides the conformance analysis of the DESIRE6G KPI with focus on Objective 7 related to integration and demonstration. The section also exposes other technical KPIs met by demonstrators and PoC, the level of KPI fulfilment in large-scale device handling, fully automated service management, AI-driven decision making, and serverless function orchestration. Finally, it outlines the main lessons learned that will inform the evolution of the DESIRE6G architecture.

7.1 Use cases KPIs

This section reports the conformance analysis of the use case KPIs discussed in WP2 during the requirements survey and identified in D2.1 [7]. These KPI are related to the requirements of the applications related to the considered use cases, developed and utilized in the DESIRE6G demonstrators. The goal is to validate the performance requirements of the applications provided by the DESIRE6G integrated architecture. As clarified in D2.2, these KPIs are not intended to be entirely targeted by the project. However, they represent a target to guarantee the full use case applicability. The analysis carried out in the following tables describes the use case KPI achievements in the DESIRE6G demonstrators, specifically Demo1 (Augmented Reality use case), Demo 2 (Digital Twin use case) and PoC3 (Image Monitoring industrial use case).

7.1.1 Augmented Reality (Demo1)

AR/VR use case KPIs	
KPI1 - E2E latency: 5ms for the network, <20ms total (ideal), <50 ms total (tolerated)	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The network one-way e2e latency of the AR app is around 10ms, mainly due to the RAN segment (5G UE + wireless link + gNB). Additional latency is experienced in the application pods. This latency fully enables interactive quality of experience required by AR services. The main bottlenecks are the AI latency experienced inside the app pods and the

	RAN latency. The rest of the latency contribution is negligible, including the DESIRE6G NFs with different backends (BMv2, NIKSS, Tofino).
KPI2 - Bandwidth (per-flow): 50-100Mbps (uplink), 130Mbps-960Mbps (downlink)	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	20 Mbps are more than enough to support bidirectional AR application services, since video streaming resorts to effective compression techniques. Demo 1 supports 50Mbps uplink and 100Mbps downlink using a dedicated TDD slot. AR quality of experience is achieved.
KPI3 - Reliability: 99%	
Status	Comment
N/A	Reliability has not been measured. The focus of the demo is on latency assurance. Reliability would imply completely different measurement set, including RAN packet loss, application packet loss, network packet loss in the case of congestion, anomaly throughput and hard failures.
KPI4 - Scalability. Number of drones per service: 1/10. Number of users per service: 100	
Status	Comment
N/A	Scalability has not been evaluated from the point of view of the AR application. However, 10-20Mb/s is required for each uplink transmission from the drone to the end-user, mainly impacting the RAN. Additional scalability issue may reside on the edge cluster resources. The SDN network including the DESIRE6G network functions are not impacted by scalability, provided that aggregation is enforced for all flows and services requiring similar packet treatment.

7.1.2 Digital Twin (Demo2)

DT use case KPIs	
KPI1 - E2E latency: 1-100 ms	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	End-to-end latency requirements for robotic Digital Twin systems depend on the specific task and the timing constraints of the control loop, as described in D2.1 [7]. In Demo 2, a quadruped mobile robot performs autonomous navigation using algorithms executed at the

	<p>edge. The most latency-sensitive flows are the downstream velocity commands from the edge to the robot, which directly control its high-level motion. The control loop runs with a 20 ms period, requiring timely delivery within this window for safe and stable movement. Measured one-way network latency between the robot and the edge node is around 8 ms, with peaks below 15 ms mainly due to the wireless access. These values are well within the control-loop budget, confirming that the network fully supports real-time operation in the validated scenario.</p>
KPI2 - Bandwidth: 1-1000 Mbps	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>Similarly to latency, bandwidth requirements depend on the sensors and data streams involved. In the validated scenario, the uplink traffic is around 90 Mbps, including video streaming (~85 Mbps), LiDAR data (~3.5 Mbps), and robot state information such as odometry, joint states and IMU (~1.5 Mbps). Downlink traffic, consisting of velocity control commands, remains below 1 Mbps. Although video dominates the uplink, it is not critical for real-time operation and could be compressed if necessary. Demo 2 supports uplink and downlink rates of 250 Mbps and 800 Mbps respectively, meeting the bandwidth demands of the robotic DT system.</p>
KPI3 - Reliability: 99.999%	
Status	Comment
N/A	<p>Reliability was not measured. A proper evaluation would require long-duration experiments and controlled fault scenarios (e.g., packet loss, link failures, component restarts) across the programmable data plane and application layers, which were outside the scope of Demo 2.</p>
KPI3 - Availability: 99.999% to 99.999999%	
Status	Comment
N/A	<p>Service availability was not quantitatively evaluated, as it requires long-duration experiments including failure and recovery scenarios, which were beyond the scope Demo 2.</p>
KPI4 - Scalability. 1-50 nodes	
Status	Comment

N/A	Scalability in terms of the number of DT application instances or robots was not directly evaluated, as the demonstrator focuses on a single DT application controlling one physical robot due to hardware limitations. However, scalability aspects were partially explored by emulating traffic from 1000 concurrent devices at the data plane, without impacting DT application performance.
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7.1.3 Image Monitoring (PoC2)

Image Monitoring use case KPIs	
KPI1 - Reliability - Sensor data: 99% Depending on the reporting frequency of sensors. Fast real-time reaction to changes in the system states requires in-time information for quality control.	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The QoSControl NF processes the robot's state messages in less than 10 usec, enabling ultrafast reaction to changes in the system state
KPI2 - Reliability - Camera streams: Depending on the applied video encoding. In H264 and H265, 98-99% when high quality video is needed, but the transmission of I-frames is required for keeping the connection alive.	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The IP cameras are emulated with H264 encoded RTP streams. In the scenario we scaled up the number of concurrent streams. After applying the QoSControl NF, all the connections have remained alive. The method also resulted in zero unintended packet drops, thus providing high quality streams when they were needed.
KPI3 - Availability: 99.9999%	
Status	Comment
N/A	We only validated the method in laboratory environment. Providing real availability measures may requires real world deployment and long-term operational experiences.

KPI3 - Data Rate: 10-50Mbps per active camera	
Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	The method's performance is only affected by the total traffic load and the total number of cameras. In the measurements the throughput demand of each camera stream was around 2-5 Mbps, but the method itself can easily work with larger per camera data rates
KPI4 - Scalability: 1-50 IP cameras at an industrial site	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	In the evaluation, we varied the number of IP cameras from 5 to 135. The QoSControl NF's performance was not affected by the number of cameras in the investigated range.

The use case also required low latency processing. In PoC2, we have shown that the processing of robot state and camera streams takes less than 10 usec, enabling the real-time decision making.

7.2 Project KPI

This section reports the conformance analysis of the project KPIs related to the integrated demonstrations and the PoC. Objective 7 KPI are reported and analyzed with respect to the workflow results of the demonstrations and specific aspects of the PoCs, as reported in the previous section. Moreover, specific KPI from different objectives related to technical work packages (i.e., WP3 and WP4) are analyzed based on PoC final results.

7.2.1 Objective 7 KPIs

Obj 7: To integrate components and to build PoC demonstrators validating the whole architecture	
KPI7.1: >1000 real/emulated devices, simultaneously requiring > 100 heterogeneous realistic services (including ultra-low latency-bounded services).	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	Demo1/PoC10: Partially fulfilled. PoC10 validates sub-second service orchestration on Demo1 NSG: more than 1000 (2048) concurrent service instantiation requests are being deployed to the Southbound interface (IML) in average 200ms per request, by scaling the Optimization Engine to 16 instances.

	<p>Demo 2: Partially fulfilled. The demo validates traffic management under concurrent load from more than 1000 emulated devices. Using the Per-Packet Value Traffic Management framework, DT service traffic from the physical robot and a second emulated robot was successfully prioritized with guaranteed throughput, while the remaining 999 users were served under a best-effort policy. This demonstrates effective service differentiation and scalability under high concurrency.</p> <p>PoC 7: Fulfilled. The PoC was configuring 100 services and 1000 users for the scalable UPF.</p> <p>The combination of the three results confirms KPI fulfillment.</p>
<p>KPI7.2: all services handled with no manual intervention, including creation and suppression, based on the defined MAS system, with knowledge transfer among MAS for perceived infinite capacity.</p>	
Status	Comment
<p>Fulfilled</p>	<p>Demo 1: Fulfilled. Deployed services are handled with any manual intervention. Different assurance loops are validated, showing the capability of the system to automatically react to SLA anomalies (e.g., latency, packet loss) thanks to the automatic intervention of the different layers: data plane programmability and control (demo 1, W3), IML at single site with the collaboration of Kafka monitoring and forecasting engine (demo 1, W4), MAS multi-site service level assurance (demo 1, W3 and W5).</p> <p>SMO-based deployment time contribution is in the order of 46ms (confirming KPI3.3 – “<1s automatic resource selection and network programmability to validate the required workflows entailing the orchestration and control functions, and the defined interfaces”).</p> <p>Demo 2: Fulfilled. The DT service is deployed, managed, assured, and federated without manual intervention. Service deployment is fully automated and completed in ~234 ms, with the SMO contributing ~115 ms, confirming KPI3.3 (<1s automatic resource selection and network programmability to validate the required workflows entailing the orchestration and control functions, and the defined interfaces). The service-assurance loop is validated at the IML layer, which automatically detects data-plane congestion caused by a sudden load of 1000</p>

	<p>emulated users and restores service performance by reprogramming the traffic manager in the programmable Tofino switch within ~0.9 s. In addition, two fully automated federation agreements are negotiated and executed across three independent domains in ~31 s (~15 s per request), addressing an unexpected infrastructure congestion event, thereby confirming KPI2.3 (<1s automatic resource selection and network programmability to validate the required workflows entailing the orchestration and control functions, and the defined interfaces) and KPI2.4 (Achieve a lightweight DLT-based federation of two domains in less than 30 seconds).</p> <p>PoC 9: Fulfilled. full secure MAS system deployment and remote attestation procedure validated.</p>
<p>KPI7.3: <100ms AI-driven decision making (leveraging on appropriate HW acceleration) and re-optimization, guaranteeing the defined KQIs, including end-to-end latency from terminal to edge under varying traffic and service conditions.</p>	
<p>Status</p>	<p>Comment</p>
<p>Fulfilled</p>	<p>Demo 1: Fulfilled. All the AI-decision making and re-optimization have been successfully tested and validated. In the deployment, service decomposition by the OE takes less than 30ms to decompose latency-constrained AR service graphs in three sites. The distributed MAS is able to detect anomalies, always against the end-to-end SLA requirement (e.g., latency), and take different re-optimization decisions based on anomaly localization, type of anomaly, and availability of recovery mechanisms in the different segments of the network. All the experiments show the capability of the MAS to react in less than 30ms, always below 100ms. Full re-optimization enforcement time strictly depends on the data plane technology. SDN rerouting and flow rule assignment is fast (order of tens of milliseconds), while other enforcement mechanisms may take longer time (e.g., RAN Handover triggered by the xApp).</p> <p>Demo 2: Fulfilled. AI-driven decision making is validated during service deployment and federation workflows. In the DT service deployment (W1), the Optimization Engine performs service decomposition for a latency-constrained service graph in approximately 30 ms. In the</p>

	<p>federation workflow (W3), upon detection of an SLA anomaly reported to the SMO via the MAS and infrastructure monitoring, the Optimization Engine executes a re-optimization decision and identifies the need for service federation due to insufficient local resources.</p>
<p>KPI7.4: Dynamic serverless function placement with function redundancy and replication, and topology reconfiguration for application resilience with perceived zero-latency, in the sub-second scale.</p>	
<p>Status</p>	<p>Comment</p>
<p>Fulfilled</p>	<p>Demo 1: Fulfilled. Results demonstrate that Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) placement, redundancy selection, and replication decisions are computed by the SMO framework within sub-second timescales, when considering the control-plane and decision-making phases only. This confirms that the latency associated with FaaS placement and resilience decisions is independent of the underlying Kubernetes execution mechanisms. As a result, resilience-aware placement and reconfiguration actions are taken immediately from a control-plane perspective, enabling perceived zero-latency adaptation at the application level.</p> <p>Topology reconfiguration (i.e., FaaS scaling) due to IML-based service assurance, in collaboration with Kafka Monitoring and Forecasting Engine, was validated.</p> <p>Less than 300ms for overall scaling operation was measured (W4).</p> <p>Demo 2: Fulfilled. Dynamic serverless function placement and resilience are validated at control-plane timescales. The SMO computes function placement, redundancy, and replication decisions within sub-second latency, independent of Kubernetes execution delays. During the federation workflow, the SMO coordinates the migration of a DT application function to an external domain and, once the federation agreement is established, instructs the IML to update the forwarding graph using a make-before-break approach. The original instance remains active until the federated instance is deployed and verified, enabling seamless topology reconfiguration and perceived zero-latency adaptation at the application level.</p>

7.2.2 Other technical KPIs

KPI3.3: <1s (depending on the involved elements) automatic resource selection and network programmability to validate the required workflows entailing the orchestration and control functions, and the defined interfaces.	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>Demo1: Fulfilled.</p> <p>Demo 2: Fulfilled.</p> <p>PoC10: Fulfilled.</p> <p>In all the considered demos/PoC, the overall time due to orchestration/control plane functions and interfaces related to the D6G architecture is always below 1 second.</p>
KPI4.5: Offloaded in-network computations result in less than 100usec response times	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>PoC1: Fulfilled. Offloading control-plane and data-plane operations to the DPU achieves microsecond-scale response times. Median hardware flow-install latency ranges from 2.7-7.3 μs, with 95th percentile below 17 μs and a worst-case of 87 μs, remaining well under the 100 μs KPI threshold. Once installed, packets are processed entirely in the DPU hardware fast path with sub-5 μs forwarding latency. Observed maximum outliers are attributable to external software traffic generator stalls, not hardware limitations. This confirms that in-network computation offload to the DPU satisfies the latency KPI under sustained high load.</p> <p>PoC5: Partially Fulfilled. While the offloading decision takes tens of ms (non-optimized controller), once CU-UP is offloaded on the programmable switch, CU-UP latency is 99.49% faster than CPU, reaching 310ns hop latency, further reinforcing the benefits of intelligent offloading to programmable data plane devices.</p>
KPI5.1: Iteration between DU control loops for managing resources between services	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>PoC6: Fulfilled. We demonstrated an iterative DU-level control loop for inter-slice radio resource management. The proposed inter-slice scheduling approach is continuously adapting PRB allocations based</p>

	on real-time telemetry reflecting service demand and performance. Leveraging a Real-Time Intelligent Controller (EdgeRIC), control-loop iterations operate at TTI granularity, enabling dynamic resource sharing between services and ensuring that service-level requirements are met under varying traffic conditions.
KPI5.2: In-network feature extraction in less than 200 μ s, compared to current >10s time required by external SW features extraction. Off-load to DPUs.	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	PoC1: Fulfilled. In-network state handling and feature-related processing, triggered on first-packet arrival of a new TEID, complete within tens of microseconds. Hardware-assisted GTP-U flow installation and DRAM-backed state enable scalable and timely feature availability, even at ~1.2 million active flows. This validates that DPU-based in-network feature extraction comfortably meets the 200 μ s KPI.
KPI5.5: Transparent acceleration of AI algorithms without SW adaptation for widely used AI frameworks.	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	PoC8: Fulfilled. AI inference acceleration is achieved transparently using the vAccel and SOL frameworks, without requiring modifications to the robot-side application or the TensorFlow/Keras model.
KPI5.7: >50% inference latency reduction for AI algorithm optimizations and 5-10x overall throughput increase.	
Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	PoC8: Partially Fulfilled. Inference latency is measured per frame, with performance reported in frames per second (FPS), a standard throughput metric for AI workloads with fixed input sizes, where FPS is the inverse of per-inference latency. The baseline configuration achieves 2.55 FPS (\approx 392 ms per inference), while SOL optimization with vAccel GPU offloading reaches 8.71 FPS (\approx 115 ms per inference), corresponding to a latency reduction well above 50% and an overall throughput improvement of approximately 3.4x.
KPI6.1: Completeness of the security functions including self-authentication, software confidentiality and run-time verification, remote execution monitoring and control leveraging DLT overlay	

Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	<p>PoC3: Partially Fulfilled. This PoC demonstrated several outcomes by introducing reference code blocks to assess (i) speed-marking call frequency as a direct indicator of software execution speed and (ii) actual CPU load derived from the workload. As shown in our self-contained performance-monitoring video, achieving sufficient measurement accuracy with low overhead proved challenging, which ultimately shaped the results presented in this PoC. Consequently, the effort focused on performance validation, leaving no time to integrate the DLT, whose use is therefore limited to Demo 1 and PoC 9 for integrity verification.</p> <p>PoC9: Partially Fulfilled. This KPI is partially met by this PoC, which illustrates how the DLT directly orchestrates remote attestation and execution control. The other security functions have been covered separately in the project, Demo1 and PoC3.</p>
<p>KPI6.4: 20% maximum average runtime overhead incurred by the composite security compared to non-protected versions of representative sample of each targeted software type as defined in KPI6.3 above. 0% increase of the one-time authentication complete cycle of the self-contained authentication novel scheme compared to TPM based authentication (given in the range of 500 msec for reference).</p>	
Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	<p>PoC3: Fulfilled. The PoC demonstrated that the impact of performance monitoring, when duly applied, can be insignificant as illustrated in the KPI penalty. Therefore, the 20 % overall performance penalty covering all runtime measures of integrity verification and execution monitoring can be satisfied.</p> <p>PoC9: Partially fulfilled. The remote attestation cycle depending on the DLT has shown to be higher than the 500 msec given for reference. However, it is worth stating that Demo1, illustrating how the DLT also bring continuous runtime integrity verification, enables to cancel remote attestation at on-boarding with an Attest-After-Starting method, enabling an instant start of time sensitive workloads.</p>

7.3 Lessons learnt

The experimental activities reported in D5.3 provide a comprehensive validation of the DESIRE6G architecture under realistic, multi-domain conditions. Beyond individual performance results, the integration, validation and evaluation activities across large-scale testbeds and local PoCs yields a set of system-level lessons, derived through cross-PoC analysis, that are broadly applicable to future 6G research and innovation initiatives.

While individual components (e.g., IML, MAS, accelerated network functions etc.) reached their targeted TRLs, one significant challenge was end-to-end integration across the different platform layers, technology and administrative domains. The stable operation of the system was achieved by the coordination of the orchestration, management, control and data planes, with clear separation of concerns, appropriate interface definition and version alignment between the different components. This confirms that in ultra-flexible and modular 6G systems, integration complexity is at least as critical as algorithmic innovation.

Data plane programmability emerged as a powerful enabler for flexibility and innovation in networking, as showcased in D5.3, allowing advanced in-network functions, fast service adaptation and performance assurance, increased network visibility etc. At the same time, the DESIRE6G evaluations confirm the “no free lunch” principle. Increased programmability inevitably comes with trade-offs in terms of performance and resource usage, as multiple functions share the same pipeline, competing for limited stages and resources. Line-rate operation and deterministic behaviour require hardware-aware pipeline design, limited state, and careful separation between fast-path and slow-path logic. These findings highlight the opportunity for software-hardware co-design, where programmable abstractions are explicitly aligned with hardware capabilities to achieve both flexibility and high performance in future 6G platforms.

The evaluations reported in D5.3 validate the hypothesis that effective operation of complex 6G systems requires hierarchical control loops operating at multiple timescales, employing AI-driven decision making. Real-time control actions with strict latency constraints, such as congestion control, packet scheduling, and traffic steering, can be executed directly in the programmable data plane at sub-millisecond timescales. At longer near-real-time timescales, local infrastructure-level loops enable AI-assisted optimization for functions such as scaling, failover, heavy-hitter mitigation, etc., while service-level loops continuously adapt end-to-end behaviour based on KPI-driven observability and distributed

AI reasoning. At the highest level, non-real-time management and orchestration loops perform cross-domain optimization, policy enforcement, and AI workflow management, addressing conditions that cannot be resolved locally. Essentially, the results show that AI is most effective when embedded within these closed-loop, multi-timescale control structures with continuous observability and feedback, enabling adaptive behaviour under dynamic and uncertain conditions. AI techniques significantly enhance adaptability and automation; however, their effectiveness depends on consistent telemetry, well-defined feature extraction pipelines, and alignment between training assumptions and operational conditions. This confirms that AI-native, multi-timescale control is a foundational architectural principle for achieving responsive and scalable 6G systems across heterogeneous domains and workloads.

The evaluations also confirm that both scalability and footprint extension in 6G systems can be achieved through distributed decision-making, federated orchestration (even in the absence of pre-established trust), and domain-level autonomy. The use of multi-agent systems, blockchain-enabled federated orchestration effectively reduces operational bottlenecks, while introducing additional coordination overhead (e.g., agent deployment, DLT interactions etc.). Explicit federation mechanisms and secure policy-aware east-west inter-domain interfaces are therefore key design elements.

Finally, D5.3 confirms that DESIRE6G applies cloud-native principles across both the execution environment and the data plane, enabling containerized application workloads, network functions and modular user-plane components to be deployed, composed, and dynamically adapted under unified management and orchestration over heterogeneous hardware resources (CPUs, DPUs, ASICs). Cloud-native execution (containerized NFs/apps, IML/k8s-based deployment, microservice-oriented SMO) is a strong enabler for rapid integration, portability across heterogeneous testbeds, and elastic scaling of services. At the same time, the experiments highlight that cloud-native deployment and operation come with non-trivial operational trade-offs such as (i) service chaining and lifecycle management overheads, (ii) observed time variability in loop execution due to distributed execution, shared resource scheduling, and event-driven coordination, (iii) contention for compute and network resources. The results therefore indicate the need for a cloud-native, but hardware- and time-aware approach, combining cloud-native mechanisms for service lifecycle management, while ensuring predictable performance through careful scheduling/affinity policies, deployment workflows, and programmable data-plane acceleration where needed.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable presented the final and comprehensive validation of the DESIRE6G architecture, demonstrating its technical maturity, operational readiness, and suitability for next-generation 6G networks. Building upon the partial integrations and preliminary experiments reported in D5.2, the work performed in Year 3 has completed the deployment, integration, and evaluation of all major DESIRE6G components across global and local testbeds. The results confirm that the project has successfully achieved the objectives set for WP5 and has delivered a fully functional platform capable of supporting advanced 6G service scenarios.

The two integrated demonstrators—Augmented Reality with Perceived Zero Latency and the Real-Time Digital Twin for Robotics—represent the core validation activities of the project. Both demonstrators implemented the full DESIRE6G architectural stack with a noticeable integration effort involving more than fifteen novel modules designed and developed by the project. Moreover, they required coordinated operation of programmable RAN, deterministic transport, edge computing, pervasive monitoring, and intelligent control loops. Their successful execution validates key architectural principles, including:

- support for ultra-low-latency and high-reliability services,
- dynamic and programmable data-plane behaviour,
- end-to-end service orchestration across multiple administrative domains, and
- AI-assisted service assurance through multi-agent systems.

In addition, the ten Proof-of-Concepts provided targeted evaluation of the architecture's enabling technologies, including SmartNIC offloading, secure multi-agent attestation, AI workload offloading, SLA-to-Intent translation, scalable SMO microservices, and CU-UP acceleration. These PoCs confirm that the DESIRE6G architecture is capable of supporting heterogeneous operational environments and performance-critical vertical use cases. They also demonstrate the modularity and extensibility of the architecture, which are essential for future 6G deployments.

Across all experiments, the platform exhibited strong alignment with the project's KPI targets. The testbeds consistently achieved millisecond-scale end-to-end latency, in-band network and control, reliable transport through PREOF and TSN mechanisms, scalable orchestration pipelines, and fast anomaly detection and reaction times (<10 ms and ~25 ms, respectively). These results provide

quantitative evidence that the DESIRE6G platform meets or exceeds the performance requirements defined in the DoA, reinforcing its relevance to future 6G technologies.

The work carried out in this deliverable has also identified important lessons learned. In particular, the evaluation highlighted the clear distinction between delays inherent to DESIRE6G's internal closed-loop mechanisms—typically tens of milliseconds—and those originating from external orchestration systems such as RIC/xAPP interactions, which may introduce multi-second delays. These insights will guide further optimization efforts and inform future research on distributed 6G control mechanisms. Additional lessons include the need for interface harmonization, improved synchronization of programmable data-plane elements, and robust trust anchors for secure agent deployment.

Overall, D5.3 confirms that DESIRE6G has reached a high level of technical and integration maturity, fulfilling the objectives of WP5 and demonstrating the feasibility of the architectural approach proposed by the project. The outcomes provide a strong foundation for future developments within the SNS ecosystem and offer concrete, validated contributions to Europe's strategic roadmap toward 6G. The validated components, methodologies, and insights reported here will support follow-up activities, potential standardization efforts, and wider adoption of the DESIRE6G concepts in forthcoming 6G research and innovation programmes.

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